

Seminole County Public Schools Exceptional Student Education Curriculum Project Evaluation Report

Abstract

The Exceptional Student Education Curriculum Project (ESECP) is a whole-school approach for students with exceptionalities that merges evidence-based behavioral approaches and traditional instructional pedagogy. This quasi-experimental and mixed methods study was used to examine implementation and impact on student outcomes for students in Exceptional Student Education (ESE) in 13 ESECP schools compared to similar ESE students in 13 schools implementing business-as-usual programming. Findings show that school and district staff had a shared understanding of ESECP project components and elements associated with implementation success, district staff generally characterized the quality of ESECP training as excellent, and there were several facilitators for successful implementation. However, there were challenges implementing ESECP with fidelity, including not meeting expectations for student lesson progress and attendance. Implementation improved over time. No significant differences in mathematics or reading achievement after one year were found between students in ESECP schools and their peers in comparison schools. Students in the developmental domain in ESECP schools made slightly more gains on listening comprehension scores compared to gains for students in comparison schools, based on descriptive analyses. Educators and parents reported positive effects of ESECP participation, including improved student social and life skills and improved student behavior.

SEMINOLE COUNTY PUBLIC SCHOOLS EXCEPTIONAL STUDENT EDUCATION CURRICULUM PROJECT

EVALUATION REPORT

PREPARED FOR:

SEMINOLE COUNTY PUBLIC SCHOOLS
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MAY 2025

**SEMINOLE COUNTY PUBLIC SCHOOLS
EXCEPTIONAL STUDENT EDUCATION CURRICULUM PROJECT**

EVALUATION REPORT

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Exceptional Student Education Curriculum Project (ESECP) is a whole-school approach for students with exceptionalities that merges evidence-based behavioral approaches and traditional instructional pedagogy. The project is designed to establish a consistent approach to selecting curriculum that is appropriate for students in exceptional student education (ESE). The model uses research-based principles of Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA) and Direct Instruction approaches. It involves a partnership with the Pennsylvania Training and Technical Assistance Network (PATTAN) and the National Institute for Direct Instruction (NIFDI) to incorporate evidence-based instruction in a systematic way through a novel school-based approach. Teachers receive ongoing training and support, including weekly consultation, to implement the ESECP. Students are assigned to least restrictive environments based on priority educational need, using assessments to understand students' level of academic functioning.

Once students are placed, they receive academic support in either the Developmental Domain or Academic Domain. This placement allows provision of instruction that meets students where they are and supports progress. Students in the Developmental Domain receive Intensive Trial Training, Natural Environment Training, and Mand Training. Daily probes allow students to demonstrate mastery if they can perform skills on the first try on three consecutive days. Students in the Academic Domain receive curriculum-based assessment to determine their instructional level. Students participate in up to three groups focused on specific target areas each day through Direct Instruction. Progress monitoring data collection is ongoing and student placement is reviewed regularly.

The implementation and evaluation of the ESECP was funded through the Education Innovation Research (EIR) Early-Phase grant program under the U.S. Department of Education for the academic years 2019/20 through 2023/24. The ESECP was designed to accomplish the following nine goals:

1. Prepare school administration, all staff, and students for implementation of the ESECP in 13 schools;
2. Prepare ESE teachers and support staff at 13 schools to implement the ESECP;
3. Implement Evidence-Based Practices for students with disabilities (SWD) with fidelity;
4. Increase parent involvement in the education process provided by the public schools and implement a parent training plan to transfer skills to the home environment;
5. Increase ESE teacher job satisfaction by consultation, ongoing training, and establishing professional learning communities;
6. Improve academic achievement for SWD on standardized, curriculum-based, and state measures of performance;
7. Disseminate findings and contribute to the research base on best practices for SWD;
8. Manualize the ESECP procedures to facilitate the ease of replication of the model in other districts;
9. Create a sustainability plan to ensure longevity of the ESECP should research demonstrate the effectiveness of the model.

RMC Research Corporation (RMC) conducted an external evaluation of the ESECP using a quasi-experimental design and mixed-method data collection to examine implementation and outcomes. During Year 1 (2019/20), RMC developed data collection mechanisms and pilot matching procedures.

Year 2 (2020/21) served as a pilot year. This report contains information about data collected during Years 3 (2021/22) through 5 (2023/24), which includes three cohorts of schools for confirmatory and exploratory impact analyses and a study of implementation. RMC analyzed data collected in 13 ESECP schools and 13 comparison schools, including: student administrative data, parent surveys, educator surveys, teacher focus groups, interviews with district administrators, school administrators, and project staff, and document review to examine implementation and outcomes during each school's first year of implementation, and after two and three years.

FINDINGS: IMPLEMENTATION

School and district staff had a shared understanding of ESECP project components and elements associated with implementation success. Interview and focus group respondents discussed training provided to TOAs, BAs, administrators, and ESE educators, parent communication, master schedules, assessment to place students and ongoing progress monitoring, and the need for successful incorporation of routines into classrooms. For example, interview and focus group respondents shared that when schools successfully created a master schedule to integrate the components required by the project, educators struggled less and had the time needed for project implementation.

SCPS staff generally characterized the quality of ESECP training as excellent. District administrators, school administrators, and district ESECP staff described training provided to TOAs, BAs, ESE educators, school administrators, and paraeducators including: skills training; pre-coaching site visits; and single-day, multi-day, and monthly training activities. Respondents reported that training for TOAs and BAs was sufficient and described deep involvement in program implementation and oversight by project leadership. Nearly all respondents stated that the hands-on components of the trainings worked best for educators to support their understanding of the curriculum and implementation. Respondents also emphasized that the training included well-defined program goals, outlined the program processes, and was clear on how activities should be implemented. On average, educator survey ratings of professional learning activities were consistently between “good” and “very good” across most activities with highest ratings for summer trainings and consultations from TOAs or BAs.

ESECP offered more training to parents and caregivers relative to comparison schools. Average survey ratings from educators in ESECP schools agreed suggested stronger agreement that training was offered to parents and caregivers than those in comparison schools. Interview and focus group respondents noted that many ESE educators were providing the level of communication with parents as expected within ESECP. Parents reported having meetings about their children's IEP up to three times a year, with some reporting that they had just one meeting per year. Parent training and communication was a key component of the intervention and the study schools met the threshold for this intervention.

Collaborative support among district ESECP staff; collaboration between school and district ESECP staff; high-quality materials; and the ability of the program to meet the needs of students regardless of their level of function or skill deficit facilitated successful ESECP implementation. Interview and focus group respondents reported being pleased with the quality of the ESECP programming. Several mentioned that they appreciated that programming was evidence-based and offered a structured curriculum for developmental students. Many respondents shared that in most developmental classrooms (in non-ESECP schools) there was a lack of guidelines or supports, and many educators looked for their own materials to use with their students. Additionally, respondents said that students receiving ESE services in non-ESECP schools engaged in Tier 3 programming for academic intervention,

but that it was more generalized and did not focus on the individual needs of students. Respondents felt that the training and support provided by ESECP helped everyone involved with the project, from district-staff to ESE educators, work together to identify implementation issues, review data to support students' skill development, and support classroom implementation.

Project leaders made substantial progress toward disseminating information about the ESECP. Project leaders communicated with several other Florida districts interested in implementing the ESECP, providing information about key components of the project. ESECP staff presented at local, statewide, and national meetings, including an SCPS School Board meeting, Florida Association for Behavior Analysis conference, EIR Project Director's Meeting, and the American Educational Research Association annual meeting.

FINDINGS: FIDELITY AND DOSAGE

Educators reported challenges implementing ESECP with fidelity. Respondents understood the need for fidelity and the project team and educators took multiple steps to ensure that ESECP classroom implementation proceeded as expected. However, educators reported challenges meeting expectations of ESECP while also accommodating student needs. Educators also reported challenges maintaining the pace of lessons due to factors outside their control, including testing or other school-level disruptions, student behaviors causing disruptions, lack of understanding of the unit and/or lesson, and student transitions among lesson groups. Some educators expressed the desire to have more autonomy over their classrooms, suggesting that they knew best what worked for their students.

ESE educators reported that educator and administrator buy-in contributed to implementation of ESECP activities with fidelity. Without strong buy-in from school administrators and ESE educators, respondents said it was much more difficult to ensure that the program was implemented with fidelity. Administrator and educator buy-in led to creating and following a master schedule, general education teacher awareness of how time was used, better attendance at trainings, and stronger collaboration with coaching staff.

ESECP students did not receive the expected number of lessons, but neither their lesson progress nor their attendance was related to outcomes. Direct instruction groups were held 49% to 59% of the scheduled time, and students were in groups that were 32 to 54 lessons behind schedule, on average.

Site review scores suggested that ESECP implementation improved over time. Classrooms improved between the first and second semester (Cohort 1 improved from 58% to 64%, Cohort 2 improved from 54% to 64%, and Cohort 3 improved from 70% to 78% across academic and developmental classrooms, on average). In addition, the academic classrooms improved implementation across cohorts even in the first semester, from 61% in Cohort 1 to 77% in Cohort 3. Cohort 2 developmental classrooms experienced the largest change from the first semester (31%) to second semester (71%).

FINDINGS: IMPACT AND PERCEIVED IMPACTS

No significant differences in mathematics or reading achievement were found between students in ESECP schools and their peers in comparison schools. No significant effects on reading or mathematics overall scores after one year of the intervention were found. Examination of the interactions between treatment and student characteristics that were included in final analytic models for each subject area

also revealed no significant effects. There were also no significant differences between students in ESECP and their peers in comparison schools two or three years after their first year of exposure.

Students in the developmental domain in ESECP schools made slightly more gains on listening comprehension scores compared to gains for students in comparison schools, based on descriptive analyses. All other point differences on tests and subtests were small, suggesting that students in the Developmental Domain experienced similar outcomes to those in the comparison condition.

Interview and focus group respondents reported that the ESECP helped to close gaps between students receiving ESE services and their peers, contributed to student skill development in self-contained classrooms, and increased student inclusion with their peers in general education classrooms. On surveys, educators agreed or strongly agreed, on average, that the ESECP improved student language development, student social outcomes, behavior outcomes, academic engagement, academic achievement, parent engagement in student learning, and parent satisfaction.

Respondents reported that the ESECP facilitated better relationships between ESE educators and students. Reasons given for improved relationships included individualization of instruction and educators better understanding student strengths and areas for growth. Respondents reported that ESE educators built relationships and rapport with students at the beginning of instruction to gain buy-in which resulted in students wanting to be in school and engaged in their learning. Use of student data to guide instruction was reported as contributing to better educator understanding of student capabilities and needs and provision of needed supports.

Almost all respondents mentioned that the ESECP had a positive impact on students' social and life skills. Respondents shared that students improved their ability to communicate and express requests and that they developed skills that led to their participation in less restrictive environments. Respondents also reported that students saw the gains they were making and became more engaged with the curriculum and in the classroom, which led to increased interactions with their peers. Some parents shared that their children were less shy, made friends, and participated in activities with other children. A few parents of children with behavioral issues shared that their children become more respectful to their educators, followed instructions better, and decreased the frequency and intensity of their behavioral issues.

Educators shared that the ESECP had a beneficial impact on student behavior in the classroom. Respondents reported that classrooms ran smoothly due to the ESECP structure and that educators and students knew what they were doing and what they were going to do next. Educators mentioned that were accountable for how they engaged with students at various points in time during the lesson and throughout the day. Students were familiar with the schedule and benefitted from the consistency and routine, which included regular feedback, praise, and positive reinforcement—and those elements helped to minimize behavioral issues.

On average, 90 to 95% of educators in ESECP schools reported that they were likely to continue teaching, in their current school, and in special education, compared to 80% of educators in comparison schools. Of the ESE educators assigned to ESECP schools, 74% to 85% remained in the same school from one year to the next. Over three-quarters of educators held the same job across years and a similar pattern was found with those who held the same job in the same school.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Refine key components.
2. Continue to offer high-quality training to TOAs, BAs, administrators, and ESE educators.
3. Consider ways to strengthen administrator buy-in.
4. Consider ways to allow ESE educators more flexibility to meet student needs while staying on track with lesson progress.
5. Document bright spots and successes.
6. Share the ESECP implementation manual with other districts interested in using this model.

INTRODUCTION

This section provides background information about the Seminole County Public Schools Exceptional Student Education Curriculum Project, including information about program implementation and the evaluation during the 2021/22 through 2023/24 academic years.

BACKGROUND

The Exceptional Student Education Curriculum Project (ESECP) in Seminole County Public Schools (SCPS) is a whole-school approach for students with exceptionalities that merges evidence-based behavioral approaches and traditional instructional pedagogy. The project is designed to establish a consistent approach to selecting curriculum that is appropriate for students in exceptional student education (ESE) through training and coaching for consultants, administrators, teachers, schools, and parents to improve academic outcomes for students receiving ESE.

The implementation and evaluation of the ESECP was funded through the Education Innovation Research (EIR) Early-Phase grant program under the U.S. Department of Education for the academic years 2019/20 through 2023/24. RMC Research Corporation (RMC) conducted an external evaluation using a quasi-experimental design to examine impact on student and teacher outcomes. Impact analyses and associated reporting were conducted by RMC, independently of SCPS. The impact study was designed to document effectiveness of the whole-school ESECP approach, with the potential to meet standards with reservations under the review criteria established by the U.S. Department of Education Institute of Education Sciences *What Works Clearinghouse*. The study also provides information about ESECP implementation that may be used to guide program improvement and replication, and to inform priorities for future research.

EXCEPTIONAL STUDENT EDUCATION CURRICULUM PROJECT (ESECP)

The ESECP model uses research-based principles of Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA) and Direct Instruction approaches. SCPS partnered with the Pennsylvania Training and Technical Assistance Network (PaTTAN) and the National Institute for Direct Instruction (NIFDI) to incorporate evidence-based instruction systematically through a novel school-based approach. Under the ESECP model, teachers receive ongoing training and support, including weekly consultation, to support implementation. Students are assigned to least restrictive environments based on priority educational need, using assessments to understand their level of academic functioning. Once students are placed, they receive academic support in either the Developmental Domain or Academic Domain. This placement allows provision of instruction that meets students where they are and supports their progress. Students in the Developmental Domain receive Intensive Trial Training, Natural Environment Training, and Mand Training. Daily probes allow students to demonstrate mastery by performing skills on their first try on 3 consecutive days. Students in the Academic Domain receive a curriculum-based assessment to determine their instructional level. Students participate in up to three groups focused on specific target areas each day through Direct Instruction. Progress monitoring data collection is ongoing, and student placement is reviewed regularly.

SCPS aimed to accomplish nine primary goals through implementation and evaluation of ECESP (Exhibit 1).

EXHIBIT 1. ESECP GOALS

- Part 1:** Prepare 13 elementary schools to implement an evidence-based curriculum model for all ESE students.
 - Goal 1:** Prepare school administration, all staff, and students for implementation of the ESECP in 13 schools.
 - Goal 2:** Prepare ESE teachers and support staff at 13 schools to implement the ESECP.
 - Part 2:** Achieve high fidelity implementation in 13 elementary schools leading to increased parent/teacher satisfaction as well as improved academic achievement on state, standardized, and curriculum-based measures.
 - Goal 3:** Implement Evidence-Based Practices for students with disabilities (SWD) with fidelity.
 - Goal 4:** Increase parent involvement in the education process provided by the public schools and implement a parent training plan to transfer skills to the home environment.
 - Goal 5:** Increase ESE teacher job satisfaction by consultation, ongoing training, and establishing professional learning communities.
 - Goal 6:** Improve academic achievement for SWD on standardized, curriculum-based, and state measures of performance.
 - Part 3:** Disseminate findings and manualized procedures, and implement a sustainability plan districtwide.
 - Goal 7:** Disseminate findings and contribute to the research base on best practices for SWD (in partnership with RMC).
 - Goal 8:** Manualize the ESECP procedures to facilitate replication of the model in other districts.
 - Goal 9:** Create a sustainability plan to ensure longevity of the ESECP should research demonstrate the effectiveness of the model.
-

RMC and ESECP project leaders worked in close collaboration to develop a logic model that specifies key components, mediators, and outcomes to be examined in confirmatory and exploratory analyses. Along with identification of key components, RMC and ESECP leaders created an implementation fidelity matrix specifying indicators of fidelity associated with each component. The team also identified data sources associated with each indicator, plans for collecting data, and thresholds for adequate implementation.

The ESECP logic model (Exhibit 2) specifies outcomes for the district and schools, teachers, students, and parents and reflects the expectation that teachers who participate in the ESECP through the whole-school approach will be able to design, implement, and evaluate instruction for SWD in the district. Key components of the intervention include training and coaching activities for ESECP coaches, training and engagement of school administrators, training for ESE staff at schools, parent training and communication, and district monitoring and support. ESECP coaches include Teachers on Assignment (TOAs) and Behavior Analysts (BAs) who attend training/coaching institutes and training sessions, engage in site visits prior to leading coaching, working with partners to proceed through training, and once trained, conduct coaching and site reviews with administrators and ESE instructors at implementing schools. Administrators participate in pre-implementation meetings and a training institute and are required to sign a collaborative agreement. ESE staff (including teachers and paraprofessionals) receive initial and ongoing training and sign the collaborative agreement. The district offers parent training sessions based on needs assessments and a Parent Information Night. These activities are supported through district monitoring and support, which includes the assignment of staff to support implementation, allocation of resources, scheduling and screening site reviews, and monitoring progress for educators, TOAs, BAs, and coaches on a regular basis. Through mediators including school support, classroom implementation, teacher engagement, student engagement, and parent engagement, these resources and key components are expected to lead to improved school and

district ESECP programming and sustainability. Specifically, these inputs and activities are expected to improve student verbal ability and academic achievement; increase teacher capacity for designing, implementing, and evaluating instruction for SWD, and improve parent ability to support students and engage in student learning. Project activities are also expected to contribute to the research base of evidence-based practices for students with disabilities.

EXHIBIT 2. ESECP LOGIC MODEL

PRIOR RESEARCH

Early findings associated with the ESECP are promising. District analyses of 2018/19 pilot ESECP data for 78 students with disabilities indicated that these students experienced growth in curriculum-based measures that were close to or greater than average-grade level growth in reading and mathematics. Analysis of district *i-Ready* diagnostic data suggest that the average reading scale score gain of ESECP participants was just below that for all students; the average mathematics scale score gain was higher than that for all students.

THIS EVALUATION

This evaluation examines the impact and implementation of ESECP for students in Grades K-5 from 2021/22 through 2023/24. During 2019/20, RMC developed data collection mechanisms and pilot matching procedures. Pilot data collection procedures were tested in 2020/21, and these data were used to examine findings from a pilot cohort. This report focuses on data collected during 2021/22 through 2023/24, which served as the three primary cohorts for the implementation and impact studies. The study methodology is presented next, followed by findings, conclusions, and recommendations.

METHODOLOGY

This section describes the evaluation questions, evaluation design, intervention and comparison conditions, quantitative and qualitative data, and methodologies used for data collection and analyses.

EVALUATION QUESTIONS

The study was guided by 11 evaluation questions about fidelity and impact (Exhibit 3). This report presents findings from analysis of data collected during the 2021/22, 2022/23, and 2023/24 academic years, providing evidence that addresses each research question.

EXHIBIT 3. EVALUATION QUESTIONS

Evaluation Questions	
Fidelity	(1) To what extent is the ESECP implemented with fidelity in participating schools and classrooms over time?
	(2) How does ESECP implementation fidelity vary according to characteristics of teachers and schools?
	(3) What factors serve to facilitate or impede ESECP implementation?
Confirmatory	(4) How does the ESECP affect student academic outcomes (in reading and mathematics) after one year of participation? ¹
Impact	(5) How does the ESECP affect other student academic outcomes (e.g., performance on district- and state-administered assessments, and oral language fluency ²) after one year of participation?
	(6) To what extent does the ESECP affect teacher retention, practice, and satisfaction after one year of participation?
	(7) To what extent does the ESECP affect parent involvement in schooling and parent satisfaction after one year of their students' participation?
	(8) How does the impact of the ESECP on student outcomes change over time?
	(9) How are the effects of participation in the ESECP mediated by the nature and extent of implementation and by interim measures of student progress (e.g., school attendance)?
	(10) How does implementation of the ESECP change for each school over time, how does the ESECP disseminate research findings, and how does SCPS transfer responsibilities for independent sustainability of activities within each school?
	Subgroups

Evaluation Questions 1-3 assess the fidelity of implementation of ESECP. Evaluation Question 4 focuses the impact of the ESECP on student outcomes for students in schools that implemented ESECP compared to matched peers in schools that provided business-as-usual programming. Evaluation Questions 5-10 are exploratory, designed to provide correlational evidence of impact on student,

¹ WWC Outcome domains: reading achievement and mathematic achievement.

² Students who are placed in the Developmental Domain only.

teacher, and parent outcomes as well as the relationship between implementation and outcomes. Evaluation Question 10 addresses opportunities for continuous improvement and sustainability. Evaluation Question 11 examines differential impact of ESECP on student subgroups to better understand for whom the intervention may be most applicable; this question also examines characteristics of teachers and schools that may be associated with greater ESECP impact.

DESIGN

Because the ESECP intervention is a whole-school model, the study used a quasi-experimental approach with matched comparison schools, designed to meet What Works Clearinghouse Standards (with reservations). Prior to the study, SCPS purposefully identified 11 ESECP schools to begin implementation during 2021/22 through 2023/24 (3 to 4 schools each year; Exhibit 4) based on their readiness for implementation³. Comparison schools that had not yet implemented ESECP were also identified.

EXHIBIT 4. SUMMARY OF ACADEMIC YEARS AND COHORTS

Academic Year	Cohort
2019/20	NA
2020/21	Pilot
2021/22	1
2022/23	2
2023/24	3

To test confirmatory and exploratory impacts on students in the academic domain, students in ESECP schools were matched at baseline with a sample of students in comparison schools using propensity score matching. Quantitative outcomes included in impact analyses are based on administrative and survey data. Confirmatory impact analyses focus on outcomes after one year of participation in ESECP. Exploratory analysis of outcome data collected from intervention and matched comparison students during each year of the study allowed for examination of program impact on student outcomes after students participated in multiple years of the intervention, changes in school and teacher implementation across multiple years of participation in the intervention, the relationship between intervention participation and student outcomes accounting for quantitative measures of fidelity of implementation, and longitudinal growth of intervention students.

During the project, RMC and SCPS project leaders collaboratively refined the logic model and fidelity thresholds. RMC collected data from interviews, focus groups, educator surveys, parent trainings, and document review to describe implementation, inform continuous improvement and test fidelity thresholds.

INTERVENTION AND COMPARISON CONDITIONS

In the intervention (ESECP) condition, educators in participating schools committed to implementation of ESECP. SCPS provided training and coaching for ESECP coaches, administrators, instructors, and parents as outlined in the logic model. Schools were expected to provide sufficient instructional minutes using their master schedules throughout the academic year. Instructors and administrators received

³ Schools for each cohort were reviewed for readiness and updated annually prior to beginning the ESECP implementation.

training and support from TOAs and BAs. Through baseline assessment and progress monitoring, instructors placed students in the least restrictive environments, and used specific classroom organization, planning, and instructional approaches, as well as approaches for engaging students. All students who qualified for ESE services in Grades K-5 in intervention schools were expected to receive instruction through the whole-school ESECP model, including developmentally appropriate supports through the developmental or academic domains⁴.

Matched comparison students in comparison schools received treatment-as-usual. Some students were identified for ESE services, other students were eligible to be comparison students if they scored two or more grade levels below in reading or mathematics (but may not have had an IEP). In SCPS, treatment-as-usual in comparison schools does not include the key components of ESECP.

SETTING

SCPS is a suburban district in Florida. The study took place within general education classrooms, self-contained classrooms, and small group instructional settings in public elementary schools.

PRE-REGISTRATION OF THE STUDY DESIGN AND INDEPENDENCE OF THE IMPACT EVALUATION

This study was pre-registered through the [Registry of Efficacy and Effectiveness Studies](#), protocol #6600.1v1. The project team made decisions to use the iReady as the confirmatory outcome measure prior to pre-registration; information about this decision is documented in Appendix A.

RMC conducted the impact evaluation independently from SCPS stakeholders. No members of the evaluation team were involved in the development or implementation of the intervention. The evaluator collected outcome data directly from the district data team (without involvement of the intervention developer), conducted all matching procedures, and conducted all analyses of findings.

DATA COLLECTION

RMC collected **administrative data** from SCPS for the 2021/22 through 2023/24 academic years, including student-level demographic information, formative assessment scores on district-administered content-based measures (i-Ready) for fall (prior to intervention) and spring (following intervention), state reading and mathematics and alternative assessments⁵, and full rosters students in intervention and comparison schools which were used to identify eligible students. The timetable of measurement was consistent across the intervention and comparison condition and across cohorts.⁶

Information about implementation (including information used to document **fidelity and quality of implementation**) was collected to align with the logic model (see the Introduction section) and the

⁴ Although it was not the focus of this study, students could also be identified for ESE services through a Medical or Behavioral domain, which included additional supports for those specific needs.

⁵ The Florida Department of Education re-scaled the alternate assessment in the 2023/24 academic year from and the two versions of the assessment are not comparable.

⁶ Assessors hired by SCPS administered the Woodcock-Johnson Oral Language, Broad Reading, and Broad Math content area assessments in spring 2021, fall 2021 (to new students), spring 2022, spring 2023, and spring 2024 to students in the Developmental domain from the ESECP intervention or comparison schools. The assessment administrators did not provide the intervention. Data from these assessments were not reported due to the small sample size of students with scores at pre and post ($n < 10$).

fidelity matrix developed by the project team (Appendix B). Data and associated documentation about the 2021/22 through 2023/24 academic years were provided by the project leader as evidence for each indicator and key component. Information included site review⁷ results for and information about the administration of groups, lesson progress, documentation associated with project activities such as parent trainings and dissemination activities, and other indicators. Indicators of potential mediators of outcomes were also collected.

Educator surveys were administered at all study schools each year (i.e., educators in Cohort 1 schools had the chance to complete surveys each fall and spring in 2021/22 through 2023/24; Cohort 2 schools in 2022/23 through 2023/24; and Cohort 3 schools in 2023/24) See Exhibit 5.

EXHIBIT 5. NUMBER OF EDUCATOR SURVEY RESPONSES BY CONDITION, COHORT, AND YEAR

	2021/22			2022/23			2023/24		
	Number of Respondents								
	ESECP	Comparison	Total	ESECP	Comparison	Total	ESECP	Comparison	Total
Cohort 1									
Fall Survey	9	5	14	10	3	13	2	0	2
Spring Survey	11	9	20	6	3	9	7	0	7
Analytic Sample ^a	7	5	12	5	1	6	1	0	1
Cohort 2									
Fall Survey	-	-	-	6	2	8	4	0	4
Spring Survey	-	-	-	14	3	17	8	1	9
Analytic Sample	-	-	-	6	1	7	4	0	4
Cohort 3									
Fall Survey	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	1	5
Spring Survey	-	-	-	-	-	-	8	2	10
Analytic Sample	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	1	4

Note. Responses were counted if at least one item beyond demographic questions was answered. ^aAnalytic samples for each cohort include educators who completed both fall and spring surveys.

For each fall and spring survey administration, RMC sent initial email invitations and multiple reminders to non-respondents to increase participation. For 2021/22, RMC sent 59 invitations and received 12 partial or complete responses to both the fall and spring survey for a response rate of 20%. In 2022/23, RMC sent 100 invitations and received 13 partial or complete responses across cohorts to both the fall and spring survey for a response rate of 13%. In 2023/24, RMC sent 90 invitations (fall) and 88 invitations (spring) and received 9 partial or complete responses across cohorts to both the fall and spring survey for a response rate of 10%.

Qualitative data were collected each spring. Cohort 1 data were collected virtually in spring 2022, and data from Cohorts 2 and 3 were collected primarily in-person with virtual supplements in spring 2023 and 2024, respectively. Data collection included interviews with school administrators and other staff involved in the implementation of ESECP programming (assistant principals, coaches, and school counselors), ESECP educators, district and project administrators and key staff (TOA and BOA), and

⁷ Site reviews are conducted each spring and fall by TOAs and BAs to support fidelity of implementation.

parents. Several attempts were made to recruit those who were not available during the on-site visit to participate in a virtual interview or focus group.

Observations of 12 parent training sessions were conducted virtually during 2021/22, 2022/23, and 2023/24.

Document review was conducted and included review documents supporting dissemination and sustainability of ESECP that were collected from project leaders. Dissemination documents included:

- Poster presentation at the American Education Research Association (AERA) in April 2022;
- Presentation at the Florida Association on Behavior Analysis (FABA) in September 2022;
- Presentation on effective partnerships between evaluators and project teams at the EIR Project Directors and Evaluators Technical Assistance Meeting in October 2022;
- Poster presentation at AERA in April 2023; and
- Roundtable presentation at AERA in April 2025.

QUANTITATIVE MEASURES

Quantitative measures included various student assessments and demographic information for students, ESE instructors, and schools.

i-Ready Diagnostic Assessments. SCPS administered these formative curriculum-based assessments three times per year to students with a verbal ability of at least 48 months. These standardized assessments are part of typical ESE implementation in the district. Assessments take 45–60 minutes per student to complete and are computer adaptive. Scores include percentile scores, Item Response Theory-based scores, developmental benchmarks, Lexile scores⁸ (for literacy content areas), scale scores, and on-grade achievement level placements. Subscales for reading include phonological awareness, phonics, high frequency words, vocabulary, comprehension, and comprehension of informational text. Subscales for mathematics include numbers and operations, algebraic thinking, measurement and data, and geometry. The National Center for Intensive Intervention (2021) reports evidence of reliability and validity for students in Grades K-5.

Florida Standards Assessment/Florida Standards Alternate Assessment. The Florida Department of Education administered the standardized computer-based Florida Standards Assessment (FSA) through 2021 and subsequently the Florida Assessment of Student Thinking (FAST) progress monitoring. The Florida Standards Alternate Assessment (FSAA) was also administered annually statewide through 2022/23. Students in Grades 3-10 for English Language Arts and Grades 3-8 for Mathematics complete the assessments which measure student gains and progress. The FSA has documented reliability and validity evidence (Florida Department of Education, 2018), as does the FAST (Florida Department of Education, 2023⁹). Students with significant cognitive disabilities may be allowed to take the Alternate Assessment. Students receive a scale score for each subject, total raw score, points earned, and a performance level from 1 (inadequate) to 5 (mastery).

Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test (PPVT). Students in the developmental domain completed the PPVT. The PPVT is a norm-referenced assessment that assesses receptive vocabulary for individuals aged 2 ½ and up. Individuals are presented with a card with 4 pictures and asked to respond by selecting the

⁸ Lexile measure is the numeric representation of an individual's reading ability or a text's readability (or difficulty).

⁹ [BEST-2223-Vol4.pdf](#)

picture that best illustrates the meaning of a given word. The assessment has evidence of internal consistency, alternate form reliability, test-retest reliability, and split-half reliability. Content validity and convergent validity have also been established for the PPVT (Dunn & Dunn, 2013).

Woodcock Johnson IV. The Woodcock-Johnson IV is a system of standardized assessments of student abilities in particular content areas, with evidence of reliability and validity (McGrew, LaForte, & Shrank, 2014). These assessments will be conducted in addition to typical assessments given to students for the purposes of the study. Assessment administrators hired by SCPS administered the Oral Language content area assessments each spring and fall. The assessment administrators do not administer the intervention. The Oral Language assessment is used to identify student strength and weakness areas with expressive language and the reading and mathematics assessments identify achievement in those content areas. The assessments are appropriate for ages two plus. Administration takes approximately 60 minutes for students in the academic domain (Broad Reading, Broad Math, Oral Language) and 30 minutes for students in the developmental domain (Oral Language). Multiple scores are reported, including W-score, which was used for the current study.

Student Characteristics. To examine baseline equivalence between the intervention and comparison conditions and to serve as covariates and outcomes in models that assess impact, student-level achievement and demographic data elements expected to be related to outcome measures were collected. In addition to assessment scores listed above, these data elements include: school, gender, grade level, race/ethnicity, IEPs¹⁰, English learner status, attendance rate, student primary exceptionality, curriculum circle (participation in the developmental and/or academic domain), the extent to which the student received instruction with non-disabled peers, and length of time receiving ESE services.

Educator Characteristics. Educator characteristics that may affect outcomes were collected including retention in the district and school, race/ethnicity, gender, years of experience in SCPS, years of experience overall, highest level of education, type of classroom, and certification type and area.

School Characteristics. School characteristics that may affect outcomes were collected including percentage of English language learners, students in special education, students designated as gifted and talented, in racial/ethnic groups, and qualified for free or reduced-price meals; aggregate academic performance on state assessments (for ESE and non-ESE students); total number of students; and grade range.

Educator Survey. The educator survey was developed by RMC in close collaboration with SCPS project leaders and, where possible, adopted or adapted items from existing measures with evidence of reliability and validity. The survey asked ESE teachers and paraprofessionals about their: demographic and background information; perceptions of preparedness related to instruction, assessment, collaboration, and best practices associated with addressing student social/emotional/behavioral needs; teaching practices including classroom organization, planning and training, delivery, assessment, and family engagement; engagement in professional activities; participation in and satisfaction with professional development and training activities, including quality and utility; satisfaction with and intent to remain teaching; and perceived impacts on students. All scales developed from survey items

¹⁰ Student's Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) were analyzed to understand the breadth and types of services that students received as well as the content areas in which they received support.

demonstrated adequate internal reliability ($\alpha > .70$) with the exception of educator practice for 2021/22, which demonstrated internal consistency of .69 (Appendix C; Exhibit C1).

Fidelity Measures. A set of indicators and corresponding implementation fidelity thresholds were developed through close collaboration between the evaluation and implementation teams. Measurable indicators were aligned with key components in the logic model and associated data sources. Key components and indicators are described in the fidelity matrix (Appendix B).

ESECP Site Review Data. Site reviews were completed through in-person classroom observation by ESECP staff. The extent to which teachers implemented the ESECP program as expected in their classroom was captured using site review forms. Each teacher/ESECP classroom received a site review in the fall and again in the spring. Separate site review forms were used for academic and developmental domain classrooms. Forms for each type of classroom share common items and items that reflect the differences between domains. In both cases, the site review form measured the presence or absence of each indicator to obtain an overall percentage of implementation. Two observers rated 10% of classrooms to ensure interobserver agreement.

Program Data. In addition to indicators of fidelity, program staff provided the research team with data on factors likely to mediate ESECP effects. Student engagement measures included the number of student absences, percentage of students placed in direct instruction groups using the direct instruction placement flow chart in each domain, percentage of instructional groups where students were working at the correctly placed level, and the percentage of students who received properly timed progress monitoring assessments. Classroom implementation was measured in terms of whether or not the Teacher Support Matrix was used to identify the support needed for each teacher, number of instructional groups held during the year, the percentage of instructional groups held, the number of lessons completed, and the number of ESECP training logs completed for coaching sessions as indicator of instructional monitoring.

QUALITATIVE MEASURES

Interview and focus group protocols were used to collect information about educator roles in ESECP implementation; training provided for program implementation; how student progress was monitored; how school and district staff ensured that the program was implemented as intended; and variations in implementation based on student, teacher, or school characteristics. Respondents were also asked about stakeholder perceptions of impacts on teachers' instructional practices, classroom management, and relationships with students, as well as on student achievement, social and emotional learning, and academic engagement. Parents were asked to share information about their participation in and satisfaction with implementation, challenges experienced, suggestions for improvement, and perceptions of impacts on student outcomes. District staff involved in project leadership (including BAs and TOAs) and school administrators (including those with primary responsibility for implementation of ESECP in each school) were asked to provide information about training, implementation, ESE instructor buy-in, strengths and challenges with implementation, and perceived impact on ESECP students. Protocols also examined progress toward sustainability, scale-up, and dissemination.

SAMPLES

INTERVENTION AND MATCHED COMPARISON SCHOOLS

SCPS strategically identified 12 intervention schools in which data were collected between 2021/22 and 2023/24 (4 Cohort 1 schools, 4 Cohort 2 schools, and 3 Cohort 3 schools; see Exhibit 6). SCPS leaders worked with RMC to identify comparison schools that: (a) had similar characteristics to intervention schools, (b) had not implemented the school-wide approach to ESECP, and (c) were on the waitlist for implementation of ESECP within 5 years.

EXHIBIT 6. ESECP AND COMPARISON SCHOOLS IN EACH COHORT

	Pilot	Cohort 1	Cohort 2	Cohort 3
	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
Bear Lake Elementary School			C	I
Carillon Elementary School		C ^a	I	
Crystal Lake Elementary School		I		
Eastbrook Elementary School	I			
English Estates Elementary School		C		C
Forest City Elementary School		I		
Geneva Elementary School		I		
Goldsboro Elementary School	I			
Heathrow Elementary School		C		C
Keeth Elementary School			I	
Lawton Elementary School			C	
Longwood Elementary School		C		I
Rainbow Elementary School			C	
Red Bug Elementary School			I	
Sabal Point Elementary School			I	
Stenstrom Elementary School		C		C
Wicklow Elementary School		C		C
Winter Springs Elementary School			C	
Woodlands Elementary School		C		C
Wilson Elementary School		I		
Midway Elementary School			C	
Partin Elementary School			C	
Walker Elementary School ^b				I

I = Intervention School; C = Comparison School

Note. All students included in the study sample (in intervention and comparison conditions) were followed through 2023/24. Schools could be identified as a comparison school for multiple cohorts. Once a school was an intervention school, students would not be considered as a match in the comparison condition. Schools could serve as a comparison school for multiple cohorts, but students were matched without replacement. ^aCarillon is only the comparison for students in the developmental domain in Cohort 1. ^b Walker was originally intended to be a Cohort 3 comparison school, but due to administrative changes became an intervention school and began implementation mid-year.

INTERVENTION AND MATCHED COMPARISON STUDENTS

Students were included in the reading and/or mathematics analytic samples if they were in grades K-5 and had baseline assessment scores in reading or mathematics that placed them two or more grade levels below¹¹, or if they had an active Individualized Education Plan (IEP) that indicated they received services in either reading or mathematics. Students were excluded if they had a single ESE code of: occupational therapy; orthopedically impaired; physical therapy; gifted; hospital/homebound; or speech impaired. Cohort 1 students had the option of taking a virtual assessment in Cohort 1 so rush flags were used to identify additional exclusions. Students who were flagged as having rushed through the i-Ready pre/post assessments in Cohort 1 (29 students in the ELA assessments and 16 students in the mathematics assessments) were excluded from analyses.

Propensity score matching was used to identify matched students in similar comparison schools not implementing the ESECP for students in the academic domain. Propensity scores were generated using logistic regression to identify the likelihood that a student would be in an ESECP school based on observable characteristics, including: the number of academic areas served (based on categorization of IEP records), the number of areas served overall (also based on categorization of IEP records), student grade, pretest reading or mathematics scale scores, grade level difference in pretest scores, and percentage of time spent with nondisabled peers¹². All students with a record of ESE services for behavior were matched to other students with records for ESE services for behavior using an exact match. The match included 1:1 matching with no caliper, and used nearest neighbor. Sample sizes for analysis of reading and mathematics outcomes, by intervention group and cohort are presented in Exhibit 7.

EXHIBIT 7. STUDENT ANALYTIC SAMPLES

Outcome	ESECP (N)				Comparison (N)			
	Cohort 1	Cohort 2	Cohort 3	Overall	Cohort 1	Cohort 2	Cohort 3	Overall
Reading	216	197	186	599	216	197	186	599
Mathematics	199	173	182	554	199	173	554	372

Baseline mean differences between the ESECP and comparison group for each analytic sample were calculated using the primary confirmatory impact model with the dependent variable as baseline scores, with a two-level Hierarchical Linear Model (HLM), with students nested in schools for each analytic sample (reading and mathematics). The analysis model can be found in Appendix C. Pre-test scores differed by .05 SD or less, which is within the acceptable range as specified by the WWC Version 5.0 (Exhibit 8). Separate analytic samples were created based on iReady reading and mathematics baseline scores.

¹¹ Kindergarten students were eligible if they were one or more grade levels below.

¹² This characteristic was only available for Cohorts 1 and 2.

EXHIBIT 8. STUDENT ANALYTIC SAMPLE: BASELINE EQUIVALENCE

Baseline Measure of the Outcome	ESECP		Comparison		Effect Size Calculations		
	<i>N</i>	Model-Adjusted Mean ($\gamma_{00} + \gamma_{01}$)	<i>N</i>	Unadjusted Mean (γ_{00})	ESECP and Comparison Difference (γ_{01})	<i>SD</i> _{pooled}	Hedge's <i>g</i> (γ_{01}/SD_{pooled})
iReady Reading	599	445.36	599	445.94	-0.58	71.94	-0.008
iReady Mathematics	554	398.21	554	400.49	-2.28	45.60	-0.05

Note. Means were estimated using the analytic model. The standard deviations and pooled standard deviation were calculated using raw data for students in the ESECP and comparison groups.

EDUCATOR SURVEY PARTICIPANTS

Generally, educator survey respondents were primarily white (69% to 100%) and female (80% to 100%) and most taught all grade levels in the study (K-5). Most respondents were educators in self-contained classrooms (Exhibit 9). For more details see Appendix C, Exhibit C2.

EXHIBIT 9. SURVEY RESPONDENT ROLES

Role	2021/22	2022/23	2023/24
	(<i>N</i> = 12)	(<i>N</i> = 13)	(<i>N</i> = 9)
	<i>n</i> (%)	<i>n</i> (%)	<i>n</i> (%)
Classroom Teacher in Self-Contained Classroom	6 (50.0)	6 (46.2)	3 (33.3)
Paraprofessional in Self-Contained Classroom	1 (8.3)	1 (7.7)	0 (0.0)
Support Facilitator in General Education Classroom(s)	1 (8.3)	2 (15.4)	3 (33.3)
Teacher of Small Groups in Resource Room Setting	2 (16.7)	1 (7.7)	1 (11.1)
Speech Language Pathologist	2 (16.7)	0 (0.0)	1 (11.1)
More than One Role	0 (0.0)	3 (23.1)	1 (11.1)

PARENT SURVEY PARTICIPANTS

Out of 1,802 parents of Cohort 1 and Cohort 2 students enrolled in ESE within SCPS study schools, 753 parents responded to the Florida ESE Parent Survey in spring 2022 and spring 2023, for an average response rate of 45%. Almost all schools participating in the study were represented. See Appendix C (Exhibit C3) for more information for each participating school. ESE parent survey data for spring 2024 were not available by school, therefore no information is available for that year (other years includes school-level findings).

INTERVIEWS AND FOCUS GROUPS

Each year, interviews and focus groups were conducted with program leadership, including the SCPS ESE Director, the Project Director, and TOA/BA supervisor(s), TOAs and BAs, school administrators, educators, and parents. Despite multiple attempts to recruit participants, educator participation in focus

groups was low in spring 2022, and parent focus group participation was low in both spring 2022 and spring 2023 (Exhibit 10). Details about participant characteristics are not presented to preserve confidentiality.

EXHIBIT 10. INTERVIEW AND FOCUS GROUP PARTICIPANTS

Participant Group	Number of Respondents		
	2022 (Cohort 1)	2023 (Cohort 2)	2024 (Cohort 3)
Leadership (SCPS ESE Director, Project Director, TOA/BA Supervisor)	3	3	5
TOAs/BAs	5	7	3
School Administrators	2	4	7
Educators ^a	0	18	16
Parents	1	1	15

^aRespondents included guidance counselors, teachers, paraprofessionals, speech-language pathologists, and interventionists.

ESECP ACTIVITY OBSERVATIONS

Twelve parent training sessions were observed virtually by RMC staff during 2021/22, 2022/23, and 2023/24. RMC staff also virtually attended a presentation on ESECP to the district School Board in September 2022.

ANALYSIS

FIDELITY

Scores from the fidelity matrix were used to examine the extent to which the ESECP was implemented with fidelity in participating schools and classrooms, and to document variation in fidelity according to teacher and school characteristics (Evaluation Questions 1 and 2). A composite implementation fidelity index (used to create a binary indicator of whether or not fidelity was met) was created for the district based on key components of ESECP as specified in the logic model and fidelity matrix. Descriptive analyses of scores (frequencies) were used to document implementation fidelity overall and for each key component.

Qualitative data were used to triangulate findings from Evaluation Questions 1 and 2, and to describe factors that facilitated or impeded ESECP implementation (Evaluation Question 3). Qualitative data were analyzed using an approach that closely follows methods described by Miles, Huberman, and Saldaña (2019).¹³ This approach emphasizes well-defined study variables to ensure the comparability and reduction of data using data displays and matrices so that common themes can be identified. Selected quotes are provided to illuminate key themes.

¹³ Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M., & Saldaña, J. (2019). *Qualitative data analysis: A methods sourcebook* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

IMPACT

Impact analyses (Evaluation Questions 4-11) involved two-level hierarchical linear models (HLM)¹⁴ to assess impact on iReady reading and mathematics scores with students nested within schools for students in the academic domain. Descriptive analyses were used to document scores for students in the developmental domain within each condition at baseline and following one year of participation in ESECP.

Impact analysis models documenting academic outcomes after one year of participation (Evaluation Question 4) account for school-level condition (intervention or comparison), pretest scores, cohort, and baseline variables related to the outcome measure. Student outcome scale scores were regressed on student-level indicators of pretest achievement and student demographic covariates that could be related to outcomes. This analysis combined all students across analytic cohorts with separate samples for mathematics and reading outcomes. The intervention indicator is included in the model at level 2 because assignment occurred at the school level. School level effects only include students who received IEP services or were two or more grade levels behind their peers (and did not include students in the general population of the school). Continuous covariates (e.g., pretest score) were grand-mean centered; dichotomous covariates (e.g., grade level dummies) were not centered. The intervention effect was fixed. Models were estimated using full information maximum likelihood estimation. All analyses were completed using all available data; no data imputation techniques were used. In the case of missing pre-test or outcome data, case deletion was used prior to the identification of matched samples. A summary of models can be found in Appendix D.

The primary impact model was adapted to address Evaluation Questions 5, 8, 9, and 11. The same impact model was used to test impact on sub-test scores of iReady reading and mathematics (Evaluation Question 5)¹⁵, impact on reading and mathematics outcomes after two and three years (three years were available for Cohort 1 and two years for Cohorts 1 and 2; Evaluation Question 8), and impact on attendance (as a mediator, Evaluation Question 9). To examine the extent to which the nature and extent of implementation mediate the impact of ESECP on student outcomes, correlations between various indicators of fidelity levels and dosage were conducted (Evaluation Question 9), and then primary impact models were replicated using only the sample of students and schools in ESECP condition. These models included fidelity indicators or mediators, and excluded the intervention indicator since only students in the ESECP condition were included in the analytic sample. Finally, to examine how the impact of ESECP may vary by student subgroups (Evaluation Question 11), the primary impact model was used with the full analytic samples, with the addition of cross-level interactions (student characteristic X treatment condition). Student characteristics examined included free/reduced meal eligibility, gender, race/ethnicity, ELL status, number of exceptionalities, and count of areas of support overall and in academic content areas based on IEP codes.

The analyses also examined the extent to which ESECP implementation was related to teacher outcomes (retention in school and in the district as measured by administrative data, practice and satisfaction as measured by the survey); and parent outcomes (involvement in school and satisfaction). Teacher

¹⁴ Hierarchical linear modeling (HLM) is a statistical technique for analysis of data that have a hierarchical or nested structure. HLM is often most appropriate for this type of data because it accounts for variation in outcomes at each hierarchical level. For example, HLM models allow analysts to examine variation in student outcomes (and the factors that contribute to them) at the classroom and school levels.

¹⁵ The Benjamini-Hochberg correction was used to account for multiple comparisons.

outcomes were measured at the teacher level and parent outcomes were measured at the school level by the state-wide survey. When at least ten respondents completed fall and spring survey items on the educator survey, descriptive statistics including means, frequencies, and standard deviations are presented. Because of the small number of participants from ESECP and comparison groups, descriptive statistics are presented, rather than inferential group comparison tests (e.g., *t*-tests).

Additional analysis of survey, administrative and program data collected from SCPS from 2021/22 through 2023/24 included descriptive analyses to provide a rich description of implementation in the district. When describing frequencies, the narrative identifies differences between groups that are greater than 10%.

FINDINGS

This section describes findings from interviews, focus groups, educator surveys, program documents and data, and district administrative data collected during the 2021/22 through 2023/24 academic years. Implementation is described first, including engagement with schools, implementation of program key components, and adherence to implementation fidelity expectations. Next, information about classroom implementation, including contextual considerations and dosage, and lessons learned are presented. Lastly, evidence of impact on educator and student outcomes is presented.

IMPLEMENTATION (EVALUATION QUESTIONS 1 AND 2)

School and district interview and focus group respondents described the program consistently across all cohorts. After a school was identified to implement ESECP, an **overview of the project** was shared with school administration and the entire ESE team and instructional staff, so that they could understand implementation and related expectations. They understood that district ESECP staff were to use **assessment results to identify students** who were two or more years behind in ELA and/or mathematics, or below 48 months of verbal ability.

A screener was used to place students in one of the following four “curriculum circles” (for the purposes of this report, also called domains) to best address the needs of each student:

1. Medical (for students who need some type of medical care and who may have very limited cognitive skills);
2. Developmental (for students who have very limited communication skills);
3. Academic (for students who have well-developed communication skills but who are 2 or more years behind in reading, language, or mathematics); and
4. Behavior (for students who need social and emotional learning due to substantial behavioral concerns and the need to be in a self-contained classroom).

This study focused on the academic and developmental domains. **In the developmental domain, students were typically placed in self-contained classrooms.** Three instructional approaches were used: (1) **intensive teaching**, where educators probed individual targets to see if the student knew them, and intensively taught identified targets to address deficits; (2) **natural environment**, to ensure that what the student was learning could be used in natural situations; and (3) **mand instruction**, where the educators made requests to address student needs and wants to teach them how to make the requests themselves. ESE educators worked with students on the individual skills identified. **For the academic domain, students were grouped based on their individual needs and worked through a progression of lessons that supported skill development using the assigned Direct Instruction curriculum.** Curricula focused on **decoding, comprehension, and/or mathematics** skills. Students in the academic domain were either placed in self-contained classrooms or they were assigned to be pulled out for up to three direct instruction groups to address their needs. Students in the behavioral domain would primarily be found in the self-contained classrooms whether or not their academic skills placed them two or more years behind in reading, language, or mathematics. In all domains, student placement was based on the least restrictive environment; and students could be assigned to one domain (e.g., medical or developmental primarily) but then join an academic small group for targeted instruction.

Respondents across cohorts noted that district-based ESECP staff and school administrators created a **master schedule** that ensured students had the opportunity to engage with one-on-one interactions, pullout groups, self-contained instruction, and other ESECP programming as necessary. The master schedule was described as a key aspect of the project by school administrators and district leaders and coaches (TOAs and BAs). District leaders and coaches reported making recommendations for the master schedule that would support all instruction, limiting interruptions to general education programming as much as possible while optimizing fidelity to ESECP implementation. Ideally, this meant that the school incorporated a designated intervention time for students to receive intensive instruction. Respondents in interviews and focus groups suggested that participating schools did this to varying degrees. Respondents reported that **when schools successfully created a master schedule to integrate the components required by the project, educators struggled less and had the time needed for project implementation.**

Daily Routines. Educators (from the third cohort) shared that the **program incorporated routines to assist students with their learning.** Students knew what to do when they came into the classroom and where to sit, had their materials close by for easy retrieval when needed, and knew the ways they could earn points to receive rewards. Several educators noted using the student-teacher game and a visual thermometer (an activity in which a thermometer is colored in as students make progress toward lesson expectations) when discussing behavior management in their classroom, adding that students liked activities in which they earned rewards.

While there was some variability in use of daily routines when needing to address behaviors of particular students, respondents reported **that they followed ESECP lessons as close to fidelity as possible.** Despite efforts to stay on pace with lessons, educators reported sometimes being unable to do so due to factors outside their control. These factors included fire and safety drills, testing or other school level disruptions, student behaviors causing disruptions, student lack of understanding of the unit and/or lesson, and transitions into different lesson groups. For example, some students had difficulty with moving to progressively complex decoding groups, due to lack of knowledge or maturity level to properly engage in activities such as checking other' students' work. Many educators shared that there were aspects of the program, such as the way a behavior was addressed and/or a concept was explained, that didn't work with some students, and they had to incorporate their own teaching style or what had previously worked with the student. They noted how occurrences in the classroom were quite different than what was practiced during ESECP training, which they described as the "best case scenario." Some educators felt the program was trying to be a "one for all," with little consideration of students' individual needs and behavioral issues. Some educators also reported that, despite the grouping suggested by their test results, students were sometimes placed in an incorrect group leading to lessons not being beneficial for them.

The ESECP program is looking at how a student fits into the program instead of how the program fits to the student. (Cohort 3)

I'm required to meet the students' IEP goals, not just teach this curriculum with fidelity. (Cohort 3)

Interview and focus group respondents indicated that implementation varied across schools and that only some were implementing fully. **Multiple steps were taken to ensure that ESECP classroom implementation proceeded as expected,** including ESE educator coaching, lesson tracking sheets that educators completed to show how many lessons or how much of a lesson they had done for each group,

a shared data spreadsheet that was updated daily and reviewed by district ESECP staff, and frequent communication with district ESECP staff. Additionally, district ESECP staff conducted fidelity checks twice a year, where they reviewed classroom expectations. For the third cohort, district ESECP staff conveyed certain non-negotiable aspects to programing including holding instruction on Wednesdays and having a minimum of 45-minutes of instruction for the groups. As respondents noted:

When there is the drive for student success and [ESE educators] assist in that progress, you see more gains with the students because the teacher is putting in the necessary time to know what their student needs; but if they don't have that buy in, and just go through the motions, then it's not as impactful, and the student doesn't progress as much. (Cohort 1)

Schools have a different flavor; those with buy-in are performing the best and getting through the most lessons. (Cohort 2)

Schools get to a tipping point where they see ESECP working for their students; then they go into implementation fully and are getting through lessons with fidelity. (Cohort 3)

Student Progress Monitoring. Respondents in all three cohorts described several ways that student progress was monitored. Educators used **curriculum-based assessments**, and the administration of **i-Ready** four times a year to see if students were meeting the district expectation of one year's growth in one year's time. For developmental students, educators used the **Verbal Behavior Milestones Assessment and Placement Program (VBMAPP) assessment** to determine which skills students acquired. Additionally, **daily data** were collected using cold probes (questions for students tailored to their level) to assess progress toward skill targets. Skill targets were considered to be mastered when the student correctly responded three days in a row; then a new skill was introduced. **Weekly data tracking sheets** were used to track specific skills for individual students. Respondents shared that ESE educators were expected to enter classroom data, such as lesson progression and mastery tests (given approximately every ten lessons), into an electronic tracking system daily or upon completion. **Coaches reviewed the data with staff from NIFDI on a weekly basis** and gave suggestions to ESE educators on ways to strengthen instruction. Respondents mentioned that district ESECP staff worked diligently to get the data completely online by the third cohort, so that **coaches could look at the data in near-real-time and assist ESE educators remotely** when they were not at the school to support them. Some educators in the third cohort shared that they enjoyed the spreadsheets used with the program and tracking systems. They liked being able to see the percentage of students who were not passing and other tracking points to decide how to address those needs. Some school administrators reported attending the weekly Webex meeting the district held to review the school's progress data, and principals also received monthly summaries of the learning progress of classes in the school. Respondents shared comments about data use in the program:

Being transparent about the learning path of the students is very helpful across the board. (Cohort 1)

We monitor progress using the Curriculum Project data that shows growth and progress; i-Ready, weekly data collection. And we can see each other's data. (Cohort 2)

Some educators from the third cohort reported that they monitored student progress using the visual thermometer. Educators noted that this assisted in keeping them and their students accountable, and students encouraged and supported one other so they could receive rewards.

Student buy-in, like the thermometers and rewards, really works to get to the goals we set; they enjoy earning stickers, candy. (Cohort 3)

Informal observations were used to obtain a rich description of implementation. The following vignette describes an example self-contained classroom in the developmental domain.

The developmental classroom was set up in centers, with a kitchen center, two kidney-shaped tables, two tables set up at the wall, a privacy screen, and activities within cupboards. Color-coded shapes identified additional stations. There was a projector on the wall, the daily schedule for each student was posted in 20-30 minute intervals (covering Mand training, Intent to Treat, Natural Environment Training), Circle time, Mand, sensory, and stations), and lesson progress was posted for each student. Colorful artwork, birthdays, and alphabet letters were displayed on the walls. At nine in the morning, seven students were in the classroom with one lead teacher and three paraprofessionals. Students ranged in their mobility, language, and function, from needing explicit support to being able to follow directions and spend time working independently. Once attendance was taken, students started circle time following music videos; some students used this time to finish eating breakfast and paraprofessionals assisted students in using the bathroom. Students danced to the videos while educators greeted them, encouraged use of language, and did some set up for the day. At 9:20 am, stations began. One student was participating in ITT with two instructors, which included following instructions on cards such as “can you show me [action] with a [noun]?” or “can you show me slide the pencil?” in which the student had a pencil on the table to slide, or asking the student to repeat what they were hearing. Each student was participating in an activity tailored to their ability. According to the schedule, stations would switch at 9:50 am. Students appeared happy and engaged in their activities. Some had a hard time focusing or were allowed to play/work independently while others received 1-to-1 attention.

ESECP ADMINISTRATOR, TEACHER ON ASSIGNMENT, AND BEHAVIOR ANALYST TRAINING AND COACHING

The ESECP team described their involvement in training provided by partners from the Pennsylvania Training and Technical Assistance Network (PaTTAN). **The PaTTAN Autism Initiative (PaTTAN AI) is a model for the training developed for ESE educators in SCPS based on evidence-based PaTTAN model Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA)** to address the needs of students with autism. It was developed in Pennsylvania and incorporated into ESECP. The training supports helped educators develop the skills they need with effective sequencing and systematic methods. The model focuses on instruction in critical social communication skills across levels of functioning, delivery methods that are monitored and adjusted based on student-level data, and practical skill outcomes. PaTTAN trainers provided training and technical assistance with implementation.

Training was also provided by the National Institute for Direct Instruction (NIFDI). Respondents reported that **NIFDI supported the TOAs and BAs with their coaching of ESECP educators, observed the coaches, and provided them with feedback and support.** Respondents across the program years mentioned that NIFDI provided weekly support to address high level concerns with educators and schools and with using

data to guide coaching and teaching. During the 2023/24 academic year NIFDI developed a coaching video that showed the process of implementing ESECP.

Respondents across cohorts shared that **TOAs and BAs participated in an intensive training-of-trainers academy**, where they learned how to teach the implementation process and deliver the training to ESE educators. They also **shadowed other ESECP coaches** when they began working on the project, participated in a three-to-five-day training held for ESE educators, engaged in weekly PLC meetings, and were supported in their work by other ESECP staff. The project team did not feel that they needed additional training beyond what was offered and described deep involvement in program implementation and oversight by project leadership. They also noted that continual support helped them to stay current on any changes or adjustments to programming. Representative comments included:

We get quite a bit of training and that will be used next summer when we take over the training ourselves [as partners phase out]. (Cohort 1)

NIFDI is helpful in improving my skill set; they coach us and support us. (Cohort 1)

The coaches break instruction down into small steps and use a gradual release model. They do problem-solving sessions in small groups in the fall. They talk about each classroom monthly. (Cohort 2)

SCHOOL ADMINISTRATOR AND DISTRICT ESECP STAFF TRAINING AND ENGAGEMENT

Respondents reported that **training provided to ESECP school administrators included a pre-implementation meeting and a one-day administrator institute**. School administrators attended a one-day training that showed them what ESE educators would be doing with the curriculum and familiarized them with the types of data collection that ESE educators would be conducting throughout the year. In addition to initial training activities, district ESECP staff worked with school administrators to help them better understand the components of the curriculum and advised them on how to work with ESE educators who were not implementing the curriculum with fidelity.

Respondents stated that **training about ESECP was provided to all ESE educators including ESE teachers, support facilitators, and paraeducators**. During all grant years this training included a three-to-five-day preservice training activity, one-day trainings for those unable to complete the three-to-five-day training or who needed additional support, and ongoing training with TOAs and BAs. Respondents noted that the **intensive training prepared ESE educators to implement three types of curricula at varied levels (decoding/reading, comprehension, and math); and at both primary (grades PK-2) and intermediate (grades 3-5) levels**. The number of days of training attended by each educator varied according to the curriculum they were implementing, with the goal of educators being confident with the first ten lessons that they would be teaching. The trainings covered direct instruction for academic students and behavioral approaches for developmental students. The one-day trainings were provided on educator workdays to make attendance easier for the educators. Additionally, during the 2023/24 academic year these sessions were archived online, and educators received an email with a link to access them.

Respondents in all three cohorts shared that **TOAs and BAs provided continual training and support to ESE educators throughout the school year**. TOAs/BAs engaged in PLC meetings, provided coaching,

assisted with data collection set up, conducted observations and provided feedback. Coaches worked closely with ESE educators to examine data and discuss other classroom information. They collaborated to pinpoint implementation problems and brainstorm solutions. Coaches and educators developed a plan for assistance to support the needs of the ESE educators so they in turn provided the best instruction to students to support their learning needs.

During weekly sessions, **hands-on support and technical assistance were provided**. Coaches modeled how to deliver the curriculum and engaged in side-by-side coaching, provided techniques and strategies, answered any questions, and addressed concerns with implementation. Respondents reported that they were provided with a systematic approach of addressing any implementation issues using a procedure. Respondents shared that progressive action steps to address challenges with program implementation included coaches working directly with the educator to develop an action plan and then revisiting their efforts within a week. If there had been no improvement, coaches would discuss areas of concern with the educator and gain insight into any issues encountered to provide solutions to use in the upcoming week. If program implementation was still not occurring with fidelity by the third week, a meeting with school administration was scheduled and administrators were informed each week of the coaching that occurred with the educator. Respondents noted that any implementation issues tended to be resolved before the point of administrator involvement, and that if an educator was not implementing the programming at all, program staff would start working with administration directly to resolve the issue. Respondents stated that when school administration understood and supported program efforts, ESE educators had more buy-in with the curriculum as well. Additionally, some respondents shared that an overview of the program was presented to general education educators at the schools, so they understood that students were engaged in specific activities during that time.

PERCEPTIONS OF ESECP TRAINING AND COACHING

Quality. District administrators, school administrators, and district ESECP staff in all cohorts generally characterized the quality of the training for ESE educators as excellent. Respondents described the training as thorough and up-to-date, and appreciated that it was applicable to their work and provided opportunities for collaboration among ESE teachers. Coaches and school administrators stated that participation in the intensive training was very helpful to educator implementation of the curriculum. Respondents shared that the training could be overwhelming to educators given the extent of new, detailed information that was shared, but it did a great job preparing them. The trainings engaged educators through active participation, such as hands-on activities, role play of ESECP implementation, and guided notes (prepared handouts for participants to follow along with and fill in notes). Additionally, they were provided with sufficient time to practice skills and reported that they learned exactly what they would be doing. **Nearly all respondents stated that the hands-on component of the training worked best for educators to support their understanding of the curriculum and implementation.** Educators were presented with real situations that could arise, and they worked together with the trainers and coaches to identify solutions. They also practiced sample lessons. Participation in training activities provided coaches with information about educators' knowledge and understanding of the curriculum and implementation process, and that served as a starting point to guide the one-on-one coaching that immediately followed at the beginning of the school year. As some respondents noted:

I have teachers who have and have not participated [in the intensive training], and it is like night and day. (Cohort 1)

[The training] does a great job giving [educators] what they need [for implementation]. (Cohort 1)

[The quality of the training] is very thorough. They are always updating the training. (Cohort 2)

What I liked about the class in the summer was networking with other ESE teachers. I've done lots of [professional developments] that are just slides and you may forget, but this was very hands-on and actually applied. (Cohort 2)

Educators reported enjoying the training they received and felt that it was beneficial to them, emphasizing the value of coaching. The training provided well defined program goals, outlined the program processes, and was clear about how the program should be implemented. Educators reported enjoying the materials and learning new strategies such as error correction and language use. Several noted that they would not have been able to implement the program without the training. Many echoed that the best part of the training was modeling and the opportunity to practice implementation. They became more familiar with the logistics and procedural instructions, script, identifying mistakes, and learning how to pivot programming in the moment. Several educators mentioned that their ESECP training was better than what they had experienced previously for working with students with exceptional needs. They shared that they typically had no ESE-specific training nor participated in general education PD. Educators responsible for classrooms in the developmental domain reporting being happy to have something specific to use with their students. Educators implementing programming with students in the academic domain reported appreciated that the curriculum was targeted toward particular skills. They appreciated that they had a chance to practice with the materials, that the training was not just lecture, and that they were able to see a video of implementation and how coaches worked with educators.

In the past [training] was more "one and done." Having a coach is a unique experience. (Cohort 3)

Professional Learning Participation. Educator survey respondents reported the extent to which they participated in professional learning activities. On average, educators reported the highest level of participation in collaborative activities and peer mentoring sessions (Exhibit 11). Across time and cohorts, ESECP and comparison educators reported similar levels of participation in professional learning activities. Though not depicted in the chart, ESECP educators participated less frequently in 2021/22 and more frequently in these activities in the subsequent two years. The most utilized professional learning activities included mentoring and/or peer observation and coaching and informal collaboration with other educators.

EXHIBIT 11. PARTICIPATION IN PROFESSIONAL LEARNING ACTIVITIES: ESECP AND COMPARISON EDUCATORS

Note. Results were combined across years and cohorts for ESECP and comparison educators. $N_{\text{ESECP}} = 26$ (7 for 2021/22, 11 for 2022/23, and 8 for 2023/24). $N_{\text{Comparison}} = 5$ (all from 2021/22 or Y1). Fewer than 5 educators responded from comparison schools in other years, so results are excluded.

Survey respondents rated the extent to which professional learning activities focused on instruction, data assessment, classroom management, and creating a positive classroom culture (Exhibit 12). ESECP educators rated each of these areas slightly higher than comparison educators, with the greatest emphasis being on instruction and creating a positive classroom culture.

EXHIBIT 12. FOCUS OF PROFESSIONAL LEARNING ACTIVITIES: ESECP AND COMPARISON EDUCATORS

Note. Results were combined across years and cohorts for ESECP and comparison educators. $N_{\text{ESECP}} = 26$ (7 for 2021/22, 11 for 2022/23, and 8 for 2023/24). $N_{\text{Comparison}} = 5$ (all from 2021/22 or Y1). Fewer than 5 educators responded from comparison schools in other years, so results are excluded.

Survey respondents from all cohorts were asked to reflect on the various professional learning opportunities available to them throughout the school year. On average, ratings of professional learning activities were consistently between “good” and “very good” across most activities, with highest ratings for summer trainings and consultations from TOAs or BAs (Exhibit 13). The Professional Learning Community (PLC) meetings and GroupMe chat received slightly lower average ratings (between “poor” and “good”). Quality ratings were similar across time.

EXHIBIT 13. QUALITY OF ESECP PROFESSIONAL LEARNING BY COHORT

Note. Year 1 $N = 16$. Year 2 $N = 9$. Year 1 outcomes include the average outcomes for the first year of implementation (7 for 2021/22, 6 for 2022/23, and 3 for 2023/24). Year 2 outcomes include the average outcomes for the second year of implementation (all 5 for 2021/22). Fewer than 5 educators responded from comparison schools in other years, so results are excluded.

Engagement in Professional Activities. Educators who took the survey indicated the extent to which they engaged in professional activities. On average, educators agreed that they kept up to date with current best practices in education and modeled professional and ethical standards (Exhibit 14).

EXHIBIT 14. EDUCATOR ENGAGEMENT IN PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES

Note. Results were combined across years and cohorts for ESECP and comparison educators. $N_{\text{ESECP}} = 26$ (7 for 2021/22, 11 for 2022/23, and 8 for 2023/24). $N_{\text{Comparison}} = 5$ (all from 2021/22 or Y1). Fewer than 5 educators responded from comparison schools in other years, so results are excluded.

Suggestions for Improving Training. Respondents from all cohorts provided suggestions for ways that ESECP training could be improved, many of which reflected a shared feeling that coaching was particularly helpful for assisting ESE educators who were struggling with program implementation. For example, respondents suggested having **a mid-year training** to further assist those who were struggling or did not participate in the intensive training, to come back together and discuss any issues that arose, to delve deeper into understanding the curriculum and implementation process, and to have a second tier of training for those who had a grasp of the curriculum and implementation. They reported that these opportunities would provide additional practice for educators and further their conceptualization of the programming. Additionally, many **interview and focus group respondents felt that an additional day of training was needed to more fully cover data collection and tracking activities, classroom management and behavior, and conducting check outs and mastery testing.** Educators also suggested providing training on new components of the program to educators who were implementing well. For instance, if an educator were trained in decoding, that educator could be trained in mathematics. They reported that this additional training would improve educator ability to address needs of new groups of students (e.g., when testing shows that new groups are needed, or when there is a need to lead a colleague’s group when they are out of the classroom) and their ability to speak with parents about student programming.

Educators also suggested **allowing training participants to use their computers in the trainings** so they could take notes along with the PowerPoint since it was a lot of material for them to take in, and so they had something to share with other educators at their schools. Cohort 3 educators also suggested having **a central location where educators could access online resources and PD webinars on specific areas efficiently.** Additional **training on writing IEPs aligned to participation in ESECP was suggested since typically IEP goals were written to academic standards and not goals towards a curriculum.** Further, said they wished that the materials for programming would be distributed to the schools before the academic year started. Some educators expressed frustration that they didn’t receive programming materials until mid-semester when they started ESECP at the beginning of the year.

Several respondents mentioned the need to **provide additional school administrator training to assist with buy-in and support for implementation** because school administrators are asked to conduct observations and provide feedback to reinforce fidelity to implementation, and educators tend to follow their administrator’s directive. Several respondents suggested having school administrators and ESE educators who were new to ESECP programming observe the model being implemented with high fidelity. They believed this could increase their understanding of program activities, accountability components, and how to monitor student progress.

PARENT TRAINING, COMMUNICATION, INVOLVEMENT, AND SATISFACTION (EVALUATION QUESTION 7)

Parents were invited to attend parent sessions that provided information about the program and curriculum, what the interventions look like, and what their child would be engaged in. Project staff worked with parents so that they understood the process and the “why” behind programming focusing on skill development and use of data to show the need for intervention. **Monthly parent trainings** were provided by the University of Central Florida Center for Autism and Related Disorders (CARD). These trainings were aligned to the work being done in the program, focusing on reading, testing, and behavior. For example, sessions included information about supporting students with bathroom habits, problem solving for individuals with autism spectrum disorder, being prepared for summer, building independence at home, feeding strategies, surviving the holidays, and preventing tragedies. Across

years, twenty sessions were provided by CARD and 218 parents/caregivers attended. See Appendix E for more information.

During the school year, parents of students in the developmental domain received a copy of the cold probe data sheet (used for tracking progress with desired behaviors) and an overview of the skill that their child was working on so that they could reinforce the work being done at home; and other communication logs specific to ESECP for parents and educators to track their discussions. Additionally, for academic students, project leaders shared that parents were to be provided with weekly progress reports and updates on mastery tests; however, parents did not report this happening (rather, they indicated annual IEP meetings were the primary mechanism of communication, and general updates at one school). Parents were also provided with newsletters, and attended parent-teacher conferences, IEP meetings, and parent nights/information sessions. Some administrators and leaders noted that they did not believe that many ESE educators were providing the level of communication with parents as expected within ESECP. Many educators shared that they provided quarterly progress reports for those with IEPs on the district platform (Skyward), met with parents annually to update student IEPs, and communicated with parents if there was something especially positive or negative to share about a student. Several educators acknowledged that they communicated with parents of students with social emotional goals on their IEPs more frequently. Some educators reported that they were not working with the same students they were responsible for regarding IEPs and this made it difficult for them to communicate to parents about what their child was working on in the intervention programming.

On average, educators who took the survey from ESECP schools agreed that training was offered to parents and caregivers while educators from Cohort 1 comparison schools tended to disagree. Both ESECP and comparison school educators agreed, on average, that there was a system in place to communicate with parents and caregivers in the community (Exhibit 15).

EXHIBIT 15. EDUCATOR PERCEPTIONS OF SUPPORT FOR FAMILY ENGAGEMENT

Note. Results were combined across years and cohorts for ESECP and comparison. Some respondents may have taken the survey in multiple years. $N_{\text{ESECP}} = 26$ (7 for 2021/22, 11 for 2022/23, and 8 for 2023/24). $N_{\text{Comparison}} = 5$ (all from 2021/22 or Y1). Fewer than 5 educators responded from comparison schools in other years, so results are excluded.

Parent focus group participants reported mixed levels of communication regarding their child related to communication from the district, school, ESE team, and child’s teachers. Communication was carried out through IEP meetings, notes/notebooks and phone calls home, emails, information on Skyward, quarterly progress reports, and formal and informal parent-teacher conferences/meetings. Some parents reported having meetings about their child’s IEP up to three times a year, while others reported having just one meeting (including sometimes not until close to the end of the academic year). Some parents received a response when they had a question, while others noted they did not get a response or that the response was not provided in a timely manner. Parents with children in the developmental domain more frequently noted a higher level of communication about their child. Parents reported that during IEP meetings, educators revised their children’s goals, the types of supports and services that would be provided and what they looked like. Parents also reported receiving informational emails and newsletters from the school or teachers in their child’s general education classroom.

Some parents reported that they were not informed of their child’s daily programming or progression and had to seek this information out from the educators, ESE team, and/or school administration. When parents received communication, the topics varied and included information such as about:

- Program pacing;
- Progress reports;
- Adjustments to the amount of time students would be receiving services;
- Changes to programming and assignments;
- Things to work on at home; and
- ‘Glows and Grows’ (strengths and weaknesses).

Few parents reported participation in district trainings, and some shared that they hadn’t been informed of these opportunities. Some parents reported having difficulty getting information about their rights and the services available to their child, with many attributing this to the lack of resources available and not knowing who to ask or what to ask for.

Parents of all SCPS students enrolled in ESE were asked to complete a statewide survey about their students’ education; for 2021/22 and 2022/23 the district and the evaluation team received results disaggregated by school that could be used to compare ESECP and comparison schools. Responses were mostly consistent across cohorts and between parents from ESECP and comparison schools (Exhibit 16). Only one item differed by more than 5 percentage points. Fewer parents from ESECP schools agreed that they were given information on parent training about special education (ESECP = 69%; Comparison = 74%).

EXHIBIT 16. PARENT AGREEMENT ON SCHOOL PERFORMANCE AND PARENT INVOLVEMENT IN SPECIAL EDUCATION

	ESECP (n = 7 schools)	Comparison (n = 12 schools)	Difference
My child's IEP tells how progress towards goals will be measured.	93.0	92.5	0.5
Teachers are available to speak with me.	94.0	91.2	2.8
The school has a person on staff who is available to answer parents' questions.	91.2	93.8	-2.5
ESE teachers make accommodations and modifications as indicated on my child's IEP.	92.3	90.3	2.0
The principal sets a positive and welcoming tone in the school.	90.3	91.9	-1.6
Teachers set appropriate goals for my child.	90.1	91.9	-1.8

	ESECP (n = 7 schools)	Comparison (n = 12 schools)	Difference
School personnel show sensitivity to the needs of students with disabilities and their families.	89.6	91.6	-1.9
The school provides my child with all the services documented on my child's IEP.	88.0	91.1	-3.1
General education teachers make accommodations and modifications as indicated on my child's IEP.	88.6	90.0	-1.4
The school offers parents a variety of ways to communicate with teachers.	88.7	89.5	-0.8
I am considered an equal partner with teachers and other professionals in planning my child's program.	86.2	90.3	-4.1
School personnel encourage me to participate in the decision-making process.	88.8	87.1	1.6
My child's Individual Educational Plan (IEP) covers all appropriate aspects of my child's development.	87.8	86.8	1.0
I was offered special assistance so that I could participate in the IEP meeting.	85.1	89.4	-4.2
Overall, I am satisfied with the school's efforts to facilitate my involvement in my child's education.	88.2	85.9	2.3
The school gives parents the help they may need to play an active role in their child's education.	85.2	86.8	-1.6
School personnel seek out parent input.	83.7	83.4	0.4
The school gives me choices with regard to services that address my child's needs.	84.4	82.2	2.2
The school communicates regularly with me regarding my child's progress on IEP goals.	77.3	80.8	-3.5
The school explains what options parents have if they disagree with a decision of the school.	75.6	76.0	-0.4
I was given information about organizations that offer support for parents of students with disabilities.	72.9	78.2	-5.3
I was given information on parent training about special education.	69.1	73.6	-4.5

Note. Numbers represent the percentage of respondents that agreed with each item. Results are summarized at the school level. Cells highlighted in blue indicate that average percentages across ESECP and comparison schools differed by 5% or more.

Parents who participated in focus groups were involved in their children's education in various ways. All reported attending IEP meetings, and many also reported attending parent-teacher conferences, sought information around their child's learning, and wanted to support that learning at home. Several parents expressed that it took a lot of advocating and time to get their child the services needed. Some mentioned that they had spoken to the teacher about their child's difficulties and others noted that the teacher had expressed concerns to them, while other children had medical documentation. All mentioned that it took a long time, in some cases the entire school year or more, to get their child the testing, services, and accommodations they needed. Parents were informed that this delay was due to collecting the data needed to support the services, which started with their child receiving tiered support services, which most parents didn't find helpful. Parents with a child who had a diagnosed disability (e.g., dyslexia, autism spectrum disorder, or attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder) were frustrated that their child was not provided with the services that were known to be needed. A few parents shared that they had to retain, and pay for out-of-pocket, an external advocate to get the services to which their child was entitled. Some parents reported that it could take up to four months

into the academic year for support programming to begin and others shared that they felt their child was falling through the cracks.

[It's] taking too long to get students identified; kids are losing time in a critical learning period; [they] need to do more earlier instead of waiting until later; it seems like the district is comfortable waiting for students to fail. (Cohort 3 Parent)

If we didn't have an advocate, [we] would have a different experience, and my [child] wouldn't be getting the services needed. (Cohort 3 Parent)

Although parents were frustrated with certain aspects of ESE services, nearly all were overwhelmingly happy with their child's ESE educators and team. While some expressed frustration with the limited communication, they understood educators' workloads, and were happy overall with the progress their child had been making. Parents reported that their child's teacher took the time to learn and understand the students' needs and how to find what would work for them, such as incorporating manipulatives during math and/or one-on-one assistance for reading. Many shared that their child liked their ESE teachers and team as well, and liked what they were working on and how the educator worked with them. Many indicated that programming improved if their child had been identified in the district for longer than a year, and in turn their child had made gains. Many parents attributed the negative aspects of services to a lack of resources. Lacking resources included funding for qualified educators and paraprofessionals, time for communication about their child's learning, and resources for testing and other evaluations,

Parents made several suggestions for improvement to ESE support services, including allowing the school to conduct some of the testing and documentation so that the process can move faster, and to allow, with parental consent, implementation of some support beyond the tiered system. Some parents advocated for an increase in the amount of time for services provided for their child. This included academic services, to allow students to learn at a faster and more consistent rate; and other services like speech, to allow students more time to work on areas of weakness. Other parents reported wanting more continuity around IEP services across academic years, not having the same conversation at IEP meetings about the child's needs and goals, and to make sure their child's IEP was being met. Parents would also like more opportunities to communicate with the ESE educators and team to be more informed about their child's programming, including what they are working on, how they are progressing, and how to support them at home. They would like to know what their child qualifies for and the services available, or resources/referrals to address anything to support their child's development. They would also like to have to have this information, including that within their child's IEP, to be written in understandable and user-friendly language.

FIDELITY TO ESECP KEY COMPONENTS AND DOSAGE

Exhibit 17 presents scores for each district-level indicator of implementation fidelity during the first year of implementation for each cohort. Across cohorts, fidelity expectations were met for: (1) most indicators within TOA and BA coaching and training, (2) few indicators of administrator training, (3) no indicators of ESE educator training, and (4) all indicators for parent training and communication. Implementation for Cohort 3 met most expectations for district monitoring and support (a key component that was added in 2022/23). Across cohorts, implementation fidelity thresholds were met for only 1 of 6 key components. For details about each indicator and key component, see Appendix F.

EXHIBIT 17. ESECP IMPLEMENTATION FIDELITY AT DISTRICT LEVEL

Key Component	Cohort 1 (2021/22)		Cohort 2 (2022/23)		Cohort 3 (2023/24)	
	District Score	Threshold Met	District Score	Threshold Met	District Score	Threshold Met
ESECP Teachers on Assignment (TOA) Training and Coaching	5/8		4/6		8/10	
Behavior Analyst (BA) Training and Coaching	6/9		3/5		5/10	
Administrator Training and Coaching	1/3		2/6		1/6	
ESE Educator Training	0/3		0/4		0/6	
Parent Training and Communication	2/3		4/4		4/4	
District Monitoring and Support	--		4/5		8/12	

= Threshold not met. = Threshold met.

Site Reviews. Exhibit 18 shows that all classrooms (defined as a classroom or educator where students receive instruction in the academic or developmental domain) **improved between the first and second semester**, as much as ten percentage points for academic classrooms and as much as 43 percentage points in the second semester. Cohorts 2 and 3 made the most improvement between semesters.. See Appendix G for more detail.

EXHIBIT 18. SITE REVIEWS FOR ESECP CLASSROOMS: TOTAL PERCENT IMPLEMENTATION IN THE FIRST YEAR OF IMPLEMENTATION ACROSS COHORTS

Cohort	Mean Percent			
	Academic		Developmental	
	Fall	Winter	Fall	Winter
Cohort 1	60.9	67.8	44.0	47.3
Cohort 2	58.6	68.4	31.3	71.1
Cohort 3	77.1	83.6	13.2	56.6

Note. A=Academic. D=Developmental.

Exhibit 19 presents information about classroom implementation, on average, in the analytic sample. In particular:

- **Mathematics.** Students were placed in groups of four, were pulled for about half of recommended school days (49%), were 47 lessons behind schedule, completed a total of 48 lessons, and were placed in recommended groups about 75 to 88% of the time.
- **Decoding.** Students were placed in groups of six, were pulled for just over half of recommended school days (59%), were 32 lessons behind schedule, and completed a total of 69 lessons.
- **Comprehension.** Students were placed in groups of four, were pulled for half of recommended school days (50%), were 54 lessons behind schedule, and completed a total of 42 lessons. Across reading groups, students were placed in recommended groups about 78 to 91% of the time.
- **Mathematics and Reading.** The percentage of groups held at the recommended level was higher in the first semester. Because groups did not meet expectations in the first semester, it was more difficult to meet recommendations in the second semester.

EXHIBIT 19. CLASSROOM IMPLEMENTATION FIDELITY AND DOSAGE

Subject	Fidelity or Dosage Indicator	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>
Mathematics	Average Number of Students in Group	137	4	2	1	8
	Average Percent of School Days Pulled	136	49	13	16	72
	Average Number of Lessons on or off Track	135	-47	25	-98	14
	Percentage of Groups Held at Recommended Level (First Semester)	427	88	21	0	100
	Percentage of Groups Held at Recommended Level (Second Semester)	482	75	28	0	100
Decoding	Average Number of Students in Group	263	6	3	1	13
	Average Percent of School Days Pulled	263	59	12	29	84
	Average Number of Lessons on or off Track	263	-32	29	-90	66
Comprehension	Average Number of Students in Group	131	4	2	1	8
	Average Percent of School Days Pulled	130	50	14	19	76
	Average Number of Lessons on or off Track	129	-54	28	-107	0
Overall Reading	Percentage of Groups Held at Recommended Level (First Semester)	291	91	18	0	100
	Percentage of Groups Held at Recommended Level (Second Semester)	346	78	26	0	100

Note. Mathematics *N* = 554. Reading *N* = 599. Scores were calculated using direct instruction group records for each student who was included in the analytic sample for the impact analyses. When students participated in multiple groups within a subject, their average scores across groups were considered. Scores are prorated if a student entered a group late and/or withdrew from a group early. Overall reading scores are presented for the percentage of groups held at the recommended level, and disaggregated by decoding and comprehension groups for the other indicators. Mathematics does not include subgroups.

FACTORS AFFECTING IMPLEMENTATION

Facilitators (Evaluation Question 3). Respondents in the cohorts identified several factors that facilitated effective ESECP implementation. **Many respondents thought that one of the strongest factors affecting implementation was the level of buy-in from administrators and ESE educators.** They reported that administrator and educator buy-in led to creating and following a master schedule, general education educator awareness of how time was used and protection of that time by not asking for other tasks to be worked on, and better attendance at trainings and collaboration with coaching staff. Multiple respondents identified the structured approach provided by ESECP as a facilitator through its contribution to ESE educators' teaching effectiveness, emphasis on use of student data, and provision of in-person coaching and ongoing support. Other project facilitators that were mentioned included:

- **Collaborative support among district ESECP staff;**
- **Collaboration between school and district ESECP staff;**
- The research-based, high-quality **materials** that were scripted, progressive, and easy to use;
- the ability of the program to **meet the needs of students** regardless of their level of function or skill deficit; and
- Participation in the **summer training** which assisted in the effective implementation of ESECP and supported knowledge of how to input and track data. In particular, participation in the intensive three-to-five-day training was reported as being very important to educator understanding of the 'what and why' of programming and how to implement with fidelity.

Challenges (Evaluation Question 3). Respondents mentioned several challenges that affected implementation including:

- **New administrators and ESE educators, or ESE educators who were hired mid-year.** Respondents reported that when an administrator or educator was hired after training had been conducted, their understanding of the program and how to implement it with fidelity suffered. ESE educators shared that it was difficult to review all the program components during the one-on-one sessions when they do not have the initial foundational information and skills needed;
- **Scheduling intervention activities.** Challenges were attributed to difficulties with school administrator and/or ESE educator understanding of the programming and scheduling and staffing. Respondents shared that the timing of the groups posed a challenge. For instance, many educators shared that math was at the end of the day and that the students had difficulty focusing and putting in the effort needed. Conversely, when the intervention period was at the very beginning of the day, there were more attendance issues with the students; and
- **School needs and the number of classrooms or groups that could be convened.** Respondents commented that several schools did not have enough staff and/or staff who were consistently there to provide the number of classrooms and/or groups needed. This led to large number of students in some groups and large difference among the grade levels of students.

IMPACT (EVALUATION QUESTIONS 4 AND 5)

Impact models tested using HLM to address Evaluation Questions 4 and 5 revealed **no significant difference in mathematics outcomes between students who participated in ESECP schools and those in comparison schools** after controlling for baseline achievement and student characteristics ($\beta=-2.10$, ns) (Exhibit 20). No mathematics subtest scores were significantly different between ESECP and comparison students (Appendix H, Exhibit H1).

EXHIBIT 20. ESECP IMPACT ON IREADY OVERALL MATHEMATICS

Predictor	Coefficient	SE	Significance
ESECP	-2.10	1.32	ns
Intercept	427.84	2.34	***
Cohort			
Cohort 1	3.46	1.55	*
Cohort 2	-1.13	1.64	Ns
Grade			
Grade K	-11.06	3.67	**
Grade 1	-6.68	3.07	*
Grade 2	-8.51	2.52	***
Grade 3	-1.48	2.00	Ns
Grade 4	2.50	1.79	Ns
Female	-4.29	1.25	***
Nonwhite	-3.00	1.24	*
Number of Exceptionalities	-1.69	0.84	*
Number of Areas Served	-0.88	0.59	Ns
Number of Academic Areas Served	-1.60	0.99	Ns
Behavior	-1.20	2.77	0.66
Pretest	0.74	0.03	***

Note. $N = 1,108$. Findings are based on the final analytic model. Cohort 3 is the reference group for Cohort. Grade 5 is the reference group for grade. Number of exceptionalities, number of areas served, number of academic areas served, and baseline scores were grand mean centered, meaning coefficients indicate weight relative to the average for all schools in the study in SCPS.

There were **no significant differences in reading outcomes between students who participated in ESECP schools and those in comparison schools** after controlling for baseline achievement and student characteristics ($\beta=-4.32$, ns) (Exhibit 21). On reading subscales, there was one negative effect on phonological awareness after one year ($\beta=-12.65$, $p < .05$). No other subscale was significantly different between ESECP and comparison students (Appendix H, Exhibit H2).

EXHIBIT 21. ESECP IMPACT ON IREADY OVERALL READING

Predictor	Coefficient	SE	Significance
ESECP	-4.32	2.63	ns
Intercept	496.34	4.54	***
Cohort			
Cohort 1	5.16	2.80	ns
Cohort 2	-1.85	3.19	ns
Grade			
Grade K	-33.37	5.82	***
Grade 1	-33.61	4.65	***
Grade 2	-21.32	3.91	***
Grade 3	4.46	3.14	ns
Grade 4	-9.12	2.91	**
Nonwhite	-3.12	2.05	ns
Free or Reduced Price Meals	-4.21	2.84	ns
Number of Exceptionalities	-2.93	1.38	*
Number of Areas Served	0.43	1.12	ns
Number of Academic Areas Served	-7.20	1.64	**
Behavior	5.77	4.57	ns
Pretest	0.71	0.03	***

Note. $N = 1,198$. Findings are based on the final analytic model. Cohort 3 is the reference group for Cohort. Grade 5 is the reference group for grade. Number of exceptionalities, number of areas served, number of academic areas served, and baseline scores were grand mean centered, meaning coefficients indicate weight relative to the average for all schools in the study in SCPS.

The impact analyses were also replicated using FAST scores after one year as the outcome for Cohorts 2 and 3 (Cohort 1 only had FSA scores prior to the statewide assessment change). These analyses only included grades 3 through 5. There were no significant differences for mathematics ($\beta = -3.68$, ns) or reading ($\beta = -0.64$, ns). Because one school in Cohort 3 only implemented ESECP for half the year, the analyses were also tested excluding those students as a sensitivity test, and the same pattern of results held with no significant differences for mathematics ($\beta = -2.04$, ns) or reading ($\beta = -4.11$, ns).

The percentage of students who improved grade level placement on the iReady from fall to spring was not substantially higher for students in the ESECP condition. For some reading subtests, the percentage of students in the comparison condition who improved grade level placements was more than 5% different from the percentage of students in the ESECP condition who improved. In particular, fewer students in the ESECP condition improved on phonics (-6%), vocabulary (-7%), comprehension of literature (-9%) and comprehension of informational text (-7%). See Exhibit 22.

EXHIBIT 22. PERCENTAGE OF STUDENTS WHO IMPROVED THEIR GRADE LEVEL PLACEMENT ON I-READY FROM FALL TO SPRING

Improved Grade Level Placement Subject	Comparison		ESECP		Difference in % (ESECP-Comparison)
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	
Mathematics	309	55.8	283	51.1	-4.7
Number Operations	225	40.6	204	36.8	-3.8
Algebraic Thinking	187	33.8	173	31.2	-2.5
Measurement	169	30.5	178	32.1	1.6
Geometry	160	28.9	153	27.6	-1.3
Reading	233	38.9	204	34.1	-4.8
Phonological Awareness	95	15.9	71	11.9	-4.0
Phonics	282	47.1	246	41.1	-6.0
High Frequency Words	156	26.0	143	23.9	-2.2
Vocabulary	316	52.8	275	45.9	-6.8
Comprehension of Literature	332	55.4	275	45.9	-9.5
Comprehension of Informational Text	321	53.6	277	46.2	-7.3

Note. Math *N* = 1,108. Reading *N* = 1,198. Grade level differences were identified for the analytic sample in the fall and spring of their first year of implementation. The percentage of students who improved in their grade level differences on each test and subtest are presented.

IMPACT ON SUBGROUPS (EVALUATION QUESTION 11)

No significant effects on reading or mathematics overall scores after one year of the intervention were found when examining the interactions between treatment and student characteristics that were included in final analytic models for each subject area: including gender, nonwhite, number of exceptionalities, number of areas and academic areas served, students who were supported with behavior services, pre-test scores, ELL status, FRM status, or cohort.

IMPACT OVER TIME (EVALUATION QUESTION 8)

Impact of ESECP on spring outcomes two years and three years after students' first year of ESECP participation was examined using the same final impact models. **No significant differences were found between students in ESECP and their peers in comparison schools two (for Cohorts 1 and 2) or three years (for Cohort 1) after their first year of exposure** (Appendix H; Exhibits H1 and H2). These analyses were expected to be underpowered.

MEDIATORS (EVALUATION QUESTION 9)

Attendance. Impact of ESECP on student attendance (as an indicator of engagement) was examined using the same final impact models, using prior year attendance rate as baseline (Exhibit 23) and their first-year attendance rate as the outcome (ESECP *M* = 95.48, *SD* = 4.38; Comparison *M* = 95.27, *SD* = 4.887). **No significant differences were found between students in ESECP and their peers in comparison schools one year ($\beta=-0.07$, ns) after their first year of exposure for the mathematics sample ($\beta=-0.07$, ns) or the reading sample ($\beta=0.34$, ns).**

EXHIBIT 23. ATTENDANCE BEFORE AND AFTER FIRST YEAR OF EXPOSURE FOR THE ANALYTIC SAMPLE

Outcome	N	Comparison			ESECP		
		M	SD	N	M	SD	
Mathematics							
Baseline Attendance	554	96.17	3.91	554	95.92	4.00	
Attendance after One Year	554	95.27	4.87	554	95.48	4.38	
Reading							
Baseline Attendance	599	96.22	3.81	599	96.09	3.93	
Attendance after One Year	599	95.01	5.17	599	95.60	4.28	

Dosage and Fidelity. Direct Instruction programs are designed to be administered at a minimum of 3 times per week, in a school year with 36 weeks and accounting for startup time, it should be expected that students receive at least 96 lessons. For the mathematics sample, 9% of students had at least 96 lessons. For the reading sample, 16% of students had at least 96 lessons for decoding and 5% had at least 96 lessons for comprehension. Exhibit 24 shows that, based on simple descriptive statistics, students with at least 96 lessons made more growth than students in the overall ESECP sample. Caution should be used when interpreting these findings due to small sample sizes. No statistical significance tests were conducted.

EXHIBIT 24. SCORE GROWTH FOR STUDENTS WHO MET THE LESSON THRESHOLD

Outcome	N	Overall			Students with at least 96 lessons		
		M	SD	N	M	SD	
Mathematics							
Baseline	554	398.21	45.96	14	336.57	15.23	
After One Year	554	419.97	42.96	14	375.36	17.50	
Difference	--	21.76	--	--	38.79	---	
Reading: Decoding							
Baseline	599	444.97	73.74	50	406.70	50.77	
After One Year	599	476.50	72.74	50	441.56	49.86	
Difference	--	31.53	--	--	34.86	--	
Reading: Comprehension							
Baseline	599	444.97	73.74	8	377.13	34.62	
After One Year	599	476.50	72.74	8	419.88	57.98	
Difference	--	31.53	--	--	42.75	--	

Indicators of intervention dosage and fidelity were also included as outcomes in models for the treatment samples (because there were not corresponding variables in the comparison group). Analytic models were the same as the final impact models, without the treatment indicator and the inclusion of one mediator at a time for mathematics, decoding, and comprehension. Neither the number of lessons on track nor the percentage of days pulled significantly explained student outcomes in mathematics (number of lessons on track $\beta=0.03$, ns; percent of days pulled $\beta=0.001$, ns), decoding (number of lessons on track $\beta=-0.30$, ns; percent of days pulled $\beta=-0.01$, ns), or comprehension (number of lessons on track $\beta=-0.14$, ns; percent of days pulled $\beta=-0.06$, ns).

OUTCOMES FOR STUDENTS IN THE DEVELOPMENTAL DOMAIN

Descriptive analyses show that **students in the Developmental Domain in ESECP schools made 9 point gains on understanding direction compared to 4 point gains in comparison students; and nearly 11 points in gains on listening comprehension scores compared to 3-point gains for students in comparison schools.** All other point differences on PPVT-5 and WJ-IV tests and subtests were within five points, suggesting students in the Developmental Domain experienced similar outcomes to those in the comparison condition. See Exhibit 25. Furthermore, thirteen students in the developmental domain in Grades K-5 in ESECP schools took the VB-MAPP prior to and following their first year of receiving support through ESECP during the 2023/24 academic year. All students (100%) improved their scores by at least one point, with a mean improvement of 14 points from baseline ($M = 69.88, SD = 41.86$) to spring ($M = 83.90, SD = 43.00$).

EXHIBIT 25. PEABODY PICTURE VOCABULARY TEST (5TH EDITION) AND WOODCOCK-JOHNSON IV TESTS OF ORAL LANGUAGE W-SCORES AT BASELINE AND OUTCOME FOR STUDENTS IN THE DEVELOPMENTAL DOMAIN

Score	ESECP				Comparison			
	N	Baseline Mean (SD)	Mean After One Year (SD)	Difference	N	Baseline Mean (SD)	Mean After One Year (SD)	Difference
PPVT	12	51.75 (9.31)	54.58 (11.48)	2.83	8	50.63 (15.23)	50.63 (12.87)	0.00
Broad Oral Language	15	421.07 (16.24)	426.07 (16.14)	5.00	8	410.75 (16.83)	415.13 (22.71)	4.38
Oral Language	15	419.13 (17.83)	422.13 (16.34)	3.00	8	406.38 (19.40)	411.25 (23.52)	4.87
Oral Expression	15	418.87 (22.85)	426.00 (24.15)	7.13	8	400.50 (24.69)	406.5 (28.44)	6.00
Picture Vocabulary	15	430.13 (31.34)	435.13 (28.73)	5.00	8	405.88 (36.85)	412.63 (41.65)	6.75
Oral Comprehension	15	407.93 (8.97)	408.73 (8.37)	0.80	8	406.25 (3.54)	409.25 (12.02)	3.00
Sentence Repetition	15	407.47 (16.39)	416.67 (23.74)	9.20	8	395.13 (13.00)	400.75 (17.46)	5.62
Understanding Directions	15	434.60 (17.52)	443.89 (17.52)	9.29	8	419.88 (21.87)	423.50 (22.76)	3.62
Listening Comprehension	15	421.53 (10.86)	432.44 (17.42)	10.91	8	413.00 (11.05)	416.25 (15.48)	3.25

Note. Only students with baseline and one-year outcomes were included. One student was in a comparison school for one year and in an ESECP school during a subsequent year. The score from the first year was counted among comparison students and the score from the subsequent year was counted among ESECP students. Insufficient data was available to report outcomes after two years.

PERCEPTIONS OF STUDENT OUTCOMES (EVALUATION QUESTION 5)

Educators at ESECP schools were asked to report on how ESECP had made an impact in their school on surveys. Educators agreed or strongly agreed, on average, that ESECP improved student language development, student social outcomes, behavior outcomes, academic engagement, academic achievement, parent engagement in student learning, and parent satisfaction (Exhibit 26). On average,

educators agreed more strongly after the second year of exposure to ESECP that it affected these outcomes. Scores were slightly higher for student outcomes though educators also agreed, on average, that ESECP improved parent engagement and satisfaction.

EXHIBIT 26. EDUCATORS’ PERCEPTIONS OF IMPACT OF ESECP

Note. Results were combined across years and cohorts. $N_{\text{ESECP}} = 26$ (7 for 2021/22, 11 for 2022/23, and 8 for 2023/24). $N_{\text{Comparison}} = 5$ (all from 2021/22 or Y1). Fewer than 5 educators responded from comparison schools in other years, so results are excluded.

Relationships between ESE Educators and Students. Interview and focus group respondents reported that **implementation of the curriculum helped to facilitate better relationships between ESE educators and students**. Reasons given for improved relationships included the individualization of instruction and educators better understanding of student strengths and areas identified for growth. Respondents reported that ESE educators built relationships and rapport with students at the beginning of instruction to gain buy-in which resulted in students wanting to be in school and engaged in their learning. Use of student data to guide instruction was reported as contributing to better educator understanding of student capabilities and needs and provision of needed support. Educators described providing positive reinforcement and assistance when students were struggling, which also contributed to positive student-educator relationships. Respondents mentioned that students advocated for themselves and succeeded, leading to a sense of trust with the ESE instructors. As some respondents noted:

I see the teacher-students' relationships that have been built through using the program, it has been amazing. (Cohort 1)

The routines and relationships are key. (Cohort 1)

There is a lot more positivity, the rapport is more bubbly, and students work more for their teachers. (Cohort 2)

Social/Life Skills. Almost all respondents in the three cohorts mentioned that **ESECP had an impact on students' social and life skills**. They shared that students learned to **communicate**, have a conversation, or request something. Students also worked on skills which led to participation in **less restrictive environments**. They also reported that students saw the gains they were making and became **more engaged** with the curriculum and in the classroom, which led to increased interactions with their peers. Respondents reported that students had many opportunities to show their learning in various ways which increased their self-confidence and led to a decrease in disruptive and problematic behavior. They also noted that students answered questions in class and took risks in their learning. It was also reported that ESE educators worked with students when social emotional goals were identified and incorporated the Accept-Identify-Move (AIM) socioemotional curriculum and other supplemental materials. As some respondents summarized:

[There have been] lots of years where [students have] been unsuccessful, so they develop negative coping mechanisms and problem behaviors, and what that is, is a lack of confidence. When you see students' confidence improve, so does the behavior. The teacher developed a relationship with [the students] and you see the shift happen, and [students] see that they are learning. (Cohort 1)

[Students] aren't getting in trouble as often and are making gains, so they have successes and a reason to celebrate. (Cohort 3)

Many of the parents reported changes to their child's social skill development. Some **parents shared that their child was less shy, making friends, and participating in activities with other children**. A few parents of children who had behavioral issues shared that their child was respectful to their educators, followed instructions better, and/or decreased the frequency and intensity of their aggressions or meltdowns. A few parents shared that their children would get frustrated if they did not understand something and become uncomfortable and/or were still shy and not interacting with others frequently. Many parents reported that their child had increased confidence, which they noted as key to their child developing foundational skills to support their learning and increase their achievement. Some parents shared that their child increased their enjoyment in the subject areas (ELA and/or mathematics) in which they were receiving support; while other parents still saw an avoidance and struggle in their child with the subjects. Overall, parents reported that their child liked their classes at school, from core subjects like science to specials (e.g., physical education, music, art).

The program is tailored for [my child] for that [reading and math], and with that his confidence has grown (Cohort 3).

Achievement and Academic Engagement. Respondents reported observing substantial achievement gains among students, and they pointed to improved i-Ready scores and Florida Standards Assessment data. In addition, they noted that students in developmental classrooms made gains with language and

other skills, which were documented and tracked, not just gauged subjectively. They also shared that students in academic domain made great strides and increased their skills in reading and math because the program kept them engaged in their learning and better targeted their needs. Respondents noted that the program naturally engaged students in their learning. They shared that **through the positive relationships built with their educators and the motivation they gained through their successes; students were engaged with the curriculum and in their classroom and closing the gaps within their learning levels.** Representative comments included:

Students [are] maybe not at grade level yet, but they are so far ahead from where they were. (Cohort 1)

[We have] never had anything in the district that has impacted at this level. (Cohort 1)

Students in the program are getting caught up, they are more engaged with their peers, do collaborative learning, and they are engaged in learning. (Cohort 1)

The lessons are rapid in a positive way so [students] are always engaged. They all get their turn and are all participating in some way. They love the student-teacher game and when they win they get so excited, so that's been amazing. (Cohort 1)

We see a lot of kids who shine really brightly because of this program. (Cohort 3)

Students love this program; it's predictable and that increases confidence. (Cohort 3)

With [the Curriculum Project], it gives you a roadmap and helps you figure out where to go. So for me it was really reinforcing to see the progress. (Cohort 3)

Educators in Cohorts 1 and 2 noted **that many parents appeared to think highly of the work being done with their child. Parents reported that their children had become more engaged with their learning.** Their children were excited and enjoyed going to school, put more effort into their learning, enjoyed earning rewards, shared more about their day, enjoyed bringing activities and artifacts home from school, and increased their participation in after-hours school activities like family nights or school shows. Some parents shared how their child had made great gains academically and were staying fairly on pace with their peers and were closing their grade level gap in their learning. Parents reported stronger reading skills, comprehension, and learning words, letters, and numbers and sounding them out. Parents were able to see how the intervention connected to the work their child was doing in their general education classroom, helped to close skill or knowledge gaps, and contributed to their child experiencing 'a-ha' moments with their learning and seeing personal success. Parents with students in developmental classrooms shared how they had seen improvements in their child carrying out or assisting with tasks at home, decreased behavioral outbursts and increased self-management, increased speech, and with their child's academics with reading and writing. Others shared that their child had progressed in their academics, only to see them decline again once services weren't provided at the same level/intensity; or were progressing at a slow rate, keeping them further behind their grade level.

A few parents expressed that their child was frustrated and struggled with the programming, mentioning that because their children were pulled out from the general education classroom, they missed information and had to make up homework. Some shared that their child did not like the online programming to be done at home.

[My child] is getting there. [They] are much further along than they were last year. (Cohort 3)

My [child] no longer says "I can't read." That's a big improvement this year. (Cohort 3)

Astonishing work, not every day is successful, but little by little [my child] is learning it. (Cohort 3)

ESE EDUCATOR OUTCOMES: PERCEPTIONS, SATISFACTION, AND RETENTION (EVALUATION QUESTION 6)

Instructional Practices. ESE educators reported being happy to have an ESE curriculum provided, especially one that was evidence-based. Prior to the implementation of ESECP, ESE educators reported that they were typically responsible for finding their own resources to use with the students, and that the ESECP provided defined curricula, gave them a framework through which to place students in the curricula, and guidance on how to implement the structured curricula. This guidance and structure contributed to improved educator practice due to better understanding of how to deliver the curricula through direct instruction and use of data to modify instruction. Respondents noted that the use of ESECP curricula and grouping of students allowed them to differentiate instruction in ways that supported student learning.

Respondents also shared that they liked the structure, predictability, and signaling of the program. However, several educators mentioned that they deviated from expectations, adjusting the program to their students' learning styles and behavioral needs to facilitate student learning. Educators shared that older students were not as motivated by the check marks and scripts, so they used other methods. They also reported having to make adjustments when new students joined groups to meet their learning needs, while also staying on track for the group.

Educators were asked about the extent to which they agreed that they implemented best practices in classroom organization, planning and training, instructional delivery, and assessment. Average ratings among educators in all cohorts suggested agreement that these practices were used (Exhibit 27). **On average, educators from ESECP schools had higher ratings of agreement that they emphasized instructional practices across all cohorts compared to educators from comparison schools.**

EXHIBIT 27. EDUCATORS' SELF-PERCEPTIONS OF INSTRUCTIONAL PRACTICES (SPRING ONLY)

Note. Results were combined across years and cohorts for ESECP and comparison educators. $N_{\text{ESECP}} = 26$ (7 for 2021/22, 11 for 2022/23, and 8 for 2023/24). $N_{\text{Comparison}} = 5$ (all from 2021/22 or Y1). Fewer than 5 educators responded from comparison schools in other years, so results are excluded. At the end of each school year educators were asked to rate their level of agreement with multiple statements regarding their use of best instructional practices in different areas. For example, an item from the classroom organization scale is 'In my classroom, seating is appropriate for children.'

Classroom Management. There was **broad agreement among respondents across cohorts that the use of ESECP had a beneficial impact on student behavior in the classroom.** Respondents reported that, when the program was implemented, classrooms ran smoothly due to the structure; educators and students knew what they were doing and what they were going to do next. Educators were accountable for what they were engaged in with the students at various points in time during the lesson and throughout the day. Students were familiar with the schedule and benefitted from the consistency and routine, which included regular feedback, praise, and positive reinforcement—and those elements helped to minimize behavioral issues. Through earning points from behaviors, tasks, games, or other earning activity, students saw themselves being successful, and that furthered their engagement in lessons. Educators modeled behavior and continuously engaged students. Representative comments included:

Kids know what they are doing. They are getting the materials, and everyone knows what's going on, and with a lot of these kids they need that routine and it's on their level, a lot of times there is no reason to act out, so that helps with behavior. (Cohort 1)

When the students know a way to communicate, their negative behavior decreases significantly. (Cohort 1)

[Students] have grown to seem more confident. I heard “dude, I’m reading” or “we’re in this class because we need to learn” the other day. (Cohort 2)

The pace gives kids very little time to misbehave, and they like the format and flow. (Cohort 2)

It’s difficult for students to be off task when there is such a high level of expectation and engagement in that moment; there’s no down time. (Cohort 3)

If you don’t have the classroom management in place the other things won’t work. You can’t move forward if you don’t have those conditions for learning in place. (Cohort 3)

Educator Satisfaction, Preparedness, and Retention. Educators rated their satisfaction with various factors related to teaching special education, including with the support they received from school leadership, co-workers, and parents; the quality of relationships with colleagues; availability of and access to resources, services, and professional learning opportunities; student behavior and discipline at the school; and opportunities to plan and complete paperwork. On average, educators reported feeling satisfied in fall and spring, with insubstantial increases over time after one and two years of exposure to ESECP (Exhibit 28). See Appendix I, Exhibit I1 for the average ratings of satisfaction for each individual area over time.

EXHIBIT 28. CHANGES IN EDUCATOR SATISFACTION

Note. Results were combined across years and cohorts for ESECP and comparison educators. $N_{\text{ESECP}} = 26$ (7 for 2021/22, 11 for 2022/23, and 8 for 2023/24). $N_{\text{Comparison}} = 5$ (all from 2021/22 or Y1). Fewer than 5 educators responded from comparison schools in other years, so results are excluded.

Preparedness. Survey respondents were asked to rate how prepared they felt to do activities involving assessment; collaboration; instruction; and supporting student social, emotional, and behavioral wellbeing. On average, educators from all groups felt moderately prepared overall and for instruction, with no more than a quarter-point increase from fall to spring (Exhibit 29). See Appendix I, Exhibit I2 for more detail.

EXHIBIT 29. CHANGES IN EDUCATOR PREPAREDNESS

Note. Results were combined across years and cohorts for ESECP and comparison educators. $N_{\text{ESECP}} = 26$ (7 for 2021/22, 11 for 2022/23, and 8 for 2023/24). $N_{\text{Comparison}} = 5$ (all from 2021/22 or Y1). Fewer than 5 educators responded from comparison schools in other years, so results are excluded.

Educators were asked how likely they were to continue in the teaching profession, teaching in their current school, and teaching in special education. On average, 90 to 95% of educators in ESECP schools stated they were likely to continue teaching in the profession, in their current school, and in special education, compared to 80% of comparison educators (Exhibit 30).

EXHIBIT 30. EDUCATOR INTENTION TO CONTINUE IN PROFESSION, IN THEIR SCHOOL, AND IN SPECIAL EDUCATION

Note. Results were combined across years and cohorts for ESECP and comparison educators. $N_{\text{ESECP}} = 26$ (7 for 2021/22, 11 for 2022/23, and 8 for 2023/24). $N_{\text{Comparison}} = 5$ (all from 2021/22 or Y1). Fewer than 5 educators responded from comparison schools in other years, so results are excluded.

Findings from interviews echoed surveys and administrative data. As one respondent stated:

With the use of ESECP, I see teachers saying, “My student is able to do something they couldn’t do before.” It makes teachers love what they do and appreciate what they are doing for these kids. If you face frustration every day, you will leave the profession. This inspires teachers to stay. (Cohort 1)

Descriptive analysis was performed to examine rates of educator retention in the same job/position in the same school from fall of each year to the subsequent year. Exhibit 31 shows educator retention rate by group and by school. **Of the ESE educators assigned to ESECP schools, 74% to 85% remained in the same school from one year to the next.** Over three-quarters of educators held the same job from fall 2021 to fall 2022 and fall 2023 to fall 2024 and a similar pattern was found with those who held the same job in the same school. Jobs were coded differently in the 2022/23 academic year so the drop in educators holding the same job (20%) could be due to misaligned job codes.

EXHIBIT 31. EDUCATOR RETENTION IN ESECP SCHOOLS

	Fall 2021 to Fall 2022 (N=27)		Fall 2022 to Fall 2023 (N=65)		Fall 2023 to Fall 2024 (N=87)	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
School Assignment						
Different School	3	11.1	0	0.0	16	18.4
Same School	20	74.1	55	84.6	67	77.0
Job Assignment						
Different Job	2	7.4	39	60.0	18	20.7
Same Job	21	77.8	26	40.0	69	79.3
Job and School Assignment						
Different Job, Different School	1	3.7	0	0.0	6	6.9
Same Job, Different School	2	7.4	0	0.0	10	11.5
Different Job, Same School	1	3.7	29	52.7	8	9.3
Same Job, Same School	19	70.4	26	47.3	59	67.8
Unidentifiable	4	14.8	10	15.4	4	4.6

QUALITY OF ESECP

Interview and focus group respondents across the three cohorts reported being **pleased with the quality of ESECP programming**. Several mentioned that they appreciated that programming was **evidence-based** and offered a **structured curriculum for developmental students**. Many respondents shared that in most developmental classrooms (in non-ESECP schools) there was a lack of guidelines or support, and many educators looked for their own materials to use with their students. Additionally, respondents said that students receiving ESE services in non-ESECP schools engaged in Tier 3 programming for academic intervention, but that was more generalized and didn’t focus on the **specific individual needs of students**. With ESECP programming, everyone involved with the project, from district staff to ESE educators, was **trained and supported**. Educators worked together to identify any implementation issues, reviewed data to support students’ skill development, and supported classroom implementation.

Educators also shared that they liked that the program had phonics, fluency, and comprehension all together, where previously they would just work with students on guided reading and assisting with IEP goals, which included assistance with grade-level assignments. Some educators shared that the math curriculum was not as strong as for reading, and that the math lessons moved very slowly and were time consuming. Educators indicated that many aspects of the program were highly beneficial to students, including the routines and structures, reinforcement, and documentation on progress. However, **several educators expressed that their students were frustrated with the repetitiveness of the programming**, and shared that if a student had mastered most everything of the unit, except one component, programming required the student to go through the entire unit again and re-do all the lessons they had previously completed. Educators indicated that they felt it would be better to focus on the one concept that the student didn't understand, instead of having the students go through everything again when understanding of the other pieces had already been demonstrated. Additionally, many respondents shared that students stayed in a group until retesting occurred, which was conducted by district level ESECP staff. Respondents expressed that they did not like the length of time it took to test students and move them to the next point of programming service, and that students were sometimes waiting and not continuing with their intensive learning. They felt that some of the testing should be conducted by the school to better serve students.

[ESECP] only reflects the data of that day, and is not always accurate of how the students is doing and what they are learning. (Cohort 3)

Several educators expressed their **desire to have more autonomy over their classrooms** and indicated that they knew what worked best with and for their students, where to push for more and where to let it be for a moment and allow the student to reflect. Furthermore, some educators reported that **some of the structures and certain aspects of the program did not work for some students due to their diagnosis and were not aligned with their learning needs**. They shared that they wanted to better meet students where they were in their learning, but the programming was very rigid, which posed a challenge. Some educators expressed that they felt they were not assisting students with what they were working on in their grade-level curriculum; and/or that the students being pulled out caused them to miss the grade-level curriculum. These missed opportunities resulted in students being unable to pass assessments and their being behind and separated from their peers. Respondent quotes that highlighted the quality of ESECP program included:

[ESECP] gives [ESE educators] the tools they need to help each student progress. (Cohort 1)

The difference with [ESECP] is about helping schools change the way that they practice. Part of it is the curriculum and fidelity; but thinking about these kids differently and thinking about a growth mindset of what progress we are going to make [also] makes a difference. (Cohort 1)

[ESE programming before ESECP] was a formless blob of doing whatever. There was no student data, no guidance for teachers, no direction on how or why; but when there is a system in place then you are going to get better progress [with students]. (Cohort 1)

[ESECP] focuses on goals not just accommodations. So much comes about when we change our mindset. (Cohort 1)

People don't believe the success stories; they don't think that kids will be able to buy into the scripted curriculum. Until they do it and see that it works. That's surprising to them. (Cohort 2)

Before using the [ESECP] materials, I wasn't doing formal testing. It's better this way: seeing one to two grade level gaps closing for many students. We're closing some big gaps and confidence is growing. (Cohort 2)

[ESECP programming] is so explicit and clear, easy in terms of planning, easy to leave for a [substitute teacher]. The data is huge and helps us keep up with the IEP data. It's a lot of data upkeep, but it pays off and helps us to be able to see and show gains. We're not just making things up with random materials like in the past; this is data-based and supported. (Cohort 2)

We have a positive overall feel about ESECP, [the program] is effective if it's done correctly, we just would love a little more flexibility with scheduling and [working with] students to make sure we teach them in the most effective way for them to progress. (Cohort 3)

SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT (EVALUATION QUESTION 3)

Respondents provided several suggestions for improvement, including:

- **Increase staff at the school and district level.** Respondents suggested having someone at the school who could provide **daily program support and oversight or having the coaches come to the school more frequently.**
- **Make training more available and encourage more participation.** Training topics of interest include data use and behavior management.
- **Require school administrators and ESE educators to observe programming before implementation at their school.**
- **Inform school administrators about the content of coaching activities** each week and planned content for the upcoming week.
- **Share with the school as a whole how ESECP is aligned to and supports general education standards.**
- **Allow educators flexibility with program implementation** to meet all the needs of the students; including having the ability to test and move students forward in their learning.
- **Build in time in the pacing of the curriculum for routine school activities** (drills, testing, field trips, absences of students and educators) and provide a progression plan so that educators have a better understanding around the process and progression of units and groups.

ALIGNMENT WITH DISTRICT GOALS FOR STUDENTS RECEIVING ESE SERVICES

Respondents were asked how the project aligned with district goals. School and district respondents in each of the cohorts reported that **the project was closely aligned with the district goal of every child achieving one year's growth in one year's time.** They noted that district administrators, coaches, and school administrators set goals at the beginning of the year and incorporated Access Points⁷ and standards into the lessons. **Many respondents across the three cohorts reported that ESECP closed gaps between students receiving ESE services and their peers, developed student skills, and increased student inclusion with their peers in general education classrooms.** Respondents agreed that the project raised expectations for student progress among students receiving ESE services, gave the

⁷ Access Points are academic achievement expectations that are aligned with Florida's standards and written for students who have significant cognitive disabilities.

support needed to raise academic achievement, and provided data to monitor and validate student growth. As some respondents shared:

[With the progress monitoring data] we can say how much [students] have learned in a year, and we can troubleshoot if students are not mastering the skills. (Cohort 1)

We are on track to meet our goals for ESE students. It's how we move them through the program, and it gets them on grade-level material quicker. (Cohort 1)

[We have] evidence of 77 students moving out of developmental to academic or [general education classrooms]. People used to think you couldn't move these students; it produces a large gain in quality of life for students. (Cohort 2)

PROGRESS TOWARD ESECP DISSEMINATION AND SUSTAINABILITY (EVALUATION QUESTION 10)

Conference and Meeting Presentations. Two behavior analysts who are part of the District ESECP staff presented a poster session at the 2022 Florida Association for Behavior Analysis (FABA) conference, held in September 2022.⁸ The session, entitled *Incentivizing Teacher Performance in Public Schools*, discussed provision of incentives and structured feedback to exceptional student teachers to help educators with effective classroom instruction. The poster was awarded Best Clinical Application.

Staff from RMC and SCPS conducted a virtual poster session entitled *Documenting Implementation of a Model Supporting Students with Disabilities: The Exceptional Student Education Curriculum Project*⁹ in April 2022 at the American Educational Research Association (AERA) Annual Meeting (San Diego, CA) to describe how the ESECP evaluation examines fidelity, implementation, and impact of a whole-school approach to exceptional student education. The authors presented findings from the 2020/21 pilot study that suggested the program is positively related to student academic and behavioral outcomes. The authors provided key design elements planned for the subsequent rigorous quasi-experimental study (using data collected during 2021/22 through 2023/24) that is intended to meet *What Works Clearinghouse* evidence standards with reservations. Lessons learned were shared from the development of a concrete measure of fidelity. These tools may support researchers who wish to design and implement similar studies.

District ESECP staff presented to the SCPS School Board in September 2022. The in-person presentation highlighted goals of the project and implementation, including testimonials from an ESE educator and a parent. Overall benefits of the program included continuity across the district in using an evidence-based approach; follow-up training and support for staff to ensure fidelity of implementation; weekly on-site support from district personnel; and students closing gaps. Board members were appreciative of the program, were moved by the testimonials, complimented the team on its work, and expressed the desire for the program to be implemented districtwide.

⁸ Machita, J., & O'Connor, A. (2022, September). *Incentivizing performance in public schools*. Poster session presented at the Florida Association for Behavioral Analysis Conference, Ponte Vedra, FL.

⁹ Espel Villarreal, E., Weston-Sementelli, J., Meyer, S., Fredericks, L., & Guffee, M. (2022, April). *Documenting implementation of a model supporting students with disabilities: The Exceptional Student Education Curriculum Project*. Poster session presented virtually at the American Educational Association Annual Meeting, San Diego, CA. <https://aera22-aera.ipostersessions.com/?s=9D-3C-70-B5-CD-51-C9-AF-6D-70-32-57-1D-B3-91-18> (available online).

Staff from ESECP and RMC gave a virtual presentation in October 2022 at the EIR Project Directors and Evaluators Technical Assistance Meeting: *Creating Possibilities: Considerations for Effective Partnerships between Educators and Project Teams*.¹⁰ The goal was to help grantees and evaluators identify key features of partnerships that are actionable, relevant, and useful. It highlighted features, strengths, and challenges found within two EIR projects funded in 2019 that are being conducted within large school districts including ESECP. Through consistent communication, creative opportunities for collaboration, and clearly identified roles, these teams have found a strong base from which to operate the evaluation and the project. For example, the ESECP team shared their experience in developing a fidelity matrix and a deep understanding of associated program data, providing useful information to both the evaluator and the program team while maintaining independence of the evaluation. ESECP District Staff also are responsive to requests from other districts and the state education agency about the programming.

An in-person poster session entitled *Using District-Administered Assessments to Evaluate District Programming with Validity*¹¹ was presented by ESECP and RMC staff in April 2023 at the Annual AERA Meeting (Chicago, IL). The paper described challenges related to recruitment and administration of student outcome assessments and the validation of a widely-administered district assessment used in its place to address these challenges. Findings show moderate to strong correlations between overall scores and subtests for iReady and WJ-IV in the domains of reading, oral language, and mathematics. The correlations suggest they measure related constructs and that this assessment substitution for confirmatory analyses is a valid way to measure outcomes for a study conducted in a district setting.

An in-person roundtable session entitled *Using Individualized Education Plans to Support the Evaluation of Special Education Programs*¹² was presented by ESECP and RMC staff in April 2025 at the Annual AERA Meeting (Denver, CO). Programs for students receiving Exceptional Student Education (ESE) service are rarely evaluated using rigorous methodology. Considering the unique needs of students with disabilities, this paper illustrated how categorizing IEP services was used to help identify a matched comparison sample to: (1) improve the rigor of an evaluation of a whole-school ESE model; and (2) could contribute to improved service provision and understanding of ESE implementation. The IEP coding methods and baseline equivalence results were shared. Guidance provided by the USDOE requires IEPs to be personalized to each student, but this mandate does not restrain schools, districts, or states from standardizing the encoding of services provided wherever possible. Such efforts would streamline translation of IEPs between schools and districts, encourage better data-informed decision making with ESE professionals, and provide researchers with the tools to identify appropriate matched comparisons with baseline equivalence when studying this population.

Leadership is also preparing a comprehensive manual to support replication of the ESECP model in other districts. This manual will include all documents that district leaders can use to support implementation in their district.

¹⁰ Guffee, M., Ridgley, L., Meyer, S., & Weston-Sementelli, J. (2022, October). *Creating possibilities: Considerations for effective partnerships between educators and project teams*. Session presented virtually at the Education Innovation (EIR) Project Directors and Evaluators Technical Assistance Meeting.

¹¹ Espel Villarreal, E., Weston-Sementelli, J., Guffee, M., & Meyer, S. (2023, April). *Using District-Administered Assessments to evaluate district programming with validity*. Poster session presented at the American Educational Association Annual Meeting, Chicago, IL.

¹² Kuhn, M., Weston-Sementelli, J., Espel Villarreal, E., Meyer, S. & Guffee, M. (2025, April). *Using Individualized Education Plans to Support the Evaluation of Special Education Programs*. Roundtable session presented at the American Educational Association Annual Meeting, Denver, CO.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section presents limitations, a summary of findings, and recommendations from the RMC evaluation of the implementation and impact of ESECP from 2021/22 through 2023/24.

LIMITATIONS

Several limitations should be noted. Implementation progress was substantially constrained by accommodations related to the COVID-19 pandemic early in the project and several planned project activities were not conducted as anticipated. Analyses designed to answer exploratory research questions were expected to be underpowered and should be interpreted with caution. Lastly, data collection was also limited due to challenges related to COVID-19 and low response rates overall. For example, there were limited responses from ESE instructors to surveys, interviews and focus groups, and few parents participated in the evaluation until the third cohort. Findings from surveys, interviews, and focus groups may not represent stakeholder groups.

FINDINGS: IMPLEMENTATION

School and district staff had a shared understanding of ESECP project components and elements associated with implementation success. Interview and focus group respondents discussed training provided to TOAs, BAs, administrators, and ESE educators, parent communication, master schedules, assessment to place students and ongoing progress monitoring, and the need for successful incorporation of routines into classrooms. For example, interview and focus group respondents shared that when schools successfully created a master schedule to integrate the components required by the project, educators struggled less and had the time needed for project implementation.

SCPS staff generally characterized the quality of ESECP training as excellent. District administrators, school administrators, and district ESECP staff described training provided to TOAs, BAs, ESE educators, school administrators, and paraeducators including: skills training; pre-coaching site visits; and single-day, multi-day, and monthly training activities. Respondents reported that training for TOAs and BAs was sufficient and described deep involvement in program implementation and oversight by project leadership. Nearly all respondents stated that the hands-on components of the trainings worked best for educators to support their understanding of the curriculum and implementation. Respondents also emphasized that the training included well-defined program goals, outlined the program processes, and was clear on how it should be implemented. On average, educator survey ratings of professional learning activities were consistently between “good” and “very good” across most activities with highest ratings for summer trainings and consultations from TOAs or BAs.

ESECP offered more training to parents and caregivers relative to comparison schools. Average survey ratings from educators in ESECP schools agreed suggested stronger agreement that training was offered to parents and caregivers than those in comparison schools. Interview and focus group respondents noted that many ESE educators were providing the level of communication with parents as expected within ESECP. Parents reported having meetings about their child’s IEP up to three times a year, with

some reporting that they had just one meeting per year. Parent training and communication was a key component of the intervention and the study schools met the threshold for this intervention.

Collaborative support among district ESECP staff; collaboration between school and district ESECP staff; high-quality materials; and the ability of the program to meet the needs of students regardless of their level of function or skill deficit facilitated successful ESECP implementation. Interview and focus group respondents reported being pleased with the quality of the ESECP programming. Several mentioned that they appreciated that programming was evidence-based and offered a structured curriculum for developmental students. Many respondents shared that in most developmental classrooms (in non-ESECP schools) there was a lack of guidelines or supports, and many educators looked for their own materials to use with their students. Additionally, respondents said that students receiving ESE services in non-ESECP schools engaged in Tier 3 programming for academic intervention, but that it was more generalized and did not focus on the individual needs of students. Respondents felt that the training and support provided by ESECP helped everyone involved with the project, from district-staff to ESE educators, work together to identify implementation issues, review data to support students' skill development, and support classroom implementation.

Project leaders made substantial progress toward disseminating information about the ESECP. Project leaders communicated with several other Florida districts interested in implementing the ESECP, providing information about key components of the project. ESECP staff presented at local, statewide, and national meetings, including an SCPS School Board meeting, Florida Association for Behavior Analysis conference, EIR Project Director's Meeting, and the American Educational Research Association annual meeting.

FINDINGS: FIDELITY AND DOSAGE

Educators reported challenges implementing ESECP with fidelity. Respondents understood the need for fidelity and the project team and educators took multiple steps to ensure that ESECP classroom implementation proceeded as expected. However, educators reported challenges meeting expectations of ESECP while also accommodating student needs. Educators also reported challenges maintaining the pace of lessons due to factors outside their control, including testing or other school-level disruptions, student behaviors causing disruptions, lack of understanding of the unit and/or lesson, and student transitions among lesson groups. Some educators expressed the desire to have more autonomy over their classrooms, suggesting that they knew best what worked for their students.

ESE educators reported that educator and administrator buy-in contributed to implementation of ESECP activities with fidelity. Without strong buy-in from school administrators and ESE educators, respondents said it was much more difficult to ensure that the program was implemented with fidelity. Administrator and educator buy-in led to creating and following a master schedule, general education teacher awareness of how time was used, better attendance at trainings, and stronger collaboration with coaching staff.

ESECP students did not receive the expected number of lessons, but neither their lesson progress nor their attendance was related to outcomes. Direct instruction groups were held 49% to 59% of the scheduled time, and students were in groups that were 32 to 54 lessons behind schedule, on average.

Site review scores suggested that ESECP implementation improved over time. Classrooms improved between the first and second semester (Cohort 1 improved from 58% to 64%, Cohort 2 improved from 54% to 64%, and Cohort 3 improved from 70% to 78% across academic and developmental classrooms, on average). In addition, the academic classrooms improved implementation across cohorts even in the first semester, from 61% in Cohort 1 to 77% in Cohort 3. Cohort 2 developmental classrooms experienced the largest change from the first semester (31%) to second semester (71%).

FINDINGS: IMPACT AND PERCEIVED IMPACTS

No significant differences in mathematics or reading achievement were found between students in ESECP schools and their peers in comparison schools. No significant effects on reading or mathematics overall scores after one year of the intervention were found. Examination of the interactions between treatment and student characteristics that were included in final analytic models for each subject area also revealed no significant effects. There were also no significant differences between students in ESECP and their peers in comparison schools two or three years after their first year of exposure.

Students in the developmental domain in ESECP schools made slightly more gains on listening comprehension scores compared gains for students in comparison schools, based on descriptive analyses. All other point differences on PPVT-5 and WJ-IV tests and subtests were within five points, suggesting students in the Developmental Domain experienced similar outcomes to those in the comparison condition.

Interview and focus group respondents reported that the ESECP helped to close gaps between students receiving ESE services and their peers, contributed to student skill development in self-contained classrooms, and increased student inclusion with their peers in general education classrooms. On surveys, educators agreed or strongly agreed, on average, that ESECP improved student language development, student social outcomes, behavior outcomes, academic engagement, academic achievement, parent engagement in student learning, and parent satisfaction.

Respondents reported that the ESECP facilitated better relationships between ESE educators and students. Reasons given for improved relationships included individualization of instruction and educators better understanding student strengths and areas for growth. Respondents reported that ESE educators built relationships and rapport with students at the beginning of instruction to gain buy-in which resulted in students wanting to be in school and engaged in their learning. Use of student data to guide instruction was reported as contributing to better educator understanding of student capabilities and needs and provision of needed supports.

Almost all respondents mentioned that the ESECP had a positive impact on students' social and life skills. Respondents shared that students improved their ability to communicate and express requests and that they developed skills that led to their participation in less restrictive environments. Respondents also reported that students saw the gains they were making and became more engaged with the curriculum and in the classroom, which led to increased interactions with their peers. Some parents shared that their children were less shy, made friends, and participated in activities with other children. A few parents of children with behavioral issues shared that their children become more respectful to their educators, followed instructions better, and decreased the frequency and intensity of their behavioral issues.

Educators shared that the ESECP had a beneficial impact on student behavior in the classroom.

Respondents reported that classrooms ran smoothly due to the ESECP structure and that educators and students knew what they were doing and what they were going to do next. Educators mentioned that they were accountable for how they engaged with students at various points in time during the lesson and throughout the day. Students were familiar with the schedule and benefitted from the consistency and routine, which included regular feedback, praise, and positive reinforcement—and those elements helped to minimize behavioral issues.

On average, 90 to 95% of educators in ESECP schools reported they were likely to continue teaching in the profession, in their current school, and in special education, compared to 80% of educators in comparison schools. Of the ESE educators assigned to ESECP schools, 74% to 85% remained in the same school from one year to the next. Over three-quarters of educators held the same job across years and a similar pattern was found with those who held the same job in the same school.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. **Refine key components.** Given that administrator buy-in was a challenge and that educators had a difficult time implementing ESECP on a sufficient number of days and with the expected amount of lesson progress, consider refining the essential components of ESECP to ensure that the requirements for stakeholders are manageable. Alternately, consider options for staged roll-out to improve uptake of ESECP key components.
2. **Continue to offer high-quality training to TOAs, BAs, administrators, and ESE educators.** Encourage participation in the trainings, and consider revisions to training activities. For example, respondents suggested:
 - Offering a mid-year training to further assist those who were struggling or did not participate in the intensive training, to come back together and discuss any issues that arose, to delve deeper into understanding the curriculum and implementation process;
 - Offering a second tier of training for those who had a grasp of the curriculum and implementation;
 - Consider an additional day of training to go in depth on topic areas of data collection and tracking, classroom management and behavior, and conducting check outs and mastery testing; and
 - Allowing participants to use their computers in the trainings so they could take notes along with the PowerPoint since it was a lot of material for them to take in, and so they had something to share with other educators at their schools once positions were filled.
3. **Consider ways to strengthen administrator buy-in.** ESE instructors, administrators, and staff all agreed that administrator buy-in was central to the success of project implementation. Ways to foster increased administrator buy-in might include identifying a support team for the administrator, engaging administrators in regular communication, and including administrators in classroom walkthroughs prior to implementation. ESECP may be most successful in schools that have buy-in from administrators prior to implementing, so using buy-in as a criterion for implementation may also foster implementation success. Other suggested ways to improve buy-in included: requiring administrators and ESE educators to observe programming before implementation at their school, informing administrators about the content of coaching activities each week, and sharing information about how ESECP is aligned to and supports

general education standards with the school as a whole.

4. **Consider ways to allow ESE educators more flexibility to meet students needs while staying on track with lesson progress.** In an effort to address fidelity and dosage, some respondents suggested that they would appreciate if educators had more flexibility with program implementation expectations so that they could better meet the needs of the students, including having the ability to test and move students forward in their learning. This flexibility could include, for example, building in time in the pacing of the curriculum for routine school activities (drills, testing, field trips, absences of students and educators) and providing a progression plan so that educators have a better understanding of the process and how units and groups should progress.
5. **Document bright spots and successes.** Although they may not meet rigorous research standards, highlighting examples of student successes in the Developmental and Academic domains may contribute to administrator, ESE educator, and parent buy-in to a project such as ESECP.
6. **Share the ESECP implementation manual with other districts interested in using this model.** This implementation manual can include a description of the project, necessary conditions for the project to succeed, key research findings, and lessons learned from project implementation in SCPS. Identify the key audiences for this manual and consider sharing it through listservs and social media avenues that may reach these audiences.

APPENDIX A. OUTCOME MEASURES MEMO UPDATE
SEMINOLE COUNTY PUBLIC SCHOOLS
EXCEPTIONAL STUDENT EDUCATION CURRICULUM PROJECT
2/8/2022

RMC Research Corporation (RMC) is conducting the evaluation of the Seminole County Public Schools (SCPS) Exceptional Student Education Curriculum Project (ESECP). The evaluation included a pilot year during 2020/21, during which sample data was collected for the originally identified confirmatory outcome measure, the Woodcock-Johnson IV Oral Language, Broad Reading, and Broad Math subtests (WJ-IV). As part of their review of pilot year activities and data, RMC and SCPS explored the option of using the iReady assessment, which is already administered by SCPS, as a confirmatory outcome measure for students in the Academic domain, rather than the WJ-IV. **As of February 2022, the team has decided to replace the WJ-IV with the iReady as the confirmatory outcome measure.** By making this change, the team expects to have a larger sample size while measuring similar constructs. Use of iReady also maintains independence of the evaluation because the iReady is administered widely by SCPS as part of standard educational practice. The rationale for this decision is as follows:

The original design included an expected matched sample ranging from n=307 to n=316 (See the Year 1 report, Appendix C). Due to challenges obtaining parent consent and student assent, quarantine issues due to COVID-19, and challenges obtaining WJ-IV assessments for students who were newly enrolled, the resulting sample included n=161 students who took the baseline WJ-IV assessment in spring 2021, for a response rate of just over 50%. The project team also had to convert the expected first cohort (2020/21) into a pilot cohort due to COVID-19. As such, there is concern about sample loss and power implications. Power analyses suggest that, if all sample size expectations were met, the minimum detectable effect size would be 0.24.¹ By using the iReady, the project team can expect a sample size close to that which was originally planned.

SCPS administers the diagnostic iReady assessment to all students during fall, winter, and spring annually. It costs \$12 per student and is a computerized assessment, allowing for efficient administration. The WJ-IV and iReady are highly correlated across overall measures and scale scores (see correlation tables below), suggesting they measure related constructs and that this assessment substitution for confirmatory analyses among students in the Academic condition would be sufficient

¹ **Power Analysis.** We expected the primary analytic sample for confirmatory impact analyses to include approximately 2,293 ESE students in Grades K-5 (half of whom are ESECP intervention students), with an average of 88 students per school in 24 schools (11 intervention schools, and 12 schools that were a comparison school; a school may be counted as a comparison school more than once). Students will not be included in multiple cohorts; once they are included as a match, they will remain a single unit. This approach minimizes contamination bias but maximizes the sample size to have sufficient power to detect a medium effect size. Power analysis conducted using Optimal Design (Raudenbush et al., 2011), accounting for 10% attrition (and with the following parameters: 79 students per school in the intervention or comparison condition, $\alpha = .05$, $R^2 = .79$, ICC = .13¹, power = .80), suggests that the proposed design yields a minimum detectable effect size of 0.24 for one-year impact analyses and three cohorts of students from 2021/22 through 2023/24.¹

EXHIBIT A1. CORRELATIONS BETWEEN WOODCOCK JOHNSON AND IREADY SCORES FOR READING

Correlations

		ORLANG_SS 389 Oral Language Standard Score 2035 3	ORLBRD_SS 399 Broad Oral Language Standard Score 2086 3	ORLEXP_SS 409 Oral Expression Standard Score 2137 3	LSTCMP_SS 419 Listening Comprehensi on Standard Score 2188 3	PICVOC_SS 489 Picture Vocabulary Standard Score 2545 3	ORLCMP_SS 499 Oral Comprehensi on Standard Score 2596 3	SENREP_SS 529 Sentence Repetition Standard Score 2749 3	PSGCMP_SS 859 Passage Comprehensi on Standard Score 4432 3	SNRDFL_SS 909 Sentence Reading Fluency Standard Score 4687 3	UNDDIR_SS 539 Understandin g Directions Standard Score 2800 3	READNG_SS 609 Reading Standard Score 3157 3	RDGBRD_SS 619 Broad Reading Standard Score 3208 3
D1Read_SS D1 Read Overall Scale Score	Pearson Correlation	.188 [*]	.133	.383 ^{**}	.193 [*]	.271 ^{**}	.206 [*]	.395 ^{**}	.197 [*]	.500 ^{**}	.272 ^{**}	.358 ^{**}	.410 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.033	.136	.000	.030	.001	.020	.000	.025	.000	.002	.000	.000
	N	129	127	133	126	135	128	134	130	129	131	129	126
D1Read_PhonA_SS Reading D1 Phonological Awareness Scale Score	Pearson Correlation	.220	.160	.472 ^{**}	.258	.436 ^{**}	.262	.473 ^{**}	.118	.204	.069	.309	.300
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.235	.390	.007	.169	.013	.162	.006	.541	.306	.711	.103	.128
	N	31	31	31	30	32	30	32	29	27	31	29	27
D1ReadPhonics_SS Reading D1 Phonics Scale Score	Pearson Correlation	-.078	-.141	.187	-.157	.121	-.129	.231 [*]	.092	.359 ^{**}	-.105	.228 [*]	.280 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.454	.180	.066	.138	.229	.217	.021	.373	.000	.307	.027	.007
	N	94	92	98	91	100	93	99	95	94	96	94	91
D1ReadHFW_SS Reading D1 High Frequency Words Sca le Score	Pearson Correlation	.097	.113	.314 [*]	.161	.310 [*]	.092	.273 [*]	.054	.333 [*]	.071	.179	.241
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.505	.444	.023	.279	.023	.532	.048	.710	.019	.622	.220	.107
	N	49	48	52	47	54	48	53	50	49	51	49	46
D1ReadVocab_SS Reading D1 Vocabulary Scale Score	Pearson Correlation	.190 [*]	.132	.357 ^{**}	.187 [*]	.275 ^{**}	.205 [*]	.365 ^{**}	.138	.451 ^{**}	.287 ^{**}	.289 ^{**}	.336 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.031	.139	.000	.036	.001	.020	.000	.118	.000	.001	.001	.000
	N	129	127	133	126	135	128	134	130	129	131	129	126
D1ReadCompLit_SS Reading D1 Reading Comprehension Literature Scale Score	Pearson Correlation	.223 [*]	.190 [*]	.423 ^{**}	.237 ^{**}	.294 ^{**}	.228 ^{**}	.441 ^{**}	.197 [*]	.476 ^{**}	.332 ^{**}	.350 ^{**}	.393 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.011	.033	.000	.008	.001	.009	.000	.025	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	129	127	133	126	135	128	134	130	129	131	129	126
D1ReadCompLit_SS Reading D1 Reading Comprehension Informational Text Scale Sc ore	Pearson Correlation	.215 [*]	.155	.375 ^{**}	.220 [*]	.244 ^{**}	.250 ^{**}	.391 ^{**}	.174 [*]	.461 ^{**}	.296 ^{**}	.310 ^{**}	.368 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.014	.082	.000	.014	.004	.004	.000	.048	.000	.001	.000	.000
	N	129	127	133	126	135	128	134	130	129	131	129	126

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

EXHIBIT A2. CORRELATIONS BETWEEN WOODCOCK JOHNSON AND IREADY SCORES FOR MATHEMATICS

Correlations

		MATH_SS 679 Mathematics Standard Score 3514 3	MATHBR_SS 689 Broad Mathematics Standard Score 3565 3	MTHCAL_SS 699 Math Calculation Skills Standard Score 3616 3	LWIDNT_SS 829 Letter – Word Identification Standard Score 4279 3	APPROB_SS 839 Applied Problems Standard Score 4330 3	CALC_SS 869 Calculation Standard Score 4483 3	MTHFLU_SS 919 Math Facts Fluency Standard Score 4738 3
D1Math_SS D1 Math Overall Scale Score	Pearson Correlation	.479	.494	.457	.241	.454	.405	.475
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.006	.000	.000	.000
	N	129	129	129	129	128	129	130
D1Math_NumOP_SS Math D1 Numbers and Operations Scale Score	Pearson Correlation	.442	.468	.455	.207	.404	.409	.470
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.018	.000	.000	.000
	N	129	129	129	129	128	129	130
D1Math_AlgThk_SS Math D1 Algebraic Thinking Scale Score	Pearson Correlation	.423	.452	.426	.205	.394	.358	.466
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.020	.000	.000	.000
	N	129	129	129	129	128	129	130
D1Math_Meas_SS Math D1 Measurement and Data Scale Score	Pearson Correlation	.496	.502	.450	.263	.486	.403	.466
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.003	.000	.000	.000
	N	129	129	129	129	128	129	130
D1Math_Geo_SS Math D1 Geometry Scale Score	Pearson Correlation	.474	.461	.395	.264	.463	.363	.399
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.002	.000	.000	.000
	N	129	129	129	129	128	129	130

APPENDIX B. SCPS ESECP FIDELITY MATRIX

EXHIBIT B1. FIDELITY MATRIX

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
Key Component 1: ESECP Teachers on Assignment (TOA) Training & Coaching										
1a. Prior Experience with Direct Instruction	TOAs have at least 1 year of direct instruction teaching experience prior to hiring or project participation.	TOA	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	0 = Less than 1 year of direct instruction teaching experience prior to project participation. 1= At least 1 year of direct instruction teaching experience prior to project participation.	1		<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of TOAs have a score of 1 1 = 100% of TOAs have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	All TOAs assigned to ESECP schools/All Year 1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
1b. DI Trainer Institute	TOAs have attended a 5-day training institute on the topic of delivery and design of educator training. Occurs prior to delivering a training.	TOA	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (did not provide training) 0 = Did not attend the 5-day training or attended less than 3 days prior to providing training to others 1 = Attended at least 3 days but less than 5 days of the 5-day training	1		<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of TOAs have a score of 1 1 = 100% of TOAs have a score of 1 or not applicable Adequate implementation = 1	All TOAs assigned to ESECP schools/All Year 1 ESECP schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
					prior to providing training to others 2 = Attended full 5-day training prior to providing training to others					
1c. Coaching Academies Y1	TOAs attend two 2-day Coaching Academies prior to coaching in a classroom.	TOA	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (did not provide coaching or not in their first year) 0 = No attendance at either coaching academy or provided coaching prior to attending either coaching academy. 1 = Attendance at 1 day of coaching prior to providing coaching. 2 = Attendance at 2 days of the coaching academy prior to coaching, or 4 days of coaching academies during first school year with 2 days prior to coaching 3 = Attendance at 4 or more days of coaching	2		District: 0 = Less than 100% of TOAs have a score of 2 1 = 100% of TOAs have a score of 2 or not applicable Adequate implementation = 1	All TOAs in assigned to ESECP schools/All Year 1 ESECP schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
					academies prior to coaching					
1d. Pre-Coaching Site Visits	TOAs complete observations in implementing schools prior to independent coaching.	TOA	Coaching logs	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (did not provide coaching) 0 = No observations prior to coaching 1 = 1 or 2 observations prior to coaching 2 = At least 3 observations prior to coaching	1		District: 0 = Less than 100% of TOAs have a score of 1 1 = 100% of TOAs have a score of 1 or not applicable Adequate implementation = 1	All TOAs assigned to ESECP schools/All Year 1 ESECP schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
1e. Partner Check-ins	Weekly data tracking with SCPS is completed by/with TOAs for each curriculum project school (Academic).	TOA (measured at the school level)	Problem Solving Summary Sheet	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.			<u>School:</u> 0 = 8 or fewer weeks of PSSs 1 = 9-17 weeks of PSSs 2 = 18-27 weeks of PSSs 3 = At least 28 weeks PSSs Adequate implementation = 2	<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of ESECP schools have a score of 2 for academic classrooms 1 = 100% of ESECP schools have a score of 2 for academic classrooms Adequate implementation = 1	All Year 1 ESECP schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
1f. Sharing of PSS results	Weekly data tracking with SCPS is shared with administrators	TOA (measured at school level)	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.			<u>School:</u> -9 = Not applicable (0 PSSs were generated) 0 = 0-33% of generated PSSs were shared	<u>District:</u> 0 = less than 100% of schools have a score of 2 1 = 100% of schools have a score of 2 or not applicable	All Year 1 ESECP schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
							1 = 34-67% of generated PSSs were shared 2 = 68% or more of PSSs were shared Adequate implementation = 2	Adequate implementation = 1		
1g. Coaching (ESE teachers)	TOAs engage in weekly coaching in the presence of students and groups with each academic/behavior ESE teacher and paraeducator they support.	TOA	Coaching logs	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of completion of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (did not provide coaching to ESE teachers) 0 = Less than 75% of ESE educators have at least 19 logs 1 = Between 75 and 99% of ESE educators have at least 19 logs 2 = All ESE educators have between 19 and 27 logs 3 = All ESE educators have at least 28 logs	2		<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of TOAs have a score of at least 2 1 = 100% of TOAs have a score of 2 or not applicable Adequate implementation = 1	All TOAs assigned to ESECP schools/All Year 1 ESECP schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
1h. Coaching (Paraeducators)	TOAs engage in monthly coaching in the presence of students and groups with each academic/behavior	TOA	Coaching logs	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of	-9 = Not applicable (did not provide coaching to paraeducators)	2		<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of TOAs have a score of at least 2	All TOAs assigned to ESECP schools/All Year 1	Year 1 of school implementation

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
	paraeducator they support.			completion of the school year.	0 = Less than 75% of ESE paraeducators have at least 5 logs 1 = Between 75 and 99% of ESE paraeducators have at least 5 logs 2 = All ESE paraeducators have between 6 and 9 logs 3 = All ESE paraeducators have at least 10 logs			1 = 100% of TOAs have a score of 2 or not applicable Adequate implementation = 1	ESECP schools	C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
1i. Site Review Training	TOAs participate in site review training and achieve an inter-observer agreement (IOA) of 85% prior to conducting independent site reviews.	TOA	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable. Did not conduct independent site reviews in Y1 ESECP schools. 0 = TOAs did not attend training prior to conducting independent site reviews. 1 = TOA attended training prior to conducting independent site reviews and prior	2		<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of TOAs have a score of 2 1 = 100% of TOAs have a score of 2 or not applicable Adequate implementation = 1	All TOAs assigned to ESECP schools / All Year 1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
					to achieving an IOA of 85%. 2 = TOA attended training and achieved an IOA of 85% prior to conducting an independent site review.					
1j. Site Review Conducted	Fall and spring site reviews were conducted for all eligible academic/behavior sites at the time of site reviews.	Site (classroom or educator). TOAs conduct these reviews and this is measured at the school level.	Site Review Form	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.			<u>School:</u> 0 = Less than 90% of Site Reviews with eligible sites 1 = 90% of Site Reviews with 100% of eligible sites Adequate implementation = 1	<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of schools have a score of 1 1 = 100% of schools have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	All TOAs assigned to ESECP schools and the sites to which they are assigned /All Year 1 ESECP schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
All Indicators					0-15	TOAs meet fidelity if they meet the threshold on all applicable indicators	<u>Schools:</u> 0-6 Adequate implementation = 6	<u>District:</u> 1-10 Adequate implementation = 10	District	Year 1 of school curriculum project implementation of C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
Key Component 2: ESECP Behavior Analyst (BA Training & Coaching)										
2a. Prior experience/training in verbal behavior assessment and programming	BAs have at least one year of experience in verbal behavior assessment and programming	BA	Project records		0 = Less than one year of experience in verbal behavior assessment and programming 1 = at least one year of experience in verbal behavior assessment and programming	1		<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of BAs have a score of 1 1 = 100% of BAs have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	All BAs assigned to ESECP schools/All Year 1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
2b. BA Coaches training	BAs complete 3 days of basic and advanced skills training prior to providing coaching.	BA	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (did not provide coaching) 0 = Did not complete any training prior to providing coaching. 1 = Full attendance (3 days) at basic skills training prior to providing coaching. 2 = Full attendance (3 days) at basic skills training and either early or advanced learner training prior to providing coaching.	1 for Y1 BAs 2 for Y2-Y3 BAs		<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of BAs meet adequate threshold 1 = 100% of BAs meet adequate threshold or not applicable Adequate implementation = 1	All BAs assigned to ESECP schools/All Year 1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
					3 = Full attendance (3 days) at basic skills training and both the early or advanced learner training prior to providing coaching.					
2c. BA Basic Skills Training	BAs attend the basic skills training prior to delivery of training	BA	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (did not provide training on basic skills) 0 = Did not attend prior to providing training 1= Attended prior to providing training	1		<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of BAs have a score of 1 1 = 100% of BAs have a score of 1 or not applicable Adequate implementation = 1	All BAs assigned to ESECP schools/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
2d. BA Training	BAs attend all trainings prior to providing training on those skills.	BA	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (did not provide training or was a Y1 BA) 0 = Did not attend prior to providing training 1 = BAs have completed trainings on at least 67% and less than 100% of	1 This is only a requirement for year 2 and year 3 BAs, but may be noted if completed earlier.		<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of Y2 or Y3 BAs have a score of 1 1 = 100% of Y2 or Y3 BAs have a score of 1 or not applicable Adequate implementation = 1	All BAs assigned to ESECP schools/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
					trainings they provide 2 = BAs have completed training on 100% of the trainings they provide.					
2e. Pre-Coaching Site Visits	BAs complete observations implementing schools prior to coaching.	BA	Coaching logs	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (did not provide coaching) 0 = No observations prior to coaching 1 = 1 or 2 observations prior to coaching 2 = At least 3 observations prior to coaching	1		<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of BAs have a score of 1 1 = 100% of BAs have a score of 1 or not applicable Adequate implementation = 1	All BAs assigned to ESECP schools/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
2f. Partner check-ins	Monthly data analysis meetings.	BA (measured at the school level)	Problem Solving Summary Sheet	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.			<u>School:</u> 0 = No PSSs 1 = Between 3 and 5 months of PSSs 2 = 6 or 7 months of PSSs 3 = At least 8 months of PSSs	<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of ESECP schools have a score of 2 for developmental classrooms 1 = 100% of BAs have a score of 2 for developmental classrooms	All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
							Adequate implementation = 2	Adequate implementation = 1		
2g. Coaching (ESE Teachers)	BAs engage in weekly coaching in the presence of students and groups with each developmental/medical ESE teacher they support.	BA	Coaching logs	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of completion of each semester.	-9 = Not applicable (did not provide coaching to ESE teachers) 0 = Less than 18 logs (or 50%) for 100% of ESE teachers 1 = At least 18 logs (or 50%) for at least 75% of ESE teachers 2 = Between 19 and 27 logs for 100% of ESE teachers 3 = At least 28 logs for 100% of ESE teachers	2		<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of BAs have a score of 2 1 = 100% of BAs have a score of 2 or not applicable Adequate implementation = 1	All BAs assigned to ESECP schools/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
2h. Coaching (Paraeducators)	BAs engage in monthly coaching in the presence of students and groups with each academic/behavior paraeducator they support.	BA	Coaching logs	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of completion of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (did not provide coaching to paraeducators) 0 = Less than 5 logs (or 50%) for 100% of ESE paraeducators 1 = At least 5 logs (or 50%) for at	2		<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of BAs have a score of 2 1 = 100% of BAs have a score of 2 or not applicable Adequate implementation = 1	All BAs assigned to ESECP schools/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
					least 75% of ESE paraeducators 2 = At least 10 logs for 100% of ESE paraeducators					
2i. Site Review Training	BAs participate in site review training and achieve an inter-observer agreement (IOA) of 85% prior to conducting independent site reviews.	BA		Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (did not conduct independent site reviews) 0 = BAs did not attend training prior to conducting independent site reviews. 1 = BA attended training prior to conducting independent site reviews and prior to achieving an IOA of 85%. 2 = BA attended training and achieved an IOA of 85% prior to conducting an independent site review.	2		<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of BAs have a score of 2 1 = 100% of BAs have a score of 2 or not applicable Adequate implementation = 1	All BAs assigned to ESECP schools/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
2j. Site Review Conducted	Fall and spring site reviews were conducted for all eligible developmental sites	Site (classroom or educator). BAs conduct	Site Review Form	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1			<u>School:</u> 0 = < 90% of Site Reviews with eligible sites	<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of schools have a score of 1	All sites/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
	at the time of site reviews.	these reviews and this is measured at the school level.		month of the end of the school year.			1 = 90% of Site Reviews with 100% of eligible sites Adequate implementation = 1	1 = 100% of schools have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1		C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
All indicators					0-16	BAs meet fidelity if they meet the threshold on all applicable indicators	<u>School:</u> 0-4 Adequate implementation = 3	<u>District:</u> 0-10 Adequate implementation = 10	All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
Key Component 3: Administer Training & Engagement										
3a. Pre-implementation meeting	Administrators attend a pre-implementation meeting prior to project implementation or within 9 weeks of hiring/reassignment into an ESECP school for the first time (principals, assistant principals, and instructional leaders should be included at the beginning of the year; principals should be included at any time point	School Administrators (principals, assistant principals, and instructional leaders).	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (not relevant to attend, or individual was an assistant principal or instructional leader who was not in place at the beginning of the year or a school administration manager) 0 = Did not attend 1 = Attended	1	<u>School:</u> 0 = The principal did not have a score of 1 1 = Only the principal had a score of 1 2 = The principal and at least one assistant principal have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 2	<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of schools have a score of 2 1 = 100% of the schools have a score of 2 Adequate implementation = 1	Instructional Leadership Team/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
	that a change is made).									
3b. Collaborative agreement	Administrator signs collaborative agreement prior to project implementation (principals, assistant principals should be included) or within 9 weeks or hiring/reassignment.	School Administrators (principals, assistant principals, and instructional leaders).	Project records of signed collaborative agreement.	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (a school administration manager or not relevant to sign) 0 = No signed agreement at the beginning of the school year or within 9 weeks of hiring/reassignment 1 = Signed agreement at the beginning of the school year or within 9 weeks of hiring/reassignment	1	<u>School:</u> 0 = The principal did not have a score of 1 1 = Only the principal had a score of 1 2 = The principal and at least one assistant principal have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of schools have a score of 2 1 = 100% of the schools have a score of 2 Adequate implementation = 1	Instructional Leadership Team/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
3c. Administrative or institute	Instructional leadership team members attend a 1-day training to ensure that participants can support the implementation of DI successfully (principals, assistant principals, instructional coach, and school	Instructional leadership team (principals, assistant principals, instructional leaders, school administration manager).	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (not relevant to attend) 0 = did not attend 1 = attended	1	<u>School:</u> 0 = No relevant instructional leadership team member attended 1 = One relevant member of the instructional leadership attended 2 = More than one relevant	<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of schools have a score of 2 1 = 100% of schools have a score of 2	Instructional Leadership Team/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
	administration manager).						member of the instructional leadership team attended. Must include at least the principal or assistant principal Adequate implementation = 2			
3d. Classroom Walk-throughs with Administrators	TOAs and/or BAs and instructional leadership team members conduct monthly classroom walkthroughs in ESECP classrooms	School	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.			<u>School:</u> 0 = Walkthroughs were conducted in 2 or fewer months or did not include at least one member of the instructional leadership team and a TOA or BA 1 = Walkthroughs were conducted with at least one member of the instructional leadership team and a TOA and/or BA in 3 to 5 months 2 = Walkthroughs	<u>District:</u> 0 = less than 100% of schools have a score of 1 or higher 1 = 100% of schools have a score of 1 or higher Adequate implementation = 1	All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
							were conducted with at least one member of the instructional leadership team and a TOA and/or BA in 6 to 10 months Adequate implementation = 1			
3e. Attendance at mid-year PSS meeting	Instructional leadership team members attend the mid-year PSS meeting.	Instructional Leadership Team (measured at the school level).	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (not relevant to attend or not hired at time of meeting) 0 = did not attend 1 = attended	1	<u>School:</u> 0 = No members of the instructional leadership team attend the mid-year PSS meeting 1 = At least one member of the instructional leadership team attends the mid-year PSS meeting Adequate implementation = 1	<u>District:</u> 0 = less than 80% of schools have a score of 1 1 = At least 80% of schools have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	Instructional Leadership Team/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
3f. Attendance at progressive action meetings when requested	Instructional leadership team members attend progressive action meetings when requested.	Instructional Leadership Team (measured at the school level).	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.			<u>School:</u> 0 = Members of the instructional leadership team attend less than 80% progressive action meetings when requested	<u>District:</u> 0 = less than 80% of schools have a score of 1 1 = At least 80% of schools have a score of 1	Instructional Leadership Team/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
							1 = At least one member of the instructional leadership team attends at least 80% of progressive action meetings when requested or all had a score of not applicable Adequate implementation = 1	Adequate implementation = 1		
All indicators					0-5	5	School: 0-10 Adequate implementation = 8	District: 0-6 Adequate implementation = 6	All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
Key Component 4: ESE Instructor Training										
4a. Pre-implementation meeting (instructors)	ESE instructors (educators, paraeducators, and SLPs) in their positions before the makeup meeting attend a pre-implementation meeting or a makeup meeting in the fall.	ESE instructors (educators, paraeducators, SLPs, and other staff who provide direct instruction).	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (not in their position prior to a pre-implementation or make up meeting, or not relevant for them to attend) 0 = Did not attend 1 = Attended	1	School: 0 = Less than 80% of appropriate ESE instructors at the time of the meeting have a score of 1 1 = 80% or more of appropriate ESE instructors have a score of 1	District: 0 = Less than 100% of schools have a score of 1 1 = 100% of schools have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	All ESE instructors /All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
							Adequate implementation = 1			
4b. School Visits (instructors)	Prior to implementation ESE educators and SLPs visit a school implementing the curriculum project before the end of the first 9 weeks of the school year.	ESE instructors (educators, paraeducators, SLPs, and other staff who provide direct instruction).	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (not a relevant ESE educator or SLP or not in that position before the end of the first 9 weeks of the school year) 0 = Did not attend before the end of the first 9 weeks of the school year. 1 = Attended before the end of the first 9 weeks of the school year.	1	School: 0 = Less than 100% of appropriate ESE educators have a score of 1 1 = 100% of appropriate ESE instructors have a score of 1 and less than 100% of SLPs have a score of 1. 2 = 100% of appropriate ESE instructors AND SLPs have a score of 1. Adequate implementation = 1	<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of schools have a score of 1 1 = 100% of schools have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	All ESE educators/ All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
4c. Pre-service training for academic instructors	ESE instructors who provide direct instruction to academic students attend the 5-day training prior to the school year OR 2-days of backup training within the first month of	ESE instructors (educators, paraeducators, SLPs, and other staff who provide direct instruction) who provide	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (did not provide direct instruction to academic students) 0 = Completed less than 2 days of training or backup training within the first month of	1	School: 0 = Less than 80% of appropriate ESE instructors have a score of at least 1 1 = at least 80% of appropriate ESE instructors have a score of 1	<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of schools have a score of 1 1 = 100% of schools have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	All ESE educators/ All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
	school/first month of hire.	instruction to academic students the majority of the school day.			school/first month of hire OR completed training outside of the specified time frame. 1 = Attended backup training AND/OR at least 2 days of pre-service training within the first month of school/first month of hire 2 = Attended all 5 days of pre-service training prior to the start of the school year		2 = 100% of appropriate ESE instructors have a score of 1. Adequate implementation = 1			
4d. Preservice training for developmental instructors	Developmental instructors complete 3 days of basic skills training prior to the start of the school year OR 2-days of backup training within the first month of school/first month of hire.	ESE instructors (educators, paraeducators, SLPs, and other staff providing training within the first month of school/first month of hire) who provide instructional to	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (not a developmental instructor) 0 = Completed less than 2 days of basic skills training or backup training completed within the first month of school/first month of hire OR completed training outside of	1	<u>School:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of developmental instructors have a score of 1 1 = 100% of Developmental instructors have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of schools have a score of 1 1 = 100% of schools have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	All ESE educators/ All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school Implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
		developmental students the majority of the school day.			the specified time frame. 1 = Attends backup training AND/OR at least 2 days of pre-service training within the first month of school/first month of hire 2 = Full attendance (3 days) at basic skills training prior to the start of the school year					
4e. Ongoing training	ESE instructors engage in monthly practice of specific curriculum skills with a coach (e.g., practice giving mastery test) outside of the classroom.	ESE instructors (educators, paraeducators, SLPs, and other staff providing who provide direct instruction).	Training logs with practice indicated	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of completion of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable 0 = No logs with practice indicated 1 = At least 3 months of logs with practice indicated 2 = 4 to 7 months of logs with practice indicated 3 = At least 8 months of logs with practice indicated	2	<u>School:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of appropriate ESE instructors have a score of 2 1 = 100% of appropriate ESE instructors have a score of 2 Adequate implementation = 1	<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of schools have a score of 1 1 = 100% of schools have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	All ESE educators/ All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
4f. Collaborative	ESE instructors attend a meeting reviewing the	ESE instructors (educators,	Project records of signed	Program leader delivers documents to	-9 = Not applicable (not relevant to sign	1	<u>School:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of	<u>District:</u>	All ESE educators/ All Y1	Year 1 of school

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
e agreement	components of the collaborative agreement within the first semester of implementation.	paraeducators, SLPs, and other staff providing who provide direct instruction).	collaborative agreement.	evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	the collaborative agreement, or not in position within first semester of implementation) 0 = No signed agreement 1 = Signed agreement		appropriate ESE instructors have a score of 1 1 = 100% of appropriate ESE instructors have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	0 = Less than 100% of schools have a score of 1 1 = 100% of schools have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	ESECP Schools	implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
All indicators					0-10 (for those who serve both developmental and academic students, otherwise 0-9)	ESE instructors meet fidelity if they meet the threshold on all applicable indicators.	<u>School:</u> 0-8 Adequate implementation = 6	<u>District:</u> 0-6 Adequate implementation = 6	All intervention schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
Key Component 5: Parent Training & Communication										
5a. Parent training sessions	Parent training sessions are provided through the project that target relevant needs for ESECP students.	District	Session materials (agendas, PPT slides)	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of completion.				<u>District:</u> 0 = None 1 = Between 3 and 5 sessions 2 = 6 Sessions Adequate implementation = 1	All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
5b. Parent Information Night	A parent information night that provides an overview of the	District (measured at the school level)	Session materials (agenda,	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by			<u>School:</u> 0 = District did not hold parent information	<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of schools have a score of 1	All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
	Exceptional Student Education Curriculum Project with parents is held for parents at each school.		PPT Slides)	email within 1 month of completion.			night for this school prior to the first semester 1 = District held parent information night for this school held prior to the first semester Adequate implementation = 1	1 = 100% of schools have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1		C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
5c. Parent Curriculum Night	A parent curriculum night that provides an overview of the ESECP curriculum in which their child will participate is held for parents at each school.	District (measured at the school level)	Session materials (agenda, PPT Slides)	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of completion.			<u>School:</u> 0 = District did not hold parent curriculum night for this school prior to the first semester 1 = District held parent curriculum night for this school held prior to the first semester Adequate implementation = 1	<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of schools have a score of 1 1 = 100% of schools have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
All indicators							0-2 Adequate implementation = 2	0-4 Adequate implementation = 2 (with at least 1 on	All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
								the parent information night)		C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
Key Component 6: District Monitoring and Support										
6a. Mentors are assigned to new TOAs and BAs	New TOAs and BAs are assigned an experienced mentor (experienced TOA/BA or coach, project leadership, or other designee) to mentor them during their first year of implementation.	District	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.				<u>District:</u> 0 = less than 100% of new TOAs/BAs were assigned a mentor 1 = 100% of new TOAs/BAs were assigned a mentor Adequate implementation = 1	All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
6b. TOA Mentorship	TOA mentors (experienced TOA or coach, project leadership, or other designee) are scheduled to be in the classroom with first year TOAs during coaching to model, observe, and provide feedback on coaching skills.	New TOA (Mentor = responsible party)	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	-9 = Not applicable (not a Y1 TOA) 0 = less than 8 mentorship sessions were scheduled 1 = 8 or 9 mentorship sessions were scheduled 2 = At least 10 mentorship sessions were scheduled	1		<u>District:</u> 0 = less than 80% of new TOAs have a score of 1 1 = at least 80% of new TOAs have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	All TOAs/ All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
6c. BA Mentorship	BA mentors (experienced BA or coach, project leadership, or other	New BA (Mentor = responsible party)	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by	-9 = Not applicable (not a Y1 BA)	1		<u>District:</u> 0 = less than 80% of Y1 BAs have a score of 1	All BAs/ All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
	designee) are scheduled to be in the classroom with Y1 BAs during coaching to model, observe, and provide feedback on coaching skills.			email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	0 = less than 8 mentorship sessions were scheduled 1 = 8 or 9 mentorship sessions were scheduled 2 = At least 10 mentorship sessions were scheduled			1 = at least 80% of Y1 BAs have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1		C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
6d. Site Review Screening - Fall	Academic and developmental sites (classrooms/educators) screened in the fall per the site review screening guidelines to determine if site reviews should happen.	District (Project Leadership or other designee is responsible party e.g., coaches)	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.				<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 90% of sites were screened. 1 = At least 90% of sites were screened. Adequate implementation = 1	All Sites/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
6e. Site Review Screening - Spring	Percent of academic and developmental sites (classrooms/educators) screened in the spring per the site review screening guidelines to determine if site reviews should happen.	District (Project Leadership or other designee is responsible party e.g., coaches)	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.				<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 90% of sites were screened. 1 = At least 90% of sites were screened. Adequate implementation = 1	All Sites/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
6f. Site Review Scheduling - Fall	Project leadership establishes the window for completing site reviews ensuring that at least 8% of site reviews are conducted by two TOAs or BAs.	District (Project Leadership or other designee is responsible party e.g., coaches)	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.				<u>District:</u> 0 = The site review window was not established 1 = The site review window was established and less than 8% of sites were assigned to be reviewed by two raters 2 = The site review window was established and at least 8% but less than 10% of sites were assigned to be reviewed by two raters 3 = The site review window was established and at least 10% of sites were assigned to be reviewed by two raters Adequate implementation = 1	All Sites/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
6g. Site Review IOA- Fall	Project leadership verifies that IOA continues to meet acceptable thresholds.	District (Project Leadership or other designee is responsible)	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the				<u>District:</u> 0 = IOA was not evaluated, or acceptable threshold was met for less than 75% of sites	All Sites/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
		party e.g., coaches)		end of the school year.				1 = IOA was evaluated, and acceptable thresholds were met for at least 75% and less than 85% of sites 2 = IOA was evaluated and meets acceptable thresholds for at least 85% of sites Adequate implementation = 2		C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
6h. Site Review IOA-Spring	Project leadership verifies that IOA continues to meet acceptable thresholds.	District (Project Leadership or other designee is responsible party e.g., coaches)	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.				<u>District:</u> 0 = IOA was not evaluated, or acceptable threshold was met for less than 75% of sites 1 = IOA was evaluated, and acceptable thresholds were met for at least 75% and less than 85% of sites 2 = IOA was evaluated and meets acceptable thresholds for at least 85% of sites Adequate implementation = 2	All Sites/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
6i. ESE Classroom Coverage	For all unfilled ESE positions, ESE responsibilities are coordinated using the checklist that is completed with the instructional leadership team within 4 weeks.	Position	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	0 = The ESE position was not filled, and the [Name] checklist was not completed within 4 weeks 1= ESE position was filled OR the [Name] checklist was completed within 4 weeks	1	<u>School:</u> 0 = less than 100% of positions have a score of 1 1 = 100% of positions have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of schools have a score of 1 1 = 100% of schools have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	All ESE positions/ All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
6j. Teacher Support Matrix	TOAs and BAs complete the Teacher Support Matrix for each educator they support prior to the beginning of the academic year or within one month of hire.	TOA/BA	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.	0 = The Teacher Support Matrix is filled out for less than 80% of educators a TOA/BA supports 1 = The Teacher Support Matrix was filled out for at least 80% of educators a TOA/BA supports	1		<u>District:</u> 0 = less than 100% of TOAs/BAs have a score of 1 1 = 100% of TOAs/BAs have a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	All TOAs/BAs/ All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
6k. TOA/BA positions filled based on the teacher support matrix	Sufficient TOA and BA FTE time is allocated to support educator needs (when possible, based on the Teacher Support Matrix).	District	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.				<u>District:</u> -9 = Not applicable (teacher support matrix was not completed) 0 = Less than 90% of TOA/BA FTE suggested by the Teacher Support Matrix was allocated 1 = At least 90% of	All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
								TOA/BA FTE suggested by the Teacher Support Matrix was allocated Adequate implementation = 1		
6I. TOA/BA Assignments	TOAs/BAs are scheduled to support educators within a school for at least 90% of the amount of time recommended (when possible, based on the results of the Teacher Support Matrix) by the end of the first month of school.	School (Project Leadership is responsible)	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.			<u>School:</u> -9 = Not applicable (teacher support matrix was not completed) 0 = TOAs/BAs were scheduled to support educators within a school for less than 90% of the time recommended by the Teacher Support Matrix 1 = TOAs/BAs were scheduled to support educators within a school for at least 90% of the time recommended by the Teacher Support Matrix Adequate implementation = 1	<u>District:</u> 0 = Less than 100% of schools had a score of 1 1 = 100% of schools had a score of 1 Adequate implementation = 1	All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
6m. Monitor progress	Project leadership or designee attend problem solving summary (PSS) meetings with schools to monitor progress.	District (Project Leadership or other designee is responsible party e.g., coaches)	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.				<u>District:</u> 0 = Project leadership or designee attends less than 50% of PSS meetings 1 = Project leadership or designee attends at least 50% of PSS meetings Adequate implementation = 1	Project leader/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
6n. Response to problems	Project leadership or designee attends PSS meetings based on the progressive action flow chart.	District (Project Leadership or other designee is responsible party e.g., coaches)	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.				<u>District:</u> -9 = Not applicable (progressive action flowchart not completed) 0 = Project leadership or designee attends less than 90% of meetings based on the progressive action flow chart 1 = Project leadership or designee attends at least 90% of meetings based on the progressive action flow chart Adequate implementation = 1	Project leader/All Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

Indicators	Definition	Unit of implementation	Data Source(s)	Data Collection (who, when)	Score for levels of implementation at unit level (if unit is smaller than school)	Threshold for adequate implementation at unit level	Roll-up to school level if needed (score and threshold): Indicate level	Roll-up to district/program level (score and threshold for adequate implementation at sample level)	Expected sample for fidelity measure	Expected years of fidelity measurement
60. Progressive Action Monitoring	Project leadership or designee monitors that progressive action steps are followed through bi-monthly discussions.	District (Project Leadership or other designee is responsible party e.g., coaches)	Project records	Program leader delivers documents to evaluator by email within 1 month of the end of the school year.				<u>District:</u> 0 = Project leadership or designee discusses the need for progressive action steps with TOAs/BAs less than 15 times during the year 1 = Project leadership or designee discusses the need for progressive action steps with TOAs/BAs at least 15 times a year Adequate implementation = 1	Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24
All Indicators						Each unit meets adequate threshold for relevant indicators	0-2 Adequate implementation = 1	0-19 Adequate implementation = 17	Y1 ESECP Schools	Year 1 of school implementation C1 21/22; C2 22/23; C3 23/24

APPENDIX C. TECHNICAL METHODOLOGICAL DETAILS

EXHIBIT C1. EDUCATOR SURVEY SUBSCALES AND RELIABILITY

Scale	Number of Items	Sample Items	Response Categories	Internal Consistency					
				2021/22		2022/23		2023/24	
				Fall	Spring	Fall	Spring	Fall	Spring
Preparedness (Overall)	18	[I feel prepared...] to use student assessment data to make adjustments designed to improve student outcomes.	1 (Not at All Prepared) to 4 (Well Prepared)	.94	.95	.95	.97	.94	.94
Preparedness (Instruction)	10	[I feel prepared...] to identify student learning goals.	1 (Not at All Prepared) to 4 (Well Prepared)	.93	.92	.93	.96	.95	.90
Educator Practice (Overall) ^a	34	I post student schedules in the classroom.	1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree)	-	.95	-	.97	-	.95
Educator Practice (Classroom Organization) ^a	8	In my classroom, seating is appropriate for children.	1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree)	-	.92	-	.91	-	.84
Educator Practice (Planning and Training) ^a	5	I participate in regular training related to my classroom instruction.	1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree)	-	.69	-	.86	-	.84
Educator Practice (Instructional Delivery) ^a	8	I use materials and resources that promote study skills.	1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree)	-	.85	-	.91	-	.88
Educator Practice (Assessment) ^a	7	I use a variety of assessment strategies to monitor student progress.	1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree)	-	.90	-	.91	-	.89
Professional Learning (Utility) ^a	6	[The professional learning...] facilitated collaboration among peers.	1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree)	-	.87	-	.92	-	.92
Satisfaction (Overall)	16	Class sizes/caseloads	1 (Very Dissatisfied) to 4 (Very Satisfied)	.76	.89	.96	.86	.92	.93

^aEducators were only asked to respond during the spring survey administrations.

EXHIBIT C2. SURVEY RESPONDENT CHARACTERISTICS

	2021/22			2022/23			2023/24		
	ESECP (N = 7)	Comparison (N = 5)	Total (N = 12)	ESECP (N = 11)	Comparison (N = 2)	Total (N = 13)	ESECP (N = 8)	Comparison (N = 1)	Total (N = 9)
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Gender									
Male	0 (0.0)	1 (20.0)	1 (8.3)	1 (9.1)	0 (0.0)	1 (7.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Female	7 (100.0)	4 (80.0)	11 (91.7)	10 (90.9)	2 (100.0)	12 (92.3)	8 (100.0)	1 (100.0)	9 (100.0)
Race/Ethnicity									
Black or African American	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (18.2)	1 (50.0)	3 (23.1)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
White	7 (100.0)	4 (80.0)	11 (91.7)	9 (81.8)	0 (0.0)	9 (69.2)	8 (100.0)	1 (100.0)	9 (100.0)
Asian	0 (0.0)	1 (20.0)	1 (8.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Hispanic	1 (14.3)	0 (0.0)	1 (8.3)	1 (9.1)	0 (0.0)	1 (7.7)	1 (12.5)	0 (0.0)	1 (11.1)
I prefer not to answer	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (50.0)	1 (7.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Grade Level									
Kindergarten	7 (100.0)	4 (80.0)	11 (91.7)	7 (63.6)	1 (50.0)	8 (61.5)	7 (87.5)	1 (100.0)	8 (88.9)
First grade	5 (71.4)	5 (100.0)	10 (83.3)	8 (72.7)	2 (100.0)	10 (76.9)	6 (75.0)	1 (100.0)	7 (77.8)
Second grade	6 (85.7)	4 (80.0)	10 (83.3)	8 (72.7)	2 (100.0)	10 (76.9)	6 (75.0)	1 (100.0)	7 (77.8)
Third grade	5 (71.4)	5 (100.0)	10 (83.3)	8 (72.7)	2 (100.0)	10 (76.9)	6 (75.0)	1 (100.0)	7 (77.8)
Fourth grade	5 (71.4)	5 (100.0)	10 (83.3)	9 (81.8)	2 (100.0)	10 (76.9)	5 (62.5)	1 (100.0)	6 (66.7)
Fifth grade	5 (71.4)	5 (100.0)	10 (83.3)	11 (100.0)	1 (50.0)	12 (92.3)	8 (100.0)	1 (100.0)	9 (100.0)
Role									
Classroom Teacher in Self-Contained Classroom	3 (42.9)	3 (60.0)	6 (50.0)	5 (45.5)	1 (50.0)	6 (46.2)	2 (25.0)	1 (100.0)	3 (33.3)
Paraprofessional in Self-Contained Classroom	1 (14.3)	0 (0.0)	1 (8.3)	1 (9.1)	0 (0.0)	1 (7.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Support Facilitator in General Education Classroom(s)	1 (14.3)	0 (0.0)	1 (8.3)	2 (18.2)	0 (0.0)	2 (15.4)	3 (37.5)	0 (0.0)	3 (33.3)
Teacher of Small Groups in Resource Room Setting	2 (28.6)	0 (0.0)	2 (16.7)	0 (0.0)	1 (50.0)	1 (7.7)	1 (12.5)	0 (0.0)	1 (11.1)
Speech Language Pathologist	0 (0.0)	2 (40.0)	2 (16.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (12.5)	0 (0.0)	1 (11.1)
Other ^a	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (27.3)	0 (0.0)	3 (23.1)	1 (12.5)	0 (0.0)	1 (11.1)
Highest degree^b									

	2021/22			2022/23			2023/24		
	ESECP (N = 7)	Comparison (N = 5)	Total (N = 12)	ESECP (N = 11)	Comparison (N = 2)	Total (N = 13)	ESECP (N = 8)	Comparison (N = 1)	Total (N = 9)
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Associate's degree	1 (14.3)	0 (0.0)	1 (8.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Bachelor's Degree	2 (28.6)	2 (40.0)	4 (33.3)	7 (70.0)	1 (50.0)	8 (66.7)	7 (87.5)	1 (100.0)	8 (88.9)
Master's Degree	4 (57.1)	3 (60.0)	7 (58.3)	3 (30.0)	1 (50.0)	4 (33.3)	1 (12.5)	0 (0.0)	1 (11.1)

^aAll participants selecting their role as "Other" reported having multiple roles. ^bN = 12 reported their highest degree in 2022/23.

EXHIBIT C3. FLORIDA ESE PARENT SURVEY RESPONSE RATES

Cohort	School Name	ESE Membership	Completed Surveys	Response Rate (%)
Cohort 1	Carillon Elementary School	100	50	50.0
	Crystal Lake Elementary School	93	32	34.4
	Forest City Elementary School	114	43	37.7
	Geneva Elementary School	68	25	36.8
	Heathrow Elementary School	60	27	45.0
	Longwood Elementary School	92	31	33.7
	Stenstrom Elementary School	98	43	43.9
	Wicklow Elementary School	98	34	34.7
	Wilson Elementary School	111	47	42.3
	Woodlands Elementary School	104	37	35.6
	Total	938	369	39.41
Cohort 2	Bear Lake Elementary School	99	44	44.4
	Carillon Elementary School	-	-	-
	Keeth Elementary School	63	36	57.1
	Lawton Elementary School	100	48	48.0
	Rainbow Elementary School	109	60	55.0
	Red Bug Elementary School	89	36	40.4
	Sabal Point Elementary School	117	54	46.2
	Winter Springs Elementary School	83	20	24.1
	Midway Elementary School	135	39	28.9
	Partin Elementary School	69	47	68.1
	Total	864	384	45.8

Note. Bolded school names indicate intervention schools. School-level survey results were not available for Cohort 3 schools.

APPENDIX D. TECHNICAL ANALYSIS DETAILS

Baseline Equivalence. The primary analysis model used to determine baseline mean differences between the ESECP and comparison group for each analytic sample was:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Level 1} \quad & Z_{ij} = \beta_{0j} + r_{ij} \\ \text{Level 2} \quad & \beta_{0j} = \gamma_{00} + \gamma_{01} * (\text{intervention}_j) + u_{0j} \end{aligned}$$

Where:

- Z_{ij} = the standardized assessment pretest score for student i in school j ;
- β_{0j} = outcome for student i in school j in the comparison group for an average student;
- r = residual error term associated with students;

- γ_{00} = unadjusted mean pretest score for comparison schools;
- γ_{01} = coefficient associated with the average intervention effect;
- intervention = the intervention indicator (1 = intervention, 0 = comparison) in a school;
- u_{0j} = error term for schools;

Pretest scores were standardized within grade level and district. The effect size of the treatment (Hedges' g) was calculated using the following formula: $\text{Hedges}' g = \gamma_{01} / SD_{pooled}$

Impact Analyses. Research Question 4 was addressed using a series of impact models to ensure the best model fit, including a null model used to assess the intraclass correlation coefficient (Model 1)¹, a model to assess the impact estimate with covariates (Model 2), a model to assess impact estimates that trimmed non-significant covariates (Model 3), and a final model that used Model 2 to empirically identify whether or not allowing each covariate to vary improved model fit (Model 4). Model 4 was the final model which we believe produces the most accurate estimate of the treatment effect. The summary of models can be found in Exhibits D1 and D2.

The final two-level equation is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Level 1} \quad & Z_{ij} = \beta_{0j} + \beta_{1j}(\text{pretest}) + \beta_{2\dots kj}(\text{covariates}) + r_{ij} \\ \text{Level 2} \quad & \beta_{0j} = \gamma_{00} + \gamma_{01}(\text{intervention}) + u_{0j} \\ & \beta_{1j} = \gamma_{10} \\ & \beta_{2\dots kj} = \gamma_{20\dots k0} \end{aligned}$$

Where:

- Z_{ij} = the assessment posttest score for student i in classroom j ;
- β_{0j} = outcome for student i in school j in the comparison group for an average student;
- β_{1j} = coefficient associated with the pretest score;
- Pretest = the pretest assessment score;

¹ The ICC for mathematics was 0.013 and for reading was 0.017. Despite the low ICC, HLM was still used to account for the clustering of students within schools.

$\beta_{2\dots kj}$ = coefficients associated with the covariates;
covariates = a vector of student-level demographic covariates;
 r_{ij} = error term associated with students;

γ_{00} = overall mean intercept adjusted for intervention participation and covariates;
 γ_{01} = coefficient associated with the average intervention effect;
intervention = the intervention indicator (1 = intervention, 0 = comparison) in a school;
 u_{0j} = error term for schools;
 γ_{10} = average school pretest effect estimate;
 $\gamma_{20\dots k0}$ = average school-level estimates associated with the vector of covariates.

EXHIBIT D1. SUMMARY OF IMPACT MODELS: MATHEMATICS

Variables	Model 1: Null	Model 2: Impact + All Covariates	Model 3: Impact + Trimmed Covariates ^a	Model 4: Final Model ^b
Level 2				
Treatment		x	x	x
Level 1				
Pre-test		x	x	random
Grade		x	x	fixed
Gender		x	x	fixed
Nonwhite		x	x	fixed
FRL		x		
ELL		x		
Number of Exceptionalities		x	x	fixed
Number of Academic Areas Served		x	x	fixed
Number of Areas Served		x	x	fixed
Behavior		x	x	fixed

^aModel 3 retained only significant or theoretically relevant covariates.

^bModel 4 was the final impact model and included all elements of Model 3 as well as random variance components that improved the precision of estimates based on chi-square goodness of fit tests.

Note. Grade was included as set of dummy variables for grades K-5 with grade 5 as the reference group. Cohort was also included as a set of dummy variables where Cohort 3 was the reference group. Number of exceptionalities, number of academic areas, and number of areas served were grand mean centered.

EXHIBIT D2. SUMMARY OF IMPACT MODELS: READING

Variables	Model 1: Null	Model 2: Impact + All Covariates	Model 3: Impact + Trimmed Covariates ^a	Model 4: Final Model ^b
Level 2				
Treatment		x	x	x
Level 1				
Pre-test		x	x	random
Grade		x	x	fixed
Gender		x	x	fixed
Nonwhite		x	x	fixed
FRL		x	x	random
ELL		x		
Number of Exceptionalities		x	x	fixed
Number of Academic Areas Served		x	x	fixed
Number of Areas Served		x	x	random
Behavior		x	x	fixed

Note. Grade was included as set of dummy variables for grades K-5 with grade 5 as the reference group. Cohort was also included as a set of dummy variables where Cohort 3 was the reference group. Number of exceptionalities, number of academic areas, and number of areas served were grand mean centered.

^aModel 3 retained only significant or theoretically relevant covariates.

^bModel 4 was the final impact model and included all elements of Model 3 as well as random variance components that improved the precision of estimates based on chi-square goodness of fit tests.

APPENDIX E. PARENT TRAINING SUMMARY

Exhibit E1 shows the date, session title, provider, and number of participants for each session, followed by a description of a sample of sessions. The total number of participants across sessions was 147.

EXHIBIT E1. 2022 PARENT/CAREGIVER TRAINING SESSIONS

Session Date	Session Title	Provider	Number of Participants
March 1, 2022	Potty Primer	UCF Center for Autism and Related Disabilities (CARD)	30
April 4, 2022	Parent Kickoff Meeting	SCPS ESE	5
April 20, 2022	Teaching the Size of the Problem to Individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD)	CARD	30
May 10, 2022	Being Prepared for Summer	CARD	20
June 14, 2022	Building Independence at Home	CARD	23
September 20, 2022	Parent Information Session	SCPS ESE	14
October 24, 2022	Battle at Mashed Potato Hill	CARD	4
November 14, 2022	Surviving the Holidays	CARD	10
December 8, 2022	Preventing Tragedies: Must-Do Safety Steps for Families Living with ASD	CARD	11

Parent kickoff and information sessions provided an overview of the EIR grant and the ESECP. Steps taken as part of the ESECP, such as assessing students and training staff were described. Overall benefits of the ESECP were presented and included continuity across the district using an evidence-based approach, weekly on-site support from district personnel, and educators who have received extensive training on evidence-based models.

The *Potty Primer* session gave an overview of potty training for children with autistic spectrum disorder and related disabilities; provided information and skills necessary for potty training; and offered approaches that are effective and research-based to help children and parents.

Teaching the Size of the Problem to Individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) highlighted and demonstrated proven interventions that may be implemented using visual supports such as hand-drawn response scales for quantifying issues, conflicts, and emotions. The session also provided general emotional regulation techniques to instruct individuals with ASD about how to best recognize and react to the problem at hand. Examples of problems included not getting picked first in class, losing homework, and getting in an argument with a sibling.

The *Being Prepared for Summer* session covered the following topics: 1) structure, planning, and scheduling; 2) creating visual strategies for free time; 3) therapies, camps, and activities; 4) helping children with academic needs; 5) reading tips; 6) summer reading solutions; 7) general tips for math; 8) language arts; 9) free learning websites; 10) functional skills; 11), social skills; 12 building leisure skills; 13) water safety; 14) family vacations and summer guests; 15) finding summer camps and questions before choosing a camp; and 16) transitioning back to school.

Building Independence at Home focused on learning about age-appropriate chores, how to assess why children may not be doing chores, and learning strategies to help make children more independent. The

presenter discussed why chores are important, such as their contribution to independence. The session highlighted: 1) the importance of recognizing that children with ASD often have fine and gross motor deficits, challenging behaviors, and executive functioning deficits, and 2) that life skills and chores can be effectively taught through visual, positive behavior supports, and tasks that children can understand how to do.

Battle at Mashed Potato Hill covered feeding disorders and guidelines for determining if a child has a feeding problem. Types of feeding problems and how to get a child to eat, especially new foods that have different textures, were discussed. The session concluded with how parents can positively reinforce children’s feeding behavior and what to do if an intervention fails. The presenter noted that there are teams in the Seminole area, such as at Nemours Children’s Hospital, that can help with feeding problems.

Preventing Tragedies: Must-Do Safety Steps for Families Living with ASD highlighted steps families with ASD can take to minimize risks in everyday life. Individuals with ASD have a risk of mortality that is twice as high as those that do not. Persons with ASD also tend to wander and get lost. Types of protection that help families include safety proofing houses, installing locks and alarms for the entry and exit points of houses, installing gates outside, communicating with local law enforcement, using tracking devices, and participating in swimming and water safety classes.

In 2023, one ESECP parent information session was held. Eight sessions were provided by CARD and included information about visual supports in Spanish, multisensory learning techniques in math and reading for elementary-aged students, and the perils of online activity for individuals with ASD. Exhibit E2 shows the date, session title, provider, and number of participants for each session, followed by a description of a sample of sessions. The total number of participants across sessions was 123.

EXHIBIT E2. 2023 PARENT/CAREGIVER TRAINING SESSIONS

Session Date	Session Title	Provider	Number of Participants
March 22, 2023	Ayudas Visuales (Visual Supports)	CARD	12
March 29, 2023	Multisensory Learning Techniques: Math and Reading Strategies for Elementary-Aged Students	CARD	24
April 1, 2023	The Perils of Online Activity for Autism Spectrum Disorder	CARD	29
May 8, 2023	Parent Information Session	SCPS ESE	6
November 9, 2023	Teaching Children with ASD About "WH" Questions	CARD	10
November 13, 2023	Picky Eaters: Protocols to Increasing Variety	CARD	14
November 27, 2023	Dealing with Death	CARD	10
November 11, 2023	Surviving the Holidays	CARD	18

Ayudas Visuales was a workshop in Spanish that explained how to use visual supports (pictograms) to reduce problem behaviors and improve communication skills. The goal was for participants to become familiar with a variety of visual supports such as schedules, charts, and timers. Examples and strategies were offered.

Multisensory Learning Techniques: Math and Reading Strategies for Elementary-Aged Students. This presentation highlighted multisensory techniques designed to develop students' mental agility by encouraging them to use many parts of the brain which allows new concepts, skills, and strategies to

create new neural pathways and stay fixed in memory. The session emphasized the helpfulness of these techniques for teaching students identified with language-based learning differences such as dyslexia, dyscalculia, and dysgraphia. Participants learned techniques using mathematics and reading manipulatives.

The Perils of Online Activity for Autism Spectrum Disorder was for parents of children or adults with ASD who use the internet. The goal of the training was to learn the pitfalls of the internet, protect children and adults from personal and legal perils, and ways they can end up in jail or worse through social media actions, gaming platforms, chat rooms, and other places in cyberspace.

The parent information session was the same as that offered on September 20, 2022, with information about the ESECP.

In 2024, five CARD sessions were held. The CARD sessions included information for parents such as dealing with death, illness, and grief, reading strategies and supports, and safety steps to take in the home. Exhibit E3 shows the date, session title, provider, and number of participants for each session, followed by a description of a sample of sessions. More than 101 participants were involved across sessions.

EXHIBIT E3. 2024 PARENT/CAREGIVER TRAINING SESSIONS

Session Date	Session Title	Provider	Number of Participants
January 16, 2024	Construyendo Independencia	CARD	9
January 22, 2024	Understanding the Individualized Education Plan (IEP)	CARD	20
January 23, 2024	Supporting Reading Skills in & Outside the Home: Evidence Based Strategies	CARD	36
January 23, 2024	Supporting Reading Skills in and Outside the Home: Evidence Based Strategies	CARD	36
April 18, 2024	Preventing Tragedies: Must-Do Safety Steps for Families Living with ASD	CARD	Not available

Dealing with Death, Illness, and Grief for Individuals on the Spectrum focused on understanding, responding to, and supporting individuals with ASD when faced with emotionally triggering life events, such as sickness or death of a loved one or parental divorce. This seminar emphasized the varying emotional responses that individuals with ASD can experience, including delayed processing and physiological responses; strategies for support included affirming, reassuring, and providing information and routines.

Supporting Reading Skills in and Outside the Home: Evidence Based Strategies emphasized evidence-based strategies for use with different levels of readers, and reintroduced parents to ESECP. Participants were provided with information about literacy development and evidence-based reading and literacy resources that could be used at home. Information about the progression of reading development included basics of letter recognition and motivating children to learn how to read; programs/resources discussed included Headsprout and Reading Eggs.

Preventing Tragedies: Must-Do Safety Steps for Families Living with ASD centered on the facts of ASD mortality risk and what to do to protect individuals with ASD in the home. Attendees received information about wandering and elopement, which are high-risk behaviors in individuals with ASD that

can lead to missing persons reports and may result in traffic injuries, drowning, or medical intervention. Steps to take to prevent harm and injury included safety proofing the home, locks and alarms for entry and exit points, gates, communication with local law enforcement, tracking devices (such as smart watches, AirTags, or Tiles) and swimming lessons.

APPENDIX F. ESECP IMPLEMENTATION FIDELITY

EXHIBIT F1. ESECP IMPLEMENTATION FIDELITY AT DISTRICT LEVEL: COHORT 1 (2021/22)

The fidelity matrix evolved as the intervention was refined each year, and corresponding data collection varied to align with these changes. In some cases, data were not available to compute the indicator for a particular key component given that year’s definition or were not collected consistently across schools within that cohort. Any gaps in information are noted throughout the table with “Information not available.” Indicators are only included for the years in which they were part of the fidelity matrix. An * denotes an indicator that changed, was added, or had data for the first time in a particular year.

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
Key Component: ESECP Teachers on Assignment (TOA) Training & Coaching				
Prior Experience with Direct Instruction	100% of TOAs have at least one year of direct instruction teaching experience prior to hiring or project participation.	1/1		
DI Trainer Institute	100% of TOAs have attended a 5-day training institute on the topic of delivery and design of educator training prior to delivering program training.	1/1		
Coaching Academies Y1	100% of TOAs attend two 2-day Coaching Academies prior to coaching in a classroom.	0/1		As of spring 2022 all five TOAs completed Coaching Academies 1 and 2 or appropriate makeup sessions, but not all were completed prior to coaching.
Pre-Coaching Site Visits	100% of TOAs have completed at least one observation in an implementing school prior to independent coaching.	1/1		
Partner Check-ins	100% of ESECP schools have completed at least 18 weeks of weekly data tracking with SCPS resulting in submitted problem solving summary sheets.	1/1		
Coaching (ESE Teachers)	100% of TOAs have conducted at least 19 weekly coaching sessions	0/1		Two of five TOAs completed at least 19 sessions with 80%

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
	in the presence of students and groups with 100% of the academic/behavior ESE teachers that they support.			of their teachers; the other three did not.
Coaching (Paraeducators)	100% of TOAs have conducted at least 6 weekly coaching sessions in the presence of students and groups with 100% of the academic/behavior ESE teachers that they support.	0/1		Two of four TOAs who supported paraprofessionals completed at least 6 sessions with 100% of their paraeducators, the other two did not.
Site Review Training	100% of TOAs participate in site review training and achieve an inter-observer agreement of 85% prior to conducting independent site reviews.	1/1		This information was available for three of five TOAs.
All Indicators		5/8		

Key Component: ESECP Behavior Analyst (BA) Training & Coaching

Prior experience/ training in verbal behavior assessment and programming	100% of BAs have at least one year of experience in verbal behavior assessment and programming	1/1		This indicator was applicable to three of four BAs.
BA Coaches Training	100% of BAs have appropriate attendance at basic and advanced skills training prior to coaching.	1/1		This indicator was available for three of four BAs; each completed full attendance at training prior to providing coaching.
Basic Skills Training Y1	100% of BAs complete the basic skills training prior to Y1.	1/1		This indicator was available for three of four BAs; each completed full attendance at training prior to providing coaching.
BA Training	100% of BAs have completed training for the trainings they provide.	1/1		This indicator was applicable to two BAs who were in their second year of implementing in an ESECP school.

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
Pre-Coaching Site Visits	100% of BAs have completed at least one observation in an implementing school prior to independent coaching.	1/1		
Partner Check-ins	100% of BAs have completed at least 6 months of data analysis meetings with SCPS resulting in submitted problem solving summary sheets.	0/1		This indicator was applicable for three of four BAs.
Coaching (ESE Teachers)	100% of BAs have conducted at least 19 weekly coaching sessions in the presence of students and groups with 100% of the developmental/medical ¹ ESE teachers that they support.	0/1		This indicator was applicable for three of four BAs. Each had less than 18 logs for each of the ESE teachers they supported.
Coaching (Paraeducators)	100% of BAs have conducted at least 19 weekly coaching sessions in the presence of students and groups with 100% of the developmental/medical ESE teachers that they support.	0/1		This indicator was applicable for three of four BAs. They did not meet this threshold.
Site Review Training	100% of BAs participate in site review training and achieve an inter-observer agreement of 85% prior to conducting independent site reviews.	1/1		This information was available for one BA.
All Indicators		6/9		

Key Component: Administrator Training & Engagement

Pre-implementation Meeting	100% of schools have a principal and least one assistant principal attend	0/1		Two of four schools met this requirement.
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¹ BAs typically support ESE classrooms for students in the developmental or medical curriculum circles. The definition for this indicator changed in subsequent years.

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
	a pre-implementation meeting prior to project implementation or within 9 weeks of hiring/reassignment into an ESECP school for the first time			
Collaborative Agreement	100% of appropriate administrators sign collaborative agreements prior to project implementation (the principal and at least one assistant principal).	0/1		One person at two of four schools signed the agreement. There is no record of signatures on the collaborative agreement from the other two schools (although they were not consistently collected).
Administrator Institute	100% of appropriate administrators attend the 1-day training to ensure that participants can support the implementation of DI successfully (principals, assistant principals, and instructional leaders should be included).	1/1		
All Indicators		1/3		Only one administrator completed all training and coaching activities.

Key Component: ESE Instructor Training

School Visits (Instructors)	In 100% of schools, 100% of appropriate ESE instructors visited a school implementing the curriculum project before the end of the first 9 weeks of the school year.	0/1		13 of 23 (56%) appropriate educators attended a school visit. In two schools, 80% of appropriate educators attended a school visit. In one school, 56% of appropriate educators attended a school visit. In the fourth school, no appropriate educators attended a school visit.
Pre-service Training for Academic Instructors	In 100% of schools, at least 80% of appropriate ESE instructors attend the 5-day training prior to the school year or 2 days of backup training within the first month of school/hire.	0/1		One school met this threshold; 83% of appropriate ESE instructors had appropriate pre-service training. Another school had 75% of appropriate ESE instructors meet this goal. Less than 50% of appropriate

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
				ESE instructors met this goal in the other two schools.
Pre-service Training for Developmental Instructors	In 100% of schools, 100% of appropriate developmental instructors attend the backup training and/or at least 2 days of pre-service training within the first month of school/hire.	0/1		Three schools had developmental educators; 67% of educators in one school met this training goal; 50% in another school met this training goal, and no educators in another school met this goal.
All Indicators		0/3		
Key Component: Parent Training & Communication				
Parent Training Sessions	At least three parent training sessions are held by the district on topics determined by parent needs.	2/2		A total of six parent training sessions were held.
Parent Information Night	A parent information meeting that provides an overview of Exceptional Student Education Curriculum Project with parents is held for 100% of participating schools.	1/1		A district-wide parent information night was held.
All Indicators		2/3		

 = Threshold met.

EXHIBIT F2. ESECP IMPLEMENTATION FIDELITY AT DISTRICT LEVEL: COHORT 2 (2022/23)

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
Key Component: ESECP Teachers on Assignment (TOA) Training & Coaching				
Prior Experience with Direct Instruction	100% of TOAs have at least one year of direct instruction teaching experience prior to hiring or project participation.	1/1		
DI Trainer Institute	100% of TOAs that provide training have attended a 5-day training	1/1		

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
	institute on the topic of delivery and design of educator training prior to delivering program training.			
Coaching Academies Y1	100% of TOAs attend two 2-day Coaching Academies prior to coaching in a classroom.	1/1		
Pre-Coaching Site Visits	100% of TOAs have completed at least one observation in an implementing school prior to independent coaching.	--		Information not available.
Partner Check-ins	100% of ESECP schools have completed at least 18 weeks of weekly data tracking with SCPS resulting in submitted problem solving summary sheets.	--		Information not available.
*Sharing of PSS results	100% of schools have shared 68% or more of problem solving summary sheets with administrators	1/1		
Coaching (ESE Teachers)	100% of TOAs have conducted at least 19 weekly coaching sessions in the presence of students and groups with 100% of the academic/behavior ESE teachers that they support.	0/1		No TOA completed at least 19 coaching sessions.
Coaching (Paraeducators)	100% of TOAs have conducted at least 6 weekly coaching sessions in the presence of students and groups with 100% of the academic/behavior ESE teachers that they support.	0/1		One of three TOAs who supported paraprofessionals completed at least 6 sessions with 100% of their paraeducators; the other two did.
Site Review Training	100% of TOAs participate in site review training and achieve an inter-observer	--	Not applicable	This information was not applicable as all participating

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
	agreement of 85% prior to conducting independent site reviews.			TOAs had been trained in prior years.
All Indicators		4/6		
Key Component: ESECP Behavior Analyst (BA) Training & Coaching				
Prior experience/training in verbal behavior assessment and programming	100% of BAs have at least one year of experience in verbal behavior assessment and programming	1/1		
BA Coaches Training	100% of BAs have appropriate attendance at basic and advanced skills training prior to coaching.	1/1		
Basic Skills Training Y1	100% of BAs complete the basic skills training prior to Y1.	1/1		This indicator was available for three of four BAs; each completed full attendance at training prior to providing coaching.
BA Training	100% of BAs have completed training for the trainings they provide.	--	--	This indicator was missing or not applicable (BAs were not in Year 2 or 3) for each of the four BAs.
Pre-Coaching Site Visits	100% of BAs have completed at least one observation in an implementing school prior to independent coaching.	--	--	This information was not applicable as all participating BAs had been trained in prior years.
Partner check-ins	100% of BAs have completed at least 6 months of data analysis meetings with SCPS resulting in submitted problem solving summary sheets.	--	--	Information not available.
Coaching (ESE Teachers)	100% of BAs have conducted at least 19 weekly coaching sessions in the presence of students and groups with 100% of the developmental/medical	0/1		Two of four BAs met this threshold; the other two were missing data.

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
	ESE teachers that they support.			
Coaching (Paraeducators)	100% of BAs have conducted at least 19 weekly coaching sessions in the presence of students and groups with 100% of the developmental/medical ESE teachers that they support.	0/1		These data were available for two of four BAs; they did not meet this threshold.
Site Review Training	100% of BAs participate in site review training and achieve an inter-observer agreement of 85% prior to conducting independent site reviews.	--	--	Information not available.
All Indicators		3/5		

Key Component: Administrator Training & Engagement

Pre-implementation meeting	100% of schools have a principal and least one assistant principal attend a pre-implementation meeting prior to project implementation or within 9 weeks of hiring/reassignment into an ESECP school for the first time	1/1		Seven of ten administrators met this requirement; the other three were missing this information. This resulted in two schools for which this indicator was applicable meeting the threshold.
Collaborative agreement	100% of appropriate administrators sign collaborative agreements prior to project implementation (the principal and at least one assistant principal).	0/1		There is no record of signatures on the collaborative agreement from appropriate administrators.
Administrator institute	100% of appropriate administrators attend the 1-day training to ensure that participants can support the implementation of DI successfully (principals, assistant principals, and	1/1		Six of ten appropriate administrators attended the training, resulting in three of four schools meeting this threshold (the threshold was not applicable for the fourth school).

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
	instructional leaders should be included).			
*Classroom walkthrough with administrators	TOAs and/or BAs and instructional leadership team members conduct monthly classroom walkthroughs in ESECP classrooms	0/1		Five of seven appropriate administrators conducted walkthroughs.
*Attendance at mid-year PSS meeting	Instructional leadership team members attend the mid-year PSS meeting	0/1		Eight of nine appropriate administrators attended the mid-year PSS meeting.
*Attendance at progressive action meetings when requested	Instructional leadership team members attend progressive action meetings when requested	0/1		This data point was not available for eight of ten administrators; two other administrators did not attend progressive action meetings when requested.
All Indicators		2/6		

Key Component: ESE Instructor Training

*Pre-implementation meeting	In 100% of schools, 80% or more of appropriate ESE instructors attend a pre-implementation or makeup meeting in the fall	0/1		Three of four educators for whom this information was tracked attended a pre-implementation meeting. The other thirty educators were missing this information.
School Visits (instructors)	In 100% of schools, 100% of appropriate ESE instructors visited a school implementing the curriculum project before the end of the first 9 weeks of the school year.	0/1		Information not available.
Pre-service training for academic instructors	In 100% of schools, at least 80% of appropriate ESE instructors attend the 5-day training prior to the school year or 2 days of backup training within the first month of school/hire.	0/1		One school met this threshold; 80% of appropriate ESE instructors had appropriate pre-service training. Another school had 67% of appropriate ESE instructors meet this goal. Fifty percent or less of appropriate ESE instructors met this goal in the other two schools.

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
Pre-service training for developmental instructors	In 100% of schools, 100% of appropriate developmental instructors attend the backup training and/or at least 2 days of pre-service training within the first month of school/hire.	0/1		Three schools had developmental educators; 33% of educators in one school met this training goal; 25% in another school met this training goal, and no educators in another school met this goal.
All Indicators		0/4		
Key Component: Parent Training & Communication				
Parent training sessions	At least three parent training sessions are held by the district on topics determined by parent needs.	2/2		Seven parent training sessions were held.
Parent Information Night	A parent information meeting that provides an overview of Exceptional Student Education Curriculum Project with parents is held for 100% of participating schools.	1/1		Two district-wide parent information nights were held to provide this information.
*Parent Curriculum Night	A parent curriculum night that provides an overview of the ESECP curriculum in which their child will participate is held for parents at each school.	1/1		Two district-wide parent information nights were held to provide this information.
All Indicators		4/4		
*Key Component: District Monitoring and Support				
*Site Review Screening - Spring	At least 90% of academic and developmental sites (classrooms/educators) screened in the spring per the site review screening guidelines to determine if site reviews should happen.	1/1		This year was a trial run.
*Site Review Inter-Observer Agreement (IOA)- Fall	Project leadership verifies that IOA continues to meet acceptable thresholds for at least 85% of sites.	1/2		

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
*Site Review IOA- Spring	Project leadership verifies that IOA continues to meet acceptable thresholds for at least 85% of sites.	2/2		
All Indicators		4/5		

 = Threshold met.

EXHIBIT F3. ESECP IMPLEMENTATION FIDELITY AT DISTRICT LEVEL: COHORT 3 (2023/24)

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
Key Component: ESECP Teachers on Assignment (TOA) Training & Coaching				
Prior Experience with Direct Instruction	100% of TOAs have at least one year of direct instruction teaching experience prior to hiring or project participation.	1/1		
DI Trainer Institute	100% of TOAs that provide training have attended a 5-day training institute on the topic of delivery and design of educator training prior to delivering program training.	1/1		
Coaching Academies Y1	100% of TOAs attend two 2-day Coaching Academies prior to coaching in a classroom.	1/1		
Pre-Coaching Site Visits	100% of TOAs have completed at least one observation in an implementing school prior to independent coaching.	1/1		
Partner Check-ins	100% of ESECP schools have completed at least 18 weeks of weekly data tracking with SCPS resulting in submitted	1/1		Two of three schools met this criteria for the entire year. One school started late and completed 15 check-ins which met expectations.

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
	problem solving summary sheets.			
Sharing of PSS Results	100% of schools have shared 68% or more of problem-solving summary sheets with administrators	1/1		
Coaching (ESE Teachers)	100% of TOAs have conducted at least 19 weekly coaching sessions in the presence of students and groups with 100% of the academic/behavior ESE teachers that they support.	0/1		One TOA completed at least 19 coaching sessions; one TOA did not.
Coaching (Paraeducators)	100% of TOAs have conducted at least 6 weekly coaching sessions in the presence of students and groups with 100% of the academic/behavior ESE teachers that they support.	0/1		One of two TOAs who supported paraprofessionals completed at least 6 sessions with 100% of their paraeducators; the other one did not.
Site Review Training	100% of TOAs participate in site review training and achieve an inter-observer agreement of 85% prior to conducting independent site reviews.	1/1		
Site Review	Fall and spring site reviews have been completed for 100% of eligible academic/behavior sites (classroom or educator) at the time of site reviews.	1/1		
All Indicators		8/10		

Key Component: ESECP Behavior Analyst (BA) Training & Coaching

Prior Experience/ Training in	100% of BAs have at least one year of experience in verbal behavior	1/1		
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Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
Verbal Behavior Assessment and Programming	assessment and programming			
BA Coaches Training	100% of BAs have appropriate attendance at basic and advanced skills training prior to coaching.	0/1		The two BAs were in their second year of ESECP. Both completed full attendance (3 days) at basic skills training but only one completed early or advanced learner training prior to providing coaching.
Basic Skills Training Y1	100% of BAs complete the basic skills training prior to Y1.	1/1		
BA Training	100% of BAs have completed training for the trainings they provide.	0/1		One BA met this threshold for implementation.
Pre-Coaching Site Visits	100% of BAs have completed at least one observation in an implementing school prior to independent coaching.	1/1		
Partner Check-ins	100% of BAs have completed at least 6 months of data analysis meetings with SCPS resulting in submitted problem solving summary sheets.	0/1		One BA completed five months of data analysis meetings, the other completed four months.
Coaching (ESE Teachers)	100% of BAs have conducted at least 19 weekly coaching sessions in the presence of students and groups with 100% of the developmental/medical ESE teachers that they support.	0/1		One of two BAs met this threshold for implementation.
Coaching (Paraeducators)	100% of BAs have conducted at least 19 weekly coaching sessions in the presence of students and groups with 100% of the developmental/medical	0/1		One BA had fewer than five logs for all paraeducators they supported; another BA had at least six for all paraeducators they supported.

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
	ESE teachers that they support.			
Site Review Training	100% of BAs participate in site review training and achieve an inter-observer agreement of 85% prior to conducting independent site reviews.	1/1		
Site Review	Fall and spring site reviews have been completed for 100% of eligible academic/behavior sites (classroom or educator) at the time of site reviews.	1/1		
All Indicators		5/10		

Key Component: Administrator Training & Engagement

Pre-implementation Meeting	100% of schools have a principal and least one assistant principal attend a pre-implementation meeting prior to project implementation or within 9 weeks of hiring/reassignment into an ESECP school for the first time	0/1		One of three schools had only a principal attend the pre-implementation meeting, but not the assistant principal. The school that did not meet the threshold was the school that started late. The other two schools met this threshold.
Collaborative Agreement	100% of appropriate administrators sign collaborative agreements prior to project implementation (the principal and at least one assistant principal).	0/1		Only one administrator signed the collaborative agreement.
Administrator Institute	100% of appropriate administrators attend the 1-day training to ensure	0/1		One school (two administrators) met the threshold for adequate

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
	that participants can support the implementation of DI successfully (principals, assistant principals, and instructional leaders should be included).			implementation. The other two schools did not.
Classroom Walkthrough with Administrators	TOAs and/or BAs and instructional leadership team members conduct monthly classroom walkthroughs in ESECP classrooms	0/1		One school met this threshold with four walkthroughs. The other two schools had only two months of walkthroughs with appropriate administrator(s).
Attendance at Mid-year PSS Meeting	Instructional leadership team members attend the mid-year PSS meeting	1/1		This indicator was only applicable for the two schools that started at the beginning of the year.
Attendance at Progressive Action Meetings when Requested	Instructional leadership team members attend progressive action meetings when requested	0/1		Two of six administrators attended progressing action meetings when requested.
All Indicators		1/6		
Key Component: ESE Instructor Training				
*Pre-Implementation Meeting	In 100% of schools, 80% or more of appropriate ESE instructors attend a pre-implementation or makeup meeting in the fall	0/1		Fewer than 50% of educators in all three schools attended a pre-implementation meeting.
School Visits (Instructors)	In 100% of schools, 100% of appropriate ESE instructors visited a school implementing the curriculum project before the end of the first 9 weeks of the school year.	0/1		Three educators met this criteria, no school had all relevant educators meet this threshold for implementation.
Pre-service Training for Academic Instructors	In 100% of schools, at least 80% of appropriate ESE instructors attend the 5-day training prior to the school year or 2 days of backup training within the first month of school/hire.	0/1		In one school, 71% of appropriate ESE instructors attended pre-service training; another school had 41%; and the school that started late did not have any instructors attend the training on time.

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
Pre-Service Training for Developmental Instructors	In 100% of schools, 100% of appropriate developmental instructors attend the backup training and/or at least 2 days of pre-service training within the first month of school/hire.	0/1		Two schools had developmental educators; seven percent of educators in one school met this training goal; none in another school met this training goal.
*Ongoing Training	In 100% of schools, 100% of appropriate ESE instructors have 4 to 7 months of logs with practice indicated.	0/1		No educators had more than three months of logs with practice indicated.
*Collaborative Agreement	In 100% of schools, 100% of appropriate ESE instructors have attended a meeting and signed the collaborative agreement within the first semester of implementation.	0/1		At one school, 67% of appropriate ESE instructors signed this agreement; at another school, 40% of appropriate ESE instructors signed this agreement; and at the school that had a late start, all appropriate ESE instructors signed the agreement.
All Indicators		0/6		
Key Component: Parent Training & Communication				
Parent Training Sessions	At least three parent training sessions are held by the district on topics determined by parent needs.	2/2		Nine parent training sessions were held.
Parent Information Night	A parent information meeting that provides an overview of Exceptional Student Education Curriculum Project with parents is held for 100% of participating schools.	1/1		Two schools held a parent information night; one school that started late did not. Recordings were available on request.
*Parent Curriculum Night	A parent curriculum night that provides an overview of the ESECP curriculum in which their child will participate is held for parents at each school.	1/1		
All Indicators		4/4		

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
Key Component: District Monitoring and Support				
*Mentors are Assigned to new TOAs and BAs	100% of new TOAs and BAs are assigned an experienced mentor (experienced TOA/BA or coach, project leadership, or other designee) to mentor them during their first year of implementation	1/1		
*TOA Mentorship	TOA mentors (experienced TOA or coach, project leadership, or other designee) are scheduled to be in the classroom with first year TOAs during coaching to model, observe, and provide feedback on coaching skills for at least 80% of new TOAs	0/1		
*BA Mentorship	BA mentors (experienced BA or coach, project leadership, or other designee) are scheduled to be in the classroom with Y1 BAs during coaching to model, observe, and provide feedback on coaching skills for at least 80% of Year 1 BAs	--	--	Not applicable. All BAs were in at least their second year.
*Site Review Screening - Fall	At least 90% of academic and developmental sites (classrooms/educators) screened in the fall per the site review screening guidelines to determine if site reviews should happen.	1/1		
Site Review Screening - Spring	At least 90% of academic and developmental sites (classrooms/educators) screened in the spring per the site review screening guidelines to determine if site reviews should happen.	1/1		

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
*Site Review Scheduling -Fall	Project leadership establishes the window for completing site reviews ensuring that at least 8% of site reviews are conducted by two TOAs or BAs.	1/1		
Site Review IOA-Fall	Project leadership verifies that IOA continues to meet acceptable thresholds for at least 85% of sites.	2/2		
Site Review IOA-Spring	Project leadership verifies that IOA continues to meet acceptable thresholds for at least 85% of sites.	2/2		
*ESE Classroom Coverage	For all unfilled ESE positions, ESE responsibilities are coordinated using the checklist that is completed with the instructional leadership team within 4 weeks.	0/1		
*Teacher Support Matrix	TOAs and BAs complete the Teacher Support Matrix for each educator they support prior to the beginning of the academic year or within one month of hire.	0/1		
*TOA/BA Positions Filled based on the Teacher Support Matrix	At least 90% of TOA and BA FTE time is allocated to support educator needs (when possible, based on the Teacher Support Matrix).	1/1		Although the Teacher Support Matrix was not completed, project leadership reported this indicator and threshold were met.
*TOA/BA Assignments	In 100% of schools, TOAs/BAs are scheduled to support educators within a school for at least 90% of the amount of time recommended (when possible, based on the results of the Teacher Support Matrix) by the	1/1		Not tracked using the Teacher Support Matrix, although it was noted that 9.5 days/week were allocated for TOAs and BAs to support ESECP schools which was appropriate.

Indicator	Definition	District Score	Implementation Threshold Met	Notes
	end of the first month of school			
*Monitor Progress	Project leadership or designee attend at least 50% of problem solving summary (PSS) meetings with schools to monitor progress.	0/1		
*Response to Problems	Project leadership or designee attends at least 90% of PSS meetings based on the progressive action flow chart.	--	--	Not applicable (no progressive action meetings).
*Progressive Action Monitoring	Project leadership or designee monitors that progressive action steps are followed through bi-monthly discussions.	--	--	Not applicable (no progressive action meetings).
All Indicators		10/14		

 = Threshold met.

APPENDIX G. SITE REVIEW DETAILS

Site Review scores by cohort are presented below. Academic site reviews are scored on a scale from *Not Implemented* (0) to *Fully Implemented* (3). The mean implementation score represents the percentage of targeted components that were implemented in the classroom. Developmental site reviews are scored no/yes (0/1). The mean implementation score represents the percentage of targeted components that were implemented in the classroom.

EXHIBIT G1. ESECP CLASSROOM LEVEL IMPLEMENTATION: ALL COHORT 1 SCHOOLS 2021/22

	Mean Percent			
	Academic (n = 20)		Developmental (n = 5)	
	Fall	Winter	Fall	Winter
Classroom Organization	48.7	56.4	50.5	50.0
Classroom Environment	85.5	87.2	100.0	100.0
Arrangement of Materials	3.0	3.0	67.0	89.0
Data Systems	76.9	88.5	25.0	48.2
Training and Consultation	51.3	64.1	75.0	41.7
Parent/Family Engagement	46.2	73.1	50.0	33.3
Inclusive Practices	56.4	51.3	44.4	22.2
Instruction	65.0	65.7	83.3	33.3
Behavior Interventions	43.8	58.3	0.0	66.7
Social Skills	--	--	0.0	0.0
MAND Training	--	--	17.0	33.0
Intensive Teaching	--	--	63.0	54.0
Natural Environment Teaching	--	--	13.0	27.0
Other Instructional Methods	--	--	50.0	50.0
Total Percent Implementation	60.9	67.8	44.0	47.3

-- indicates scores were not available. Some scores were not relevant for academic indicators. Group Instruction (only applicable for developmental sites) was indicated as not available at any time point and is excluded from this exhibit.

EXHIBIT G2. ESECP CLASSROOM LEVEL IMPLEMENTATION: ALL COHORT 2 SCHOOLS 2022/23

	Mean Percent			
	Academic		Developmental	
	Fall (<i>n</i> = 11)	Winter (<i>n</i> = 14)	Fall (<i>n</i> = 2)	Winter (<i>n</i> = 2)
Classroom Organization	51.5	65.5	50.0	87.5
Classroom Environment	88.9	85.5	66.7	100.0
Arrangement of Materials	3.0	3.0	67.0	100.0
Data Systems	86.4	92.9	31.3	70.1
Training and Consultation	24.2	64.3	0.0	100.0
Parent/Family Engagement	36.4	32.1	75.0	75.0
Inclusive Practices	78.8	77.8	16.7	50.0
Instruction	60.3	64.3	100.0	100.0
Behavior Interventions	60.0	100.0	50.0	100.0
Social Skills	--	--	0.0	0.0
MAND Training	--	--	8.0	58.0
Intensive Teaching	--	--	13.0	63.0
Natural Environment Teaching	--	--	20.0	50.0
Other Instructional Methods	--	--	25.0	50.0
Total Percent Implementation	58.6	68.4	31.3	71.1

-- indicates scores were not available. Some scores were not relevant for academic indicators. Group Instruction (only applicable for developmental sites) was indicated as not available at any time point and is excluded from this exhibit.

EXHIBIT G3. ESECP CLASSROOM LEVEL IMPLEMENTATION: ALL COHORT 3 SCHOOLS 2023/24

	Mean Percent			
	Academic		Developmental	
	Fall (n = 8)	Winter (n = 12)	Fall (n = 1)	Winter (n = 2)
Classroom Organization	77.1	79.2	25.0	37.5
Classroom Environment	87.5	97.2	100.0	100.0
Arrangement of Materials	3.0	3.0	0.0	83.0
Data Systems	93.8	100.0	12.5	77.8
Training and Consultation	75.0	66.7	0.0	75.0
Parent/Family Engagement	68.8	95.8	50.0	25.0
Inclusive Practices	95.2	90.0	33.3	50.0
Instruction	69.3	79.6	0.0	75.0
Behavior Interventions	90.0	100.0	0.0	100.0
Social Skills	--	--	0.0	0.0
MAND Training	--	--	0.0	25.0
Intensive Teaching	--	--	0.0	63.0
Natural Environment Teaching	--	--	0.0	10.0
Other Instructional Methods	--	--	0.0	100.0
Total Percent Implementation	77.1	83.6	13.2	56.6

-- indicates scores were not available. Some scores were not relevant for academic indicators. Group Instruction (only applicable for developmental sites) was indicated as not available at any time point and is excluded from this exhibit.

APPENDIX H. ADDITIONAL IMPACT FINDINGS

EXHIBIT H1. ESECP IMPACT ON IREADY MATHEMATICS SUBTESTS AFTER 1, 2, AND 3 YEARS

Outcome	Students (<i>n</i>)	Coefficient	<i>SE</i>	Significance
One Year				
Overall	1,108	-2.10	1.32	ns
Number Operations	1,108	-2.18	1.65	ns
Algebraic Thinking	1,108	-2.26	1.69	ns
Measurement	1,108	-2.54	1.72	ns
Geometry	1,108	-2.23	1.77	ns
Two Years				
Overall	442	0.51	2.17	ns
Number Operations	442	-0.14	2.73	ns
Algebraic Thinking	442	3.12	2.69	ns
Measurement	441	0.97	2.82	ns
Geometry	442	-1.54	2.82	ns
Three Years				
Overall	194	-6.12	4.53	ns
Number Operations	205	-5.21	5.67	ns
Algebraic Thinking	205	-9.41	4.82	ns
Measurement	194	-2.39	5.27	ns
Geometry	194	-6.13	5.11	ns

Note. Each subset was examined using a separate model with the subtest score as the outcome and the same set of predictors used in the final impact estimate models. ns=nonsignificant.

EXHIBIT H2. ESECP IMPACT ON iREADY READING SUBTESTS AFTER 1, 2, AND 3 YEARS

Outcome	Students (n)	Coefficient	SE	Significance
One Year				
Overall	1,198	-4.32	2.63	ns
Phonological Awareness	268	-12.65	5.90	*
Phonics	713	-7.29	3.81	ns
High Frequency Words	434	-8.47	5.52	ns
Vocabulary	1,198	-5.33	2.87	ns
Comp Lit	1,198	-4.94	3.63	ns
Comp Informational Text	1,198	-3.29	3.47	ns
Two Year				
Overall	534	-3.30	3.47	ns
Phonological Awareness	73	6.07	11.00	ns
Phonics	299	1.56	6.50	ns
High Frequency Words	138	6.28	11.59	ns
Vocabulary	533	-1.33	3.87	ns
Comp Lit	533	-0.78	4.32	ns
Comp Informational Text	533	-8.80	5.11	ns
Three Year				
Overall	240	-4.37	6.57	ns
Phonological Awareness	--	--	--	--
Phonics	99	15.15	14.87	ns
High Frequency Words	36	11.92	15.81	ns
Vocabulary	240	-1.00	7.43	ns
Comp Lit	240	-9.28	6.75	ns
Comp Informational Text	240	-5.91	6.67	ns

Note. Each subset was examined using a separate model with the subtest score as the outcome and the same set of predictors used in the final impact estimate models. One exception was that the models for the phonological awareness subtest excluded grades 3-5. ns=nonsignificant.

APPENDIX I

This appendix contains detailed educator survey findings for each component within overall satisfaction and preparedness.

EXHIBIT I1. AVERAGE CHANGES IN EDUCATOR SATISFACTION

	ESECP						Comparison		
	After 1 Year (N=16)			After 2 Years (N=9)			After 1 Year (N=5)		
	Fall	Spring	Difference	Fall	Spring	Difference	Fall	Spring	Difference
Overall Satisfaction	2.87	3.01	0.14	3.15	3.35	0.20	2.76	2.73	-0.03
Availability of resources to meet student needs	2.78	3.33	0.55	3.38	3.35	-0.03	2.40	2.75	0.35
Class sizes/caseloads	2.50	2.39	-0.11	2.93	3.15	0.23	2.40	2.25	-0.15
Support from administrators	2.89	2.95	0.06	3.48	3.70	0.23	3.20	3.50	0.30
Presence of knowledgeable paraeducators	3.06	3.33	0.27	3.23	3.00	-0.23	3.20	2.75	-0.45
Having a principal who is a strong instructional leader	3.11	3.00	-0.11	3.38	3.60	0.23	3.00	3.25	0.25
Professional learning opportunities	2.95	2.84	-0.11	2.78	2.85	0.08	2.80	3.00	0.20
Extent of paperwork	2.39	2.82	0.43	3.08	3.25	0.18	2.40	1.75	-0.65
Access to related service personnel	3.17	3.22	0.06	3.28	3.60	0.33	3.20	3.50	0.30
Access to technology (including technical support)	2.48	3.00	0.52	3.25	3.10	-0.15	2.60	3.25	0.65
Opportunities to collaborate with colleagues	2.77	3.00	0.23	2.45	3.20	0.75	2.40	2.75	0.35
Opportunities to plan instruction	2.72	2.78	0.06	3.00	3.15	0.15	2.00	2.00	0.00
Your relationship with co-workers	3.22	3.39	0.17	3.68	3.90	0.23	3.20	3.00	-0.20
Support and encouragement from co-workers	3.06	3.28	0.22	3.20	3.40	0.20	2.80	2.75	-0.05
Student behavior in your school	2.94	2.84	-0.11	3.00	3.20	0.20	2.60	2.25	-0.35
Student discipline in your school	2.61	2.89	0.28	3.00	2.80	-0.20	3.00	2.25	-0.75
Support from parents	3.09	3.09	0.00	3.20	3.60	0.40	3.00	2.75	-0.25

Note. Item scales ranged from 1 (Very Dissatisfied) to 4 (Very Satisfied). The computed scale scores are highlighted. Results were combined across years and cohorts. $N_{ESECP1Yr} = 16$ (7 for 2021/22, 6 for 2022/23, 3 for 2023/24). $N_{Comparison} = 5$ for 2021/22). Fewer than 5 educators responded from comparison schools during subsequent years, so results are excluded.

EXHIBIT I2. AVERAGE CHANGES IN EDUCATOR PREPAREDNESS

	ESECP						Comparison		
	After 1 Year (N=16)			After 2 Years (N=9)			After 1 Year (N=5)		
	Fall	Spring	Difference	Fall	Spring	Difference	Fall	Spring	Difference
Overall Preparedness	3.26	3.44	0.18	3.57	3.83	0.26	3.50	3.62	0.12
Instructional Preparedness	3.25	3.61	0.36	3.58	3.82	0.25	3.40	3.63	0.23
To identify student learning goals	3.19	3.71	0.52	3.38	3.90	0.53	3.60	3.80	0.20
To prioritize learning goals	3.11	3.42	0.31	3.13	3.90	0.78	3.40	3.80	0.40
To adapt curriculum for specific learning goals	3.30	3.66	0.36	3.13	3.60	0.48	3.80	3.60	-0.20
To teach cognitive and metacognitive strategies to support student learning	3.21	3.55	0.33	3.68	3.70	0.03	3.00	3.40	0.40
To provide scaffolded supports	3.40	3.78	0.37	3.68	3.90	0.23	3.40	3.60	0.20
To use flexible grouping	3.29	3.53	0.24	3.68	4.00	0.33	3.40	3.60	0.20
To use strategies that promote active student engagement	3.25	3.28	0.03	3.55	3.74	0.19	3.60	3.80	0.20
To use assistive and instructional technologies	3.20	3.45	0.25	3.58	3.50	-0.08	3.00	3.40	0.40
To provide intensive instruction	3.25	3.73	0.48	3.68	3.90	0.23	3.60	3.40	-0.20
To provide constructive feedback to guide student learning	3.21	3.55	0.35	3.55	3.90	0.35	3.60	3.80	0.20
To use student assessment data to make adjustments designed to improve student outcomes	3.15	3.57	0.42	3.43	3.90	0.48	3.60	3.60	0.00
To examine instructional practices and make adjustments designed to improve student outcomes	3.36	3.61	0.25	3.58	3.80	0.23	3.60	3.60	0.00
To collaborate with professionals to increase student success	3.48	3.51	0.03	3.68	3.90	0.23	3.60	3.80	0.20
To collaborate with families to support student success	3.21	3.78	0.57	3.38	3.90	0.53	3.60	3.40	-0.20
To establish an organized learning environment	3.59	3.73	0.14	3.78	3.80	0.03	3.40	3.60	0.20
To establish a respectful learning environment	3.68	3.78	0.10	3.75	3.80	0.05	3.80	3.80	0.00
To provide positive feedback to guide student behavior	3.52	3.51	-0.01	3.75	3.90	0.15	3.60	3.80	0.20
To implement student behavior plans	3.31	3.40	0.09	3.80	3.80	0.00	3.40	3.40	0.00

Note. Item scales ranged from 1 (Not at all prepared) to 4 (Well prepared). The computed scale scores are highlighted. Results were combined across years and cohorts. $N_{ESECP1Yr} = 16$ (7 for 2021/22, 6 for 2022/23, 3 for 2023/24). $N_{Comparison} = 5$ for 2021/22). Fewer than 5 educators responded from comparison schools during subsequent years, so results are excluded.

